

HORIZON 2020

The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation

Project acronym: procuRE

Grant Agreement Number: 963648

Project full title: Pre-commercial Procurement of Breakthrough Solutions for
100% Renewable Energy Supply in Buildings

Call identifier: H2020-LC-SC3-2020-Joint-Actions-1

D7.5 procuRE Pilot Outcomes

Version: 1.1

Status: Final

Dissemination Level: Public

Submission Date: 18 November 2025

Work Package: WP7 Evaluation & Impact Assessment

Lead partner for this deliverable: PORTO

Partners contributing: ALL

Main authors:

João Encarnação

Federico Trentin

Elad Topel

Touraj Ashrafiyan

Patrick Bradley

Georg Vogt

PORTO

EURAC

EILAT

OZU

NUREMBERG

EMP

Alexander Cuartas-Acosta

Sefer Meşe

Niko Natek

Sašo Mozgan

Alexander Nordhus

Marta Pascual Gavalda

EMP

ISTANBUL

KSSENA

KSSENA

NUREMBERG

AMB

Abstract

The document contains the full report on the evaluation results of the procuRE pilots. The deliverable incorporates results from Tasks 7.4, 7.5 and 7.6.

Revision History

Version	Date	Changes made	Authors
0.1	13.12.2024	First draft version	Petr Popov (EMP)
0.2	14.02.2025	Reviewed and provided input and comments	João Encarnação (PORTO)
0.3	20.04.2025	Procurers' first input	All
0.5	15.07.2025	Procurers' revised input	All
0.9	20.07.2025	Peer review	Niko Natek (KSSENA)
1.0	30.07.2025	Final version submitted	João Encarnação (PORTO)
1.1	18.11.2025	Additions and revisions based on review meeting	All

Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	Introduction	9
2	Pilot testing overview	10
2.1	Objectives of pilot testing	10
2.2	Organisation of pilot testing	10
2.3	Overview of demonstration pilot sites	11
2.3.1	Barcelona, Spain (SEBR)	13
2.3.2	Eilat, Israel (PARadISE)	20
2.3.3	Istanbul, Turkey (PARadISE)	32
2.3.4	Nuremberg, Germany (SEBR)	41
2.3.5	Velenje, Slovenia (PARadISE)	47
2.3.6	Villa Nova de Gaia, Portugal (SEBR)	63
3	Testing methodology	69
3.1	Building performance	69
3.1.1	Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	69
3.1.2	BMS, sensors and other data collection tools to ensure continuous performance	70
3.1.3	Smart Readiness Indicators (SRI) assessment	71
3.2	User experience	72
3.2.1	Co-design process for procurers	72
3.2.2	Survey for operators	73
4	Pilot outcomes	75
4.1	Building performance	75
4.1.1	Nuremberg, Germany (SEBR)	76
4.1.2	Barcelona, Spain (SEBR)	87
4.1.3	Vila Nova de Gaia, Portugal (SEBR)	96
4.1.4	Velenje, Slovenia (PARadISE)	106
4.1.5	Istanbul, Turkey (PARadISE)	116
4.1.6	Eilat, Israel (PARadISE)	123
4.2	User experience	132
4.2.1	[SEBR] Assessment of co-design procedure	133
4.2.2	[PARadISE] Assessment of co-design procedure	134
4.2.3	Operators – Survey Results	136
4.2.4	Occupants – Insights from the Awareness-raising Activities for	137
	Appendix 1: Operator survey	141
	Appendix 2: Models’ validation based on monitored data	144
	Appendix 3: Definition of procuRE Key Performance Indicators	149

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1. First-floor lighting system upgrade	15
Figure 2. Second-floor lighting system upgrade	15
Figure 3. Third-floor lighting system upgrade	16
Figure 4. Schematic of the VRF system.....	21
Figure 5. Example of one typology of emission units installed.....	22
Figure 6. Example of a different typology of emission units installed.....	22
Figure 7. Roof Mounted Unit Layout	24
Figure 8. Schematic of the PV panels installation on the building’s roof	25
Figure 9. Schematic of the PV panels installation on the building’s roof	25
Figure 10. View from above.....	26
Figure 11. EMS interface (Eilat)	26
Figure 12. Six battery units installed in the Eilat demo site.....	27
Figure 13. Picture of the terminal tower covered in PV panels.....	29
Figure 14. Rendered image Eilat site (Pergola).....	30
Figure 15. Image Existing Roof.....	30
Figure 16. Picture "Bakery School Building"	32
Figure 17. Scheme of the PV installation highlighting the different PV system parts	36
Figure 18. View of the PV system from Google Maps (as of April, 2025)	36
Figure 19. BMS System Interface.....	38
Figure 20. Occupants Training Session	39
Figure 21. Heat Pump	42
Figure 22. PV-System on school (left) and daycare (right)	42
Figure 23. Battery Cabinet with Fence.....	43
Figure 24. Occupant Training Session.....	44
Figure 25. Noise Reduction Housing.....	45
Figure 26. Heat-pump and ventilation unit assembly (commissioning stage).....	48
Figure 27. Heat-pump and ventilation unit assembly placement.....	49
Figure 28. Battery Electric Storage System (building A)	55
Figure 29. Example of a connection diagram of electrical equipment installed in building A – branch school (as-built project).....	56
Figure 30. Heat Pump installation on EBMAP.....	64
Figure 31. PV installation and Batteries on EBMAP	65
Figure 32. BMS installation on EBMAP	66
Figure 33. Overview of absolute key performance indicators across six pilot sites	75

Figure 34. Overview of relative key performance indicators across six pilot sites	76
Figure 35. Nuremberg Energy KPIs (1-7 February)	79
Figure 36. Nuremberg electric energy flows and battery State of Charge (1-7 February).	79
Figure 37. Nuremberg Energy KPIs (15-22 March)	80
Figure 38. Nuremberg electric energy flows and battery State of Charge (15-22 March).	81
Figure 39. Nuremberg Energy KPIs (15-22 July).....	82
Figure 40. Nuremberg electric energy flows and battery State of Charge (15-22 July).....	82
Figure 41. SRI for the different impact criteria. Nuremberg pilot site.....	86
Figure 42. SRI for the different technical domains. Nuremberg pilot site	86
Figure 43. Barcelona Energy KPIs (1-7 February).....	89
Figure 44. Barcelona Energy KPIs (15-22 March).....	89
Figure 45. Barcelona Energy KPIs (15-22 July)	90
Figure 46. Illuminance (lux) on the tables on 2 nd floor before renovation. Barcelona pilot site	92
Figure 47. Illuminance (lux) on the tables on 2 nd floor after renovation and tuning. Barcelona pilot site.....	93
Figure 48. SRI for the different impact criteria. Barcelona pilot site	95
Figure 49. SRI for the different technical domains. Barcelona pilot site	95
Figure 50. Vila Nova de Gaia Energy KPIs (1-7 February).....	99
Figure 51. Vila Nova de Gaia electric energy flows and battery State of Charge (1-7 February).	99
Figure 52. Vila Nova de Gaia Energy KPIs (15-22 March)	100
Figure 53. Vila Nova de Gaia electric energy flows and battery State of Charge (15-22 March).	101
Figure 54. Vila Nova de Gaia Energy KPIs (15-22 July).....	101
Figure 55. Vila Nova de Gaia electric energy flows and battery State of Charge (15-22 July).....	102
Figure 56. SRI for the different impact criteria. Vila Nova de Gaia pilot site	105
Figure 57. SRI for the different technical domains. Vila Nova de Gaia pilot site	105
Figure 58. Velenje Energy KPIs (1-7 February).....	108
Figure 59. Velenje electric energy flows and battery State of Charge (1-7 February).....	108
Figure 60. Velenje Energy KPIs (15-22 March).....	110
Figure 61. Velenje electric energy flows and battery State of Charge (15-22 March).....	110
Figure 62. Velenje Energy KPIs (15-22 July)	111
Figure 63. Velenje electric energy flows and battery State of Charge (15-22 July).	112
Figure 64. SRI for the different impact criteria. Velenje pilot site	115
Figure 65. SRI for the different technical domains. Velenje pilot site	115
Figure 66. Istanbul Energy KPIs (1-7 February).....	118
Figure 67. Istanbul Energy KPIs (15-22 March).....	118
Figure 68. Istanbul Energy KPIs (15-22 July)	119
Figure 69. SRI for the different impact criteria. Istanbul pilot site	123
Figure 70. SRI for the different technical domains. Istanbul pilot site	123

Figure 71. Eilat Energy KPIs (1-7 February).....	126
Figure 72. Eilat electric energy flows and battery State of Charge (1-7 February).....	126
Figure 73. Eilat Energy KPIs (15-22 July)	128
Figure 74. Eilat electric energy flows and battery State of Charge (15-22 July).....	128
Figure 75. SRI for the different impact criteria. Eilat pilot site	132
Figure 76. SRI for the different technical domains. Eilat pilot site	132
Figure 77. Assessment of features and activities during the co-design procedure - SEBR.....	134
Figure 78. Assessment of features and activities during the co-design procedure - PARadISE.....	136
Figure 79. Awareness-raising and training materials samples (SEBR)	138
Figure 80. Awareness-raising and training materials samples (PARadISE)	140
Figure 81. Comparison between simulation results (blue) and measured quantities (red) for the Nuremberg Model’s validation.....	146
Figure 82. Building’s electric consumption in Eilat	147
Figure 83. PV production in Eilat	148

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1. Summary of pilot sites actual status and main upgrades	12
Table 2. Existing system and key upgrades in the Barcelona demo site.....	13
Table 3. Actual and new units heating and cooling indoor units installed with related nominal thermal power in both heating and cooling operations.....	14
Table 4. Lighting KPIs before and after installation in four different offices	18
Table 5. Existing system and key upgrades in the Eilat demo site.....	20
Table 6. List of wall mounted AC in each room.	22
Table 7. Total Cooling Capacity (Total 51 R.T.) - LG VRF Air-Conditioning System	23
Table 8. Existing system and key upgrades in the Istanbul demo site.....	33
Table 9. Existing system and key upgrades in the Nuremberg demo site	41
Table 10. Existing system and key upgrades in the Velenje demo site	47
Table 11. Existing system and key upgrades in the Villa Nova de Gaia demo site	63
Table 12. Yearly energy KPIs for the Nuremberg pilot site before and after intervention.....	77
Table 13. Number of hours over the year with indoor temperature in defined ranges.....	83
Table 14. Yearly CO ₂ emissions of pre and post-intervention situation and related savings. Nuremberg pilot site	84
Table 15. SRI overall score and related class before and after renovation, Nuremberg pilot site	85
Table 16. Yearly energy KPIs for the Barcelona pilot site before and after intervention.	88
Table 17. Number of hours over the year with indoor temperature in defined ranges.....	91
Table 18. Yearly CO ₂ emissions of pre and post-intervention situation and related savings. Barcelona pilot site	93

Table 19. SRI overall score and related class before and after renovation, Barcelona pilot site	94
Table 20. Yearly energy KPIs for the Vila Nova de Gaia pilot site before and after intervention.	97
Table 21. Number of hours over the year with indoor temperature in defined ranges.	103
Table 22. Yearly CO ₂ emissions of pre and post-intervention situation and related savings. Vila Nova de Gaia pilot site	104
Table 23. SRI overall score and related class before and after renovation, Vila Nova de Gaia pilot site	105
Table 24. Yearly energy KPIs for the Velenje pilot site before and after intervention.	107
Table 25. Number of hours over the year with indoor temperature in defined ranges.	113
Table 26. Yearly CO ₂ emissions of pre and post-intervention situation and related savings. Velenje pilot site	114
Table 27. SRI overall score and related class before and after renovation, Velenje pilot site	115
Table 28. Yearly energy KPIs for the Istanbul pilot site before and after intervention.	117
Table 29. Number of hours over the year with indoor temperature in defined ranges.	120
Table 30. Yearly CO ₂ emissions of pre and post-intervention situation and related savings. Istanbul pilot site	121
Table 31. SRI overall score and related class before and after renovation, Istanbul pilot site	122
Table 32. Yearly energy KPIs for the Eilat pilot site before and after intervention.	124
Table 33. Number of hours over the year with indoor temperature in defined ranges.	129
Table 34. Yearly CO ₂ emissions of pre- and post-intervention situation and related savings. Eilat pilot site	130
Table 35. SRI overall score and related class before and after renovation, Eilat pilot site	131

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable documents the outcomes of the pilot testing phase, focusing on both building performance and user experience. Key outcomes include the technical performance evaluation of implemented systems and user feedback collected through surveys.

All six demonstration sites have been deployed and monitor relevant operational data. The delays in the progress made it necessary to use simulations for extending the data duration and to extrapolate Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) over a timeframe that shall provide evidentiary results and performance validation (over the entirety of a year and/or heating season). To ensure the simulation results are representative of buildings and related energy systems' performances, the models have been validated against the available monitored data as described in Appendix 2.

The six pilot sites exhibit considerable variation in their energy KPI results. The Renewable Energy Share (representing the fraction of the building's consumption effectively covered by locally produced renewable energy) varies from 30 % in Barcelona and Istanbul (due to the specific boundary conditions for these two sites) to around 50 % in Nuremberg, Vila Nova de Gaia and Velenje, and up to practically 100 % in Eilat, thanks to the temporal alignment of building's thermal demand for space cooling and the PV production.

Regarding the Indoor Environmental Quality KPIs, the implemented renovation packages ensured, for most of the time, increased thermal comfort of building in terms of both indoor ambient temperature and air humidity. Notable improvement across all sites was also indicated for the management of CO₂ levels inside the building. Some exceptions were observed at the Vila Nova de Gaia and Barcelona pilot site, where underheating occurred during certain hours. Overall, users' comfort always improved in comparison to the pre-intervention situation.

The implemented renovation packages resulted in a significant reduction of the CO₂ emissions associated with buildings' operations across all six demonstration sites. This reduction ranges from 28% in Istanbul (value particularly low due to the high electric consumption of this building associated with its use profile specifics) to 100% in Eilat despite 24/7-use of the building (ability to charge batteries throughout the year).

The Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) improved from an average of 20% to 66% across buildings.

1 Introduction

The procuRE project, funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, aims to advance the adoption of renewable energy solutions in public buildings across Europe. The project is designed to demonstrate how innovative Renovation Packages can be applied to existing non-residential buildings to achieve 100% renewable energy supply while improving energy efficiency and reducing operational costs.

The project was divided into one preparation and three development phases:

- **Phase 0:** Building analysis, call for tender and market engagement
- **Phase I:** Conceptual development and initial design of the Renovation Packages.
- **Phase II:** Testing and prototyping of the solutions in controlled environments.
- **Phase III:** Implementation of these solutions in real-world settings across six pilot sites in different countries.

This deliverable focuses on the outcomes of **Phase III** and provides a detailed account of the outcomes from the pilot tests conducted in selected buildings.

2 Pilot testing overview

2.1 Objectives of pilot testing

The primary objectives of the pilot testing were to validate the technical performance of the proposed Renovation Packages in real-world settings, assess the effectiveness of these solutions in achieving energy efficiency and renewable energy goals, ensure that the systems are user-friendly and meet the operational needs of building operators and occupants, and gather feedback from various stakeholders to refine the solutions before full-scale deployment.

2.2 Organisation of pilot testing

The pilot testing in the procuRE project was the culmination of extensive planning and development that began in earlier phases.

In **Phase I**, the groundwork was laid through the initial design and conceptualisation of the Renovation Packages. This phase involved understanding the specific needs of the pilot sites and setting the goals for energy efficiency and renewable energy integration.

Phase II was focused on turning these designs into functional prototypes. In procuRE these were the process and the output of rapidly iterating Renovation Packages. All Suppliers developed and iterated six Renovation Packages in parallel. The test included the process itself as the joining of planning and contracting works is often a separate process. Preparations for the pilot sites, including infrastructure setup and stakeholder training, were also completed during this phase.

Phase III marked the full-scale deployment and testing of these Renovation Packages across multiple pilot sites. This phase was critical in validating the solutions under actual operating conditions, providing a true test of their effectiveness and usability. Key activities in this phase included:

- **Deployment of Renovation Packages:** The fully developed Renovation Packages were installed and integrated into the pilot buildings. This involved ensuring all systems were operational and ready for continuous monitoring.
- **Performance Monitoring:** Advanced monitoring systems were used to track energy consumption, indoor environmental quality, and other key performance indicators (KPIs). This data was essential in evaluating how well the systems met the project's energy and sustainability targets.
- **User Interaction and Feedback:** Building occupants and operators interacted with the new systems, providing valuable feedback on usability and comfort. This real-world input was crucial for assessing the overall success of the renovations and identifying any areas needing adjustment. The following actions were deployed:
 - **Operators:**
 - Suppliers' contractors were required to conduct training sessions on the new hardware equipment. This entailed producing manuals (in local languages) and providing technical assistance on demand.
 - The suppliers' consortium coordinated the BMS training (once installation was completed and the system was functional).
 - **Occupants:**

- The suppliers' consortium organised on-site¹ training sessions for school and office staff, complemented by awareness campaigns (including gamified learning strategies) targeting children. The training emphasised the environmental and efficiency gains brought about by the RES solutions. Relevant materials, such as presentations, flyers and learning materials like booklets (for school children) were prepared by suppliers and offered to occupants.
- Continuous Optimisation: Throughout the testing period, continuous commissioning processes were employed to optimise system performance. Real-time data allowed for immediate adjustments, ensuring the systems operated at their best.

2.3 Overview of demonstration pilot sites

The pilot testing involved several diverse locations across Europe and the Middle East, each with unique challenges and specific goals for energy efficiency and renewable energy integration. Table 1 represents a detailed overview of each site, including the renovations and upgrades performed.

¹ The only online training occurred in Eilat and constituted an exception justified by due to the political circumstances and security concerns.

Table 1. Summary of pilot sites actual status and main upgrades

Pilot	Location	Building size (Floor area m ²)	Existing system	Key upgrades					
				Consumption devices		Production/ storage devices		Control/ monitoring	
				HVAC system		Lights	RES	Storage (el.)	BMS
				H&C	Mech. Vent.				
City Council Central Office	Barcelona, Spain	2,350	Old HP system, mech. Vent, PV system	● (HP)	-	●	● (PV)	-	●
Municipal office building	Eilat, Israel	800	50 small AC Units	● (VRF)	●	-	● (PV)	● (BESS)	●
Bakery school	Istanbul, Turkey	3,900	VRF system, No fresh air unit mech. Vent.	● (VRF)	-	●	● (PV)	-	●
Elementary school	Nuremberg, Germany	3,072	Gas boiler, mech. Vent.	● (HP)	-	-	● (PV)	● (BESS)	●
School and multi-use hall	Velenje, Slovenia	1,947	Oil boiler	● (HP)	●	-	● (PV)	● (BESS)	●
School Center	Vila Nova de Gaia, Portugal	4075	Gas boiler, VRF, mech. Vent.	● (HP)	-	-	● (PV)	● (BESS)	●

2.3.1 Barcelona, Spain (SEBR)

The pilot site in Barcelona was the City Council central offices in Sant Boi de Llobregat, covering 2,350 m². The building, originally constructed in 1850 and last refurbished in 2010, currently features a heating and cooling system based on a two-pipe heat pump, distributing water to fan coils in offices. Despite these updates, the building still requires significant upgrades, particularly in the plenary room, which need air-conditioning improvements. The building's artificial lighting is mainly provided by fluorescent and halogen lamps, and there is an old, inefficient 5 kWp PV plant on the roof. The renovation focused on upgrading the HVAC systems, and considering the replacement of the PV plant with a bigger and more efficient system. Moreover, the lighting system will be also updated and all systems will be connected to a unique BMS. The general details of the upgrades are summarised in the Table 2.

Table 2. Existing system and key upgrades in the Barcelona demo site

METRIC →	STATUS	KEY UPGRADES				
BUILDING/ SIZE [m ²] ↓	INTER.	Demand-side		Supply and storage		Control and monitoring
		HVAC systems		RES	BESS	BMS
		Heating & cooling	Ventilation	Production	Storage	Management
2,350	<i>Before</i>	1 air-water HP (225kW, th)	present	Mainly fluorescent	PV (5 kWp)	-
	<i>After</i>	2 air-water HP (170 kW,th)	No interv.	LEDs	PV (66 kWp)	-

Implemented upgrades HVAC system

The centralised existing air-water heat pumps have been replaced with 2 new ones for a total heating thermal capacity of 170,64 kW and cooling thermal capacity of 177,6. The intervention also consists of updating all the hydraulic connections in the technical room. While no intervention has been made on the distribution system, 12 internal emission units have been changed in order to install a more efficient model with a power aligned with the new external system installed. The new system provides both heating and cooling to all rooms.

In each zone served by the new emission internal units, a thermostat has been installed to enable control of the system’s heating and cooling modes, fan speed, and desired comfort temperature.

Additionally, thermostats for the existing fan coil units are being replaced with new Modbus-compatible models. This upgrade allows seamless integration with the two newly installed heat pumps and enables full HVAC system control through the Building Management System (BMS). As a result, the system can be managed centrally and efficiently, allowing for optimal and zoned temperature regulation.

Table 3. Actual and new units heating and cooling indoor units installed with related nominal thermal power in both heating and cooling operations

Ref.	Plan code	Location	Current model	Proposed model			
			Cooling (kW)	Heating (kW)	Equipment model	Cooling (kW)	Heating (kW)
1	MI-C-S1-A01	Basement	11.8	11.8	DAIKIN-FWD16AT	16.40	19.81
2	MI-C-S1-A02	Basement	12	12	DAIKIN-FWD12AT	11.03	11.92
3	MI-C-S1-A03	Basement	12	12	DAIKIN-FWD12AT	11.03	11.92
8	MI-C-P1-A04	1 st floor	6	6	DAIKIN-FWP10CTV	6.27	6.68
9	MI-C-P1-A05	1 st floor	6	6	DAIKIN-FWP10CTV	6.27	6.68
10	MI-C-P1-A06	1 st floor	6	6	DAIKIN-FWP10CTV	6.27	6.68
11	MI-C-P1-A07	1 st floor	5	5	DAIKIN-FWP10CTV	6.27	6.68
12	MI-C-P1-A08	1 st floor	5	5	DAIKIN-FWP10CTV	6.27	6.68
13	MI-C-P1-A09	1 st floor	5	5	DAIKIN-FWP10CTV	6.27	6.68
5	MI-F-PB-A16	Ground floor	3.3	3.8	DAIKIN-FWZ06ATV	6.32	7.51
7	MI-SP-PB-A18	Ground floor	3	3	DAIKIN-FWT04GT	3.13	4.36
42	MI-C-P3-A12	2 nd floor	17.2	17.2	DAIKIN-FWP11CTV	7.45	7.62

Lighting system

The existing lighting system was mainly composed of fluorescent lights. All fluorescent lights have been replaced with LED ones. The intervention focused on the upper 3 floors, hosting party offices and technicians open spaces. On the lowest floor, in the public area, the lighting had already been updated to more efficient led system some years ago.

Figure 1. First-floor lighting system upgrade

Figure 2. Second-floor lighting system upgrade

Figure 3. Third-floor lighting system upgrade

Third Floor lighting system updates

The new lighting systems installed follow, as much as possible, the requirements for the lighting systems inside the AMB offices, regarding lighting intensity, uniformity, colour replication and glare.

PV system

The existing 5 kWp PV system on the roof has been replaced by a new PV system. The new PV system has a total nominal peak power of 65.94 kW and is composed of two different sections. The first (for a nominal peak power of 26.16 kW) is installed on the roof, replacing the existing 5 kWp system. The second part (for a nominal peak power of 39.78 kW) is installed on two canopies respectively of 18 and 22 meters long, located around 210 m from the building. The panels installed in the parking lot will be directly connected to the public grid, ensuring an energy exchange regime for the municipality of Sant Boi.

BMS

A new BMS is deployed to the demo. It monitors the different systems installed, i.e. the HVAC system, the lighting system and the PV system as well as indoor environment conditions (temperature, humidity, level of CO₂). The existing BMS is integrated inside the Mondas Platform, a Software as a service (SaaS) system which allows to gather every information of the building, from performance of the systems to internal air quality, and compare it with external data and forecast. Moreover, it allows the implementation of specific controls for the HVAC and lighting systems.

Operator and occupant training / onboarding

Operator training: Throughout the implementation phase of the project, various actions were carried out to ensure a proper understanding and effective management of the new systems by the technical staff responsible for the municipal buildings. While no formal training programme was delivered, several technical meetings, documentation handovers and working sessions were held with both the suppliers and the relevant municipal services.

- **HVAC system:** The HVAC supplier conducted a technical handover that included as-built documentation, equipment manuals, and full project documentation. A dedicated meeting was held with municipal staff to define the system's operating parameters, including temperature setpoints and control strategies, ensuring optimal operation aligned with the building's needs.
- **Lighting system:** Following the installation of the new LED lighting, several technical meetings were held to adjust lighting levels according to the real use of the workspaces. The supplier also provided all necessary documentation to facilitate operation and maintenance by municipal staff.
- **Photovoltaic (PV) system:** All relevant technical documentation will be delivered to the municipality, including plans, manuals and warranty certificates. In this case, the legalisation process of the PV installation will be carried out by the municipality itself because the process may last several months.
- **Monitoring and control platform (MONDAS):** Two key sessions were organised with building managers: one focused on defining the system's configuration and monitored parameters, and another on presenting the dashboard interface and key functionalities. These sessions enable municipal teams to autonomously monitor energy data and building performance.

Occupant training: To complement the technical implementation of the project, two awareness-raising sessions were organised with the aim of informing building users and engaging the wider community. These sessions helped contextualise the renovation efforts and promote behavioural change towards more sustainable practices.

Session for building users: This session targeted the regular users of the renovated building and focused on explaining the overall objectives of the procuRE project and the specific improvements carried out within the building (e.g. HVAC, lighting, PV installation, monitoring system). It aimed to foster understanding of the energy upgrades and how users could contribute to energy efficiency through daily actions.

Open session for citizens: A public event was held to present the project to the broader community and raise awareness about the importance of sustainable building renovation. The session focused on:

- Understanding the key stages of a building renovation process
- Identifying common barriers and frictions to sustainable renovation
- Co-creating solutions from the public administration to make the process more accessible and citizen-friendly

Challenges overcome at the site

Delay and limits in the periods for the switching OFF and replacement of the HVAC system

Challenge and cause: The intervention on the HVAC system (mainly the replacement of the existing air-water heat pumps) implies that, during the intervention, space heating or cooling cannot be delivered to the building for approximately one week. Considering the building location, the related climatic conditions, and the building usage, this limited the possible periods for the intervention on the centralized HVAC system.

Mitigation action: Thus, the installations must take place in the months of spring or autumn where the users’ thermal comfort can be ensured also without the availability of the space heating and cooling system. For this reason, the replacement of the main unit was done in Oct 2024; the building remained without HVAC for a week approximately.

Lighting system requirements

Challenge and cause: The raising prices lead to the costs of the lighting system to go beyond the tendered limit budgeted during Phase 2. The target was to replace existing fluorescent bulbs with more efficient LED, with the replacement of the lamp when needed for the LED plug necessity. The original requirement and intent was to replace the entire lightning system location to adapt it to the working station layout.

Mitigation action: SEBR avoided the major works to the ceiling necessary to change the entire lighting system. Instead, the focus was put on having at least 500 lux (Em) on top of the working tables without creating adverse effects in the uniformity (Emin/Em). A data collection study of the current lighting values was conducted across all three floors. A simulation generated a new design which resulting in the change of all 214 lamps on the three upper floors. Keeping the existing system, however, came with a reduced energy efficiency achievement in some areas. However, the GHG impact of the measure was reduced by prolonging the use of existing fixtures and avoiding material use.

The chosen approach enabled to customise the light output for individual spots and ensures long-term compliance with changing building regulations.

Table 4. Lighting KPIs before and after installation in four different offices

Comparison of lighting values between current status and proposal					
Floor	Room	Installation	Value of Energy Efficiency in a Facility (W/m2)	Em (lux)	Emin/Em
2	Room 1	Current	8,65	218	0,11
		Proposed	4,28	495	0,224
2	Room 2	Current	9,73	234	0,037
		Proposed	4,73	527	0,183
3	Room 1	Current	6,72	527	0,176
		Proposed	5,5	662	0,231
3	Room 2	Current	9,48	395	0,068
		Proposed	4,96	567	0,238

Once the new lighting system was installed, several complaints were received regarding excessive brightness and perceived over-illumination. To address this issue, the lighting intensity was reduced in specific areas by dimming the LED fixtures. This adjustment allowed for a more comfortable lighting environment while still complying with regulatory lighting requirements.

Delays in the PV process (POMO)

Challenge and cause: The approval of some important renovation interventions in public buildings like the one used as demo case requires the publication of a complete project description (POMO) for public review. The forecast for the POMO approval was February 2024. The local administration required changes to the PV side of the project. In order to not slow down the whole installation, the decision was made to split the POMO into three, one for each major system installed. The main reason was to ensure a quick approval of the HVAC POMO, which had not received any additional specification requests after the municipality’s review. However, the approval of the HVAC POMO was still delayed to the point that the installation team was no longer available, which therefore moved the installation from spring to fall.

Mitigation action: the PV POMO had an even longer process due to requests for additional structural roof verifications, which were staggered over weeks and months, which led to approval only in March 2025, one year after the entire process had begun. Before deploying the intervention the related POMO must be finally approved. This includes the preparation of the POMO, the approval from the City Council, the publication, 30 days of public exposure and, if no comments are received, the works can start. The fact that three POMOs were necessary made the process longer; but finally they were signed and approved.

Furthermore, the roof was close to reaching its structural load limit with the addition of the new photovoltaic installation. Therefore, the existing panels had to be removed first. The new panels were then unloaded in strict compliance with the maximum permitted load ($1 \text{ kN/m}^2 \approx 100 \text{ kg/m}^2$). As a full pallet exceeded this limit, it could not be placed on the roof. Instead, it was kept suspended by a crane while the panels were individually offloaded and installed directly in their final positions.

2.3.2 Eilat, Israel (PARadISE)

In Eilat, the pilot project was conducted at the municipality offices. The single-floor building, covering 800 m², was originally used as part of the municipality’s offices. The existing HVAC system consists of 50 autonomous AC split systems units used exclusively for cooling, with no mechanical ventilation system in place. The building lacks real-time monitoring systems, relying instead on utility bills to track energy consumption. The renovation project in Eilat focused on the renovation of the existing cooling system, implementation of renewable energy production system (PV), electric battery and BMS to actively monitor and control energy production and consumption. In Eilat, it was decided to install bigger energy storage system to reach as higher energy independent and use of renewables. The office also serves as the main calling service of the municipality, and it works 24/7 which mean high energy consumption. Table 5 summarises the general details of the main upgrades.

Table 5. Existing system and key upgrades in the Eilat demo site

METRIC →	STATUS	KEY UPGRADES				
BUILDING/ SIZE [m ²] ↓	INTER.	Demand-side		Supply and storage		Control and monitoring
		HVAC systems		RES	BESS	BMS
		Heating & cooling	Ventilation	Production	Storage	Management
700	<i>Before</i>	VRF system	NO Mech Vent.LED's		-	-
	<i>After</i>	VRF system (196 kW,th)	ARUN140 (611,700 Btu/hr)	No interv.	PV (91 kWp)	BESS (194 kWh)

Implemented upgrades

HVAC system

The HVAC system upgrade included replacing 50 standalone heat pumps with a Variable Refrigerant Flow (VRF) system, featuring ceiling ducts for the indoor units, along with two fresh air indoor units placed on the roof to deliver space cooling to the entire building. The new system consists of five outdoor units, offering a combined cooling capacity of 196 kW, and is segmented into five separate cooling circuits, as illustrated in the accompanying diagram.

Figure 4. Schematic of the VRF system

Note: The figure highlights the five external units placed on the roof and the relation (see the different colours) with the internal emission units

Figure 5. Example of one typology of emission units installed

Figure 6. Example of a different typology of emission units installed

The actual wall mounted units connected to the roof main units were installed as follows:

Table 6. List of wall mounted AC in each room.

type	colour	circle	model	unit	no.
cassette	green	1	ARNU - 12	IDU - 19	1
cassette	green	1	ARNU 12	IDU -19.1	2
cassette	green	1	ARNU - 12	IDU - 19.2	3
cassette	green	1	ARNU - 12	IDU - 19.3	4
wall mount	green	1	ARNU - 15	IDU - 37	5
wall mount	green	1	ARNU -07	IDU - 38	6
wall mount	green	1	ARNU -07	IDU - 39	7
wall mount	green	1	ARNU -07	IDU - 40	8
cassette	green	1	ARNU - 09	IDU - 43	9
cassette	green	1	ARNU - 18	IDU - 14	10
wall mount	green	1	ARNU - 9	IDU - 24	11
wall mount	purple	2	ARNU -12	IDU -7	12
wall mount	purple	2	ARNU -12	IDU - 10	13
wall mount	purple	2	ARNU - 12	IDU -21	14

wall mount	purple	2	ARNU - 12	IDU -22	15
wall mount	purple	2	ARNU - 12	IDU -23	16
wall mount	purple	2	ARNU -12	IDU - 30	17
wall mount	purple	2	ARNU - 12	IDU - 33	18
cassette	purple	2	ARNU - 18	IDU - 6	19
wall mount	purple	2	ARNU - 07	IDU - 44	20
wall mount	purple	2	ARNU -18	IDU - 5	21
wall mount	orange	3	ARNU - 15	IDU - 4	22
wall mount	orange	3	ARNU - 09	IDU - 13	23
wall mount	orange	3	ARNU -07	IDU - 18	24
wall mount	orange	3	ARNU - 09	IDU - 24	25
wall mount	orange	3	ARNU -09	IDU - 28	26
wall mount	orange	3	ARNU - 09	IDU - 29	27
wall mount	orange	3	ARNU - 15	IDU - 31	28
wall mount	orange	3	ARNU - 09	IDU - 32	29
wall mount	orange	3	ARNU - 15	IDU - 11	30
wall mount	orange	3	ARNU - 09	IND - 34	31
wall mount	orange	3	ARNU - 07	IND -35	32
wall mount	orange	3	ARNU - 09	IND - 36	33
wall mount	blue	4	ARNU - 07	IDU - 25	34
wall mount	blue	4	ARNU - 07	IDU - 26	35
wall mount	blue	4	ARNU - 07	IDU - 27	36
wall mount	blue	4	ARNU - 15	IDU - 17	37
cassette	blue	4	ARNU - 18	IDU - 1	38
cassette	blue	1	ARNU - 18	IDU - 1.1	39
wall mount	blue	4	ARNU - 07	IDU - 41	40
wall mount	blue	4	ARNU -12	IDU - 3	41
wall mount	blue	4	ARNU - 12	IDU - 8	42
cassette	blue	4	ARNU -24	IDU - 12	43
cassette	blue	4	ARNU - 24	IDU - 12.1	44
wall mount	כחול	4	ARNU - 12	IDU - 15	45
wall mount	כחול	4	ARNU -12	IDU - 16	46
wall mount	כחול	4	ARNU - 12	IDU - 2	47
wall mount	yellow	5	ARNU - 54	FRESH AIR-1	48
wall mount	yellow	5	ARNU - 54	FRESH AIR-2	49

Table 7. Total Cooling Capacity (Total 51 R.T.) - LG VRF Air-Conditioning System

IDU Model	Cooling Capacity (BTU/hr)	Quantity	Total Cooling Capacity (BTU/hr)	Total Cooling Capacity (T.R)
ARNU 07	7,500	9	67,500	5.6
ARNU 09	9,600	8	76,800	6.4

ARNU 12	12,300	11	135,300	11.2
ARNU 15	15,400	6	92,400	7.7
ARNU 18	19,100	5	95,500	7.95
ARNU 24	24,200	2	48,400	4
ARNU 48	48,100	1	48,100	4
Total	—	—	564,000	46.85
IDU Model	Cooling Capacity (BTU/hr)	Quantity	Total Cooling Capacity (BTU/hr)	Total Cooling Capacity (T.R)

Figure 7. Roof Mounted Unit Layout

PV system

The PV solar field is situated on the flat roof, with a total peak capacity of 91.14 kWp distributed across 147 panels. These bifacial PV panels, each with a nominal peak power of 620 Wp – with the optimal dimensions for the utilisation of the roof - are installed at a 12° incline and oriented toward the southwest (SW). The placement and orientation were determined based on simulations conducted using the Building Energy Model, which accounted for shadowing effects caused by newly installed components in the central roof area during the renovation (e.g., outdoor units) as well as shadows cast by nearby structures, such as adjacent buildings and trees.

Figure 8. Schematic of the PV panels installation on the building's roof

Figure 9. Schematic of the PV panels installation on the building's roof

Note: It is possible to note the PV panels and some of the centralized external units of the VRF system

Figure 10. View from above

Electric battery

The installed electric battery system has a nominal capacity of 194.4 kWh consisting of six batteries (each comprising nine modules) and three hybrid inverters, each with a capacity of 30 kW. Following discussions with local providers, it was decided to use multi-MPPT inverters instead of optimizers.

A relatively large-capacity electric battery was chosen compared to the typical size selected for the given PV system. This decision was made in agreement between the supplier and the procurer, where the procurer specifically asked to have a system that can ensure a certain independence from the grid.

An additional requirement based on previous experience of the procurer, was that the BMS will automatically activated one's there is no energy from the grid, that was done successfully after few modifications in the system and now it automatically activated after 10 mili-seconds, so the building can shift from off grid to on grid without effect on the building users.

Figure 11. EMS interface (Eilat)

Picture of the BMS system, shows 0 energy injection and 0 energy receiving from and to the grid

Figure 12. Six battery units installed in the Eilat demo site

BMS

The proposed Building Management System (BMS) is carried out under the integration of all the subsystems (including VRF units, PV system, and ESS) of the building to grant total control of the installation while providing the best and greatest use of information to enhance the results of building management. This system also provides the site with air quality monitoring, including humidity, temperature, CO2, formaldehyde, VOC (Volatile Organic Compounds), and concentration of particulate matter.

The platform has a system for managing energy data; the BMS system can manage histories, trending as many energy variables as necessary, partialising, totalising, etc.

The system has the option of managing alarms with functions that, for example, prevent the operator from hiding or temporarily getting rid of alarms, reactivating them automatically at a certain time.

System navigation is map-based, to display information only as needed for detailed and intuitive navigation, and support touch control for quick use and training, with the ability to view and manage multiple facility systems in one place, including information on the efficiency and energy performance of the building in real time.

Operator and occupant training / onboarding

Operator training: Operator Training was done on each of the system:

HVAC – training was executed for the municipal HVAC system officer under the Electricity and Energy Department. The HVAC system is under maintenance agreements for the next 5 yrs.

PV – training is part of the PV system maintenance in the city. The maintenance company was part of the training and it is now under maintenance agreements.

STORAGE – it was decided that the storage maintenance will be part of the maintenance of the PV system with the same maintenance company. The training were done by the supplier to the maintenance company staff as well as to the municipal Electricity and Energy Department.

BMS – training was done after installation but in ongoing dialogue about improvements and testing,

Occupant training: The occupant training on the HVAC, PV and Storage were done after the installation of each.

Challenges overcome at the site

Change of demonstration site due to change of national funding

Challenge and cause: The primary building in Eilat site was the old terminal that was located in the middle of the city. The Israeli government gave a 5 mil Euro budget to renovate it, so it will be the innovation center for tourism technologies. Due to delays in the renovation planning from the engineer departments of the city and disagreement of what type of uses that building will bring- the government canceled the funding, so we had to change the site to the municipality office main building.

Due to remarkable shifting capabilities, the contractor adapted very quickly to the change and created a new planning to the office building.

Figure 13. Picture of the terminal tower covered in PV panels

Mitigation action: intensive meetings and positive contribution from the contractor to shift to design the new pilot site

Two different designs to the office building

The office building is very low in the ground and can be easily access, so the first planning was to create a double use for the roof by creating a pergola above it using BIPV (Building Integrated Photovoltaics) and regular PV to act as a shade for the pergola. R2M and their team designed an amazing pergola (Figure 14) and we also got green light to proceed from the Mayor.

On the 7th of October 2023 a war started in Israel and we had 60,000 refugees coming to Eilat in 3 days. Considering the municipality 500k Euro creating this pergola and the fast shifting on municipality investment caused by the war – we had to cancel the pergola planning.

Mitigation action: fast shifting and strong will from Eilat team, procuRE partners and the contractor- we designed a new planning for the office building so it can act also as a resilience centre for the municipality in time of crisis,

In addition to the above, and considering the understanding of the municipality, the needs for more technologies like those we implemented in ProcuRE, the municipality added 150k Euro to maximise the PV and battery size (own investment, beyond the ProcuRE budget for the pilot site).

Figure 14. Rendered image Eilat site (Pergola)

RENDER

Challenge and cause: Finding a usage for the 50 HVAC small units in the office building.

Mitigation action: The city's energy department checked all the municipality buildings (about 120) to see if any of them need an AC unit. Eventually, all the units that could be reused were installed in other buildings instead of being thrown away.

Figure 15. Image Existing Roof

Challenge and cause: The energy department wanted to install a regular generator next to the storage system because the goal of the project is not to create a 24/7 off-grid building.

Mitigation action: The municipality added internal investment so we can maximise the PV and storage installation, and in the end, we cancelled the regular generator.

One of the primary delays in the implementation of the solutions has been the provision of tenders for the selection of subcontractors for the main systems. This step is necessary due to the selection process utilised by the municipalities in Israel. The preparation of documents, both for the HVAC system and the main electrical systems - PV, BESS and BMS - required additional time. This is because all installation requirements, including technical, legal, and economic aspects, need to be agreed upon between the procurers and suppliers and must be meticulously detailed. The iterative process of document preparation demands significant time and resources, as each iteration requires careful review and revision to incorporate feedback and address any concerns raised by the involved parties.

War in Israel

Challenge and cause: *force majeure* event.

Mitigation action: Political conflicts, particularly the ongoing war in Israel, posed a significant risk to this project. Although the project has continued, the situation for local companies has been adversely affected. Their capacity to undertake work locally has diminished, and response times have lengthened due to a portion of the workforce having to leave their usual positions. Additionally, the time required to obtain products or equipment, especially from foreign sources, has increased. Import processes have also been affected, with higher rates, taxes, and more meticulous procedures being implemented.

Despite of the obstacles mentioned above, the demonstration site managed to implement the renovations. However, this led to a tender procedure, which was longer than usual. Also, local contractors with whom the city already has contractual agreements were deployed into the project, such as PV EPC company as well as municipal roof insulation company.

2.3.3 Istanbul, Turkey (PARadISE)

The Bakery School of Istanbul Municipality was built in 2015 and is used as a bakery school. There are three theoretical classes, six cooking classes with large industrial ovens and cold storage rooms (~10m² each). The building also has administration offices, the instructors' room and a large conference room.

Figure 16. Picture "Bakery School Building"

The pilot site in Istanbul was the Bakery School of Istanbul Municipality Life Long Learning Center, a 3,900 m² building. The building was equipped with a Variable Refrigerant Flow (VRF) system for heating and cooling but lacked renewable energy systems. The building is used as a bakery school with large industrial ovens, cold storage rooms, and classrooms. Despite its relatively modern construction in 2015, the building lacks renewable energy systems. The pilot explored the installation of solar panels on the roof to reduce the building's carbon footprint and improve energy efficiency. The general details of the main upgrades are reported in Table 8.

Table 8. Existing system and key upgrades in the Istanbul demo site

METRIC →	STATUS	KEY UPGRADES				
BUILDING/ SIZE [m ²] ↓	INTER.	Demand-side		Supply and storage		Control and monitoring
		HVAC systems		RES	BESS	BMS
		Heating & cooling	Ventilation	Production	Storage	Management
3,900	<i>Before</i>	VRF system	present	Mainly fluorescent	-	-
	<i>After</i>	13 new indoor VRF units added (112 kW,th)	No interv.	LEDs	PV (150 kWp)	-

Implemented upgrades

HVAC system

A new, stand-alone VRF system was strategically installed to address specific areas in the building where the existing HVAC system was insufficient to maintain comfortable conditions. This targeted upgrade was primarily aimed at increasing cooling capacity and providing more precise climate control in designated zones. The newly introduced system, Systemair SYSVRF AIR EVO HP (Mini VRF), adds a total of 112.7 kW of HVAC capacity to the building. This system is designed with flexibility and efficiency in mind and is well suited to provide accurate temperature control to selected rooms. General features of the Systemair SYSVRF AIR EVO HP series include DC Inverter technology for energy-efficient operation, a wide operating range for both cooling and heating modes, and a design that simplifies installation and maintenance. The system also includes multiple protection functions for reliable long-term operation and is compatible with various types of indoor units (such as wall-mounted, cassette and duct units) and various central and individual controllers. Functions such as automatic restart after power failure, intelligent defrost cycles and diagnostics are standard.

An important aspect of the building's HVAC strategy is the integration of all systems, both existing and new, with the Building Management System (BMS). This integration enables central monitoring, control and optimisation of energy consumption and user comfort. Communication gateways are used to ensure seamless communication between the various VRF systems and the BACnet-based or Modbus-based BMS.

Challenge and cause: The cause for choosing a 3-pipe VRF system in the İSMEK Bakery and Pastry School building is its ability to provide simultaneous heating and cooling for different functional areas. Practical kitchens, baking rooms, and theoretical classrooms may require heating and cooling at the same time; at this point, 3-pipe VRF systems enhance comfort and ensure energy efficiency through simultaneous operation and heat recovery. In addition, the independent control of each classroom and workshop allows for flexible and efficient climate control tailored to the needs of both students and instructors. With these features, the system stands out as an ideal solution that supports the overall quality of education.

Mitigation action: The main intervention to the HVAC system regarded the installation of a new VRF system distributed across 13 indoor units in specific areas of the building. This installation aimed to enhance cooling capacity in zones where the existing system was insufficient to maintain

comfortable conditions. The newly added system provides a total capacity of 112.7 kW. The existing VRF systems remain in operation, and all systems, both existing and newly installed, have been integrated into the Building Management System (BMS) for centralized monitoring and control. No important interventions were made to the centralized mechanical ventilation system.

Lighting system

The existing lighting system was mainly composed of fluorescent lights. Lighting conditions in various parts of the building—particularly in some workrooms and workshops—were described as inadequate. This situation caused visual discomfort for occupants and potentially hindered the performance of detailed tasks. The existing system did not utilize energy-efficient LED technology uniformly and lacked centralized smart control capabilities. Although the initial plan focused on upgrading specific workshop areas, the demonstrable benefits and feasibility of a broader implementation led to a decision to extend the scope to a full-building lighting upgrade.

All lights have been replaced with LED ones. The primary fixture selected and installed for this comprehensive upgrade is the Borled 60x60 Square Slim LED Panel. Initially, 243 of these LED panels were installed across 12 rooms, and later the same model was used to complete the lighting renovation in the remaining parts of the building. The installed Borled LED fixtures—primarily 40W models such as BL-05-2001, BL-05-2002, and BL-05-2003—offer several key features. With a Color Rendering Index (CRI) of $R_a > 80$, they ensure good color perception, which is critical in both learning and production environments. The fixtures are designed to operate within a wide voltage range of 85–265 V AC, making them resilient against potential voltage fluctuations. Each unit produces a luminous flux of approximately 3600 Lumens with an efficiency of approximately 90 Lm/W. Dimensions are 595 x 595 x 7.5 mm, suitable for standard ceiling grids and an optional frame is available for surface mounted applications if required. The system also integrated with a remote-control system that give the building manager/engineer the capability to control the usage remotely.

PV system

A PV system with a nominal peak power of 150.24 kWp has been installed on the roof of the building. All roof parts presenting the possibility of installing PV panels and a convenient production (kWh per year per kWp) have been used to install PV to increase as much as possible the PV production. This is particularly relevant in this demo as the electrical consumption is relatively high in comparison to a typical school due to the presence of industrial ovens and cold storage rooms. This high consumption is why no electric batteries have been installed. In fact, after an analysis of the energy consumption and PV production, it emerged that the presence of an electric battery would have a limited effect and is not a cost-effective solution for this specific building.

It is useful to mention that, as the building roof presents sections with different heights, the PV system has been first simulated to check eventual effects due to shadows between different parts of the building on the PV system production.

The solar field is design and implemented with the following configuration and combining different solar technologies:

- Pergola: In this case, a semi-transparent PV laminate was used, with nominal efficiency of 20.8%, with 0° slope. In total, 87 PV panels were installed with total PV power of 46.98 kWp.

- Corridor: As well as in the pergola, semi-transparent PV laminate was used, with nominal efficiency of 20.8%, with 0° slope. In total, 25 PV panels were installed with total PV power of 13.5 kWp.
- School: On the tilted rooftop, 108 PV panels of 440 Wp each were installed on a coplanar structure, with a total PV power of 47.52 kWp.
- Office: On the rooftop of the office 96 PV panels of 440 Wp each were installed on a coplanar structure on the tilted rooftop summing up a total PV power of 42.24 kWp.

In total, 316 PV panels with a total power of 150.24 kW were installed. The system is connected to three Huawei inverters that convert the DC current from the PV panels into AC current injected into the school's main electrical switchboard. This solution will provide an estimated annual production of 180,751 kWh.

Figure 17. Scheme of the PV installation highlighting the different PV system parts

Figure 18. View of the PV system from Google Maps (as of April, 2025)

BMS

The proposed new Building Management System (BMS) is carried out under the integration of all the subsystems (including VRF system, PV system and Lighting) of the building to grant total control of the installation while providing the best and greatest use of information to enhance the results of building management. The platform has a system for managing energy data; the BMS system can manage histories, trending as many energy variables as necessary, partialising, totalising, etc.

The system has the option of managing alarms with functions that, for example, prevent the operator from hiding or temporarily getting rid of alarms, reactivating them automatically at a certain time.

System navigation is map-based, to display information only as needed for detailed and intuitive navigation, and support touch control for quick use and training, with the ability to view and manage multiple facility systems in one place, including information on the efficiency and energy performance of the building in real time.

Operator and occupant training/onboarding

Operator training: The operators training focus on the new systems at the building namely the PV, VRF and lighting via BMS. A new BMS is deployed to the building. It monitors the different systems installed, i.e. the HVAC system, the PV system, the electricity consumption of the building per floor and HVAC and the batteries as well as indoor environment conditions (temperature, humidity, level of CO₂). Moreover, it allows the implementation of specific controls for the HVAC, PV and lighting systems.

Figure 19. BMS System Interface

Occupant training: The occupant training campaign aims to educate building occupants about the energy efficiency measures implemented in the building, their impact on daily life, and the importance of adopting sustainable practices. It emphasizes the benefits of energy-saving initiatives to promote eco-friendly behaviours. The activity picture is as Figure 20. In Session 1, occupants were introduced to the building’s upgraded systems (HVAC, lighting, BMS, and RES), with a structured explanation covering the scope of the project, existing issues in the building, implemented solutions, benefits for occupants, and sustainable practices. Additionally, interactive sessions included:

- Activity 1: Energy Scavenger Hunt – Occupants were grouped to identify areas in the building needing improvement or with potential for enhancement.
- Activity 2: Quiz – Focused on Turkey and sustainability, testing occupants’ knowledge.
- Activity 3: Survey – Conducted to understand occupants’ motivations for engaging in sustainable activities. The team that excelled in both the scavenger hunt and quiz received a book on sustainable cooking as a prize.

Figure 20. Occupants Training Session

Challenges overcome at the site

Import procedures for solar panels

Challenge and cause: The import process, initiated in late January 2024, faced significant delays due to customs duties and value-added tax (VAT) complications. As R2M, a Spanish company, lacked VAT registration in Turkey, Paradise assigned their local supplier, Exopanel, responsible for system installation, as the importer. This would have resulted in double VAT charges—once for importing the equipment and again for Exopanel’s invoice—as mandated by Turkish tax laws for projects executed on behalf of non-Turkish entities

Mitigation action: Efforts to address this included consulting customs experts and exploring exemptions by emphasizing the project’s EU status and R2M’s non-profit role. Ultimately, IMM intervened as the importer, providing VAT exemption, relevant documentation and bureaucratic work, enabling the system’s release from the border by the end of May 2024.

PV permit application

Challenge and cause: The PV permit application, submitted on November 30, 2023, remains unissued as of May 2025 due to a series of setbacks. Initially delayed by a building registration

paperwork issue, the process faced further hurdles during a network capacity analysis, with evaluations paused until April 2024. Although technical approval was achieved by June 2024, unresolved discrepancies involving transformer power and current transformer replacements have continued to stall progress. Paradise has been addressing these challenges, but reapplication hinges on completing transformer related work and securing fire permit approval, highlighting the intricate administrative and technical obstacles encountered.

Mitigation action: Paradise and IMM have addressed these challenges, but reapplication hinges on completing transformer-related work and securing fire permit approval, highlighting the intricate administrative and technical obstacles encountered.

National policy change to remote VPN access

Challenge and cause: The national government decided on March 19, 2025, to cut existing VPN connections going abroad. The consequence was that the BMS lost connection to the systems collecting data from the local hardware sensors and meters.

Mitigation action: IMM and PaRADiSE addressed this issue by working mostly on the local network.

2.3.4 Nuremberg, Germany (SEBR)

In Nuremberg, the pilot project took place at Grundschule Zerzabelshof, a primary school for around 200 pupils, covering 3,072 m². The building, constructed in 2015, meets passive house standards but lacks renewable energy systems. It relies on a natural gas condensing boiler for heating and has an efficient central ventilation system with heat recovery. The renovation focused on integrating a heat pump, PV, and electric battery and complementing the existing building management system (BMS) to monitor and optimise energy use. Table 9 summarises the general details of the main upgrades.

Table 9. Existing system and key upgrades in the Nuremberg demo site

METRIC →	STATUS	KEY UPGRADES				
BUILDING/ SIZE [m ²] ↓	INTER.	Demand-side		Supply and storage		Control and monitoring
		HVAC systems		RES	BESS	BMS
		Heating & cooling	Ventilation	Production	Storage	Management
3,077	<i>Before</i>	Gas boiler	present	LED	-	-
	<i>After</i>	1 air-water HP (90 kW _{th})	No interv.	No interv. -	PV (87 kW _p)	BESS (90 kWh)

Implemented upgrades

HVAC system

The intervention on the HVAC system focused on the installation of an air-water heat pump with a nominal thermal capacity of 90 kW. The existing gas boiler is maintained as back-up unit. Interventions were mainly limited to the technical room and the connection to the external units. No relevant interventions have been made on the distribution and emission systems. During commissioning, the noise level of the heat pump, when operating, resulted higher than expected leading to uncomfortable conditions. For this reason, a dedicated box with acoustic insulation has been installed to reduce the heat pump’s noise. Although no legal noise limits were exceeded beforehand, the installation of the noise protection fence achieved a significant reduction in noise to even barely perceptible levels at some places.

Figure 21. Heat Pump

PV system

A 87 kWp PV system, divided into two sections, was installed on the roof of the two-story main building and the one-story day-care part of the building. The PV production is primarily used to cover the building’s electric consumption. Any PV surplus is firstly stored in the battery for later usage or, in case the battery is already fully charged, is sent to the grid.

Figure 22. PV-System on school (left) and daycare (right)

Electric battery

The installed electric battery presents a nominal capacity of 90 kWh.

The battery was installed outside of the building beside the road, close to the electrical grid connection point. For this case, the battery manufacturer offers a complete solution including a weatherproof, air-conditioned metal cabinet.

To secure the battery cabinet and prevent unauthorised people to manipulate the device’s control elements, a fence was erected around the complete cabinet. Now the battery is also visually recognized as an extension of the existing small grid connection building beside the road.

Figure 23. Battery Cabinet with Fence

BMS

The existing BMS was supplemented. It monitors the different systems which had newly been installed and parts of the already existing systems, e.g. the heat pump, the PV system and the electric battery as well as the main indoor environment characteristics (temperature and humidity). Moreover, it allows the implementation of specific controls for the HVAC system and potentially for the management of the electric battery.

Operator and occupant training / onboarding

Operator training: The operator training focused on the use of the new BMS and consisted of two consecutive workshops. At first, the design was presented and basic settings were explained. In the second workshop, a deeper knowledge of the software foundation was given, together with a feedback session to optimise the existing widget designs.

Occupant training: Occupant training took place on 10/Apr/2024 on site. It was planned as half-day event, which was even slightly extended due to the response of the teachers. A specially qualified trainer provided teachers with information on the topics of renewable energy production and energy efficiency. In addition, kits were built and specific teaching units were developed as part of a workshop. Finally, a small picture book for primary school children was presented, which vividly illustrates climate change and what people can do about it. This book was so popular that the school later ordered more copies.

Figure 24. Occupant Training Session

The city of Nuremberg held an open pilot day on October 28, 2024. As part of this event, the project was presented to interested citizens on site. Two guided tours of the PV system, the heat pump and the battery were conducted and the respective function and interaction of the components were explained.

Challenges overcome at the site

Incorrect documentation for the battery-metering connection

Challenge and cause: The battery manufacturer refused to activate the battery as long they did not have a stable internet-connection to the system. For this issue, please refer to the challenge “IT Network Issues”. Additionally, the manufacturer did not properly document the requirement for the Modbus-TCP capable electricity meter. The documentation claimed to operate with a specific protocol but did not refer to a specific product. However, the battery required one certain brand to be able to function properly. The battery could only be put into operation once this electricity meter had also been installed.

Mitigation action: The connection issue was anticipated and investigated first on network and system level as the physical connection between meter and battery obviously had been established correctly. During the investigation, a support ticket with the battery manufacturer was opened, during which it became clear that the installed brand of the meter was not yet cleared by the manufacturer. The manufacturer in this case was very responsive and even checked if they could certify the already installed meter at short notice but unfortunately was not able to do this in the required timeframe. Thus, it was decided to add an additional electricity meter with matching specifications according to the battery manufacturer and connect it to the BMS. After this, the battery could immediately be activated and works fine since then.

Noise cancellation for the air-source heat pump

Challenge and cause: Noise cancellation should be considered early in the project and should play a role in the location of the site. Ignoring this issue can lead to problems with the neighbours. Also, the psychological effect of such a change can be bigger than expected. Out of sight, out of mind plays an important part.

Mitigation action: Make a noise measurement, before, during and after the execution of the project. It could be also good to make a noise measurement before and after the implementation of the noise barriers during the execution phase in the project. Not only to have proof for later but also to see if the calculated noise reduction is achieved.

Figure 25. Noise Reduction Housing

IT Network and Security Issues

Challenge and cause: The time and timeline required to resolve all IT-related issues in order to establish network communication with the devices, the BMS, remote access, and remote platforms — while complying with local municipal IT security standards—must be carefully considered. The challenges extended beyond the declaration of IP address ranges and included complications with firewall settings, both of which proved to be time-consuming.

Additionally, coordinating the municipality's IT security standards with those of various device manufacturers required significant effort. These standards differ in several respects, possibly necessitating a formal agreement to align them. Key questions had to be addressed: What is required? What is feasible? What can be implemented easily? Which IT aspects require special attention?

Another important factor was the time needed to coordinate communication between the device manufacturers and the municipal IT department. Both parties showed little motivation to

communicate directly, even though such direct communication would have significantly simplified the implementation process.

Mitigation action: Knowing that the IT department has a long lead time for work due to overload and is often difficult to reach, we announced the work early on. Nevertheless, it took nearly a year to resolve all issues.

IT Network integration Issues

Challenge and cause: A further major challenge was establishing communication between the individual system components. The aforementioned grid connection building is located approximately 80 metres from the school building and lacks a wired communication link.

Mitigation action: The municipal IT department set up a wireless connection to the building's IoT network, which fully complied with the municipality's stringent IT security requirements. This task took considerably more time than anticipated but was ultimately completed successfully.

PV-System monitoring connection

Challenge and cause: The PV-System did not connect properly to the internet. This might be due to the IT security settings, but it could never finally be clarified. For no apparent reason, communication was interrupted in September 2024 and was re-established "automatically" in January 2025, after many repair attempts had failed in the meantime. Enquiries to the manufacturer's service department also failed to clarify the incident.

Mitigation action: None, issue still pending. Currently, the system is online.

2.3.5 Velenje, Slovenia (PARadISE)

The demonstration pilot includes two buildings in Vinska Gora, a rural village 6 km southeast of Velenje, Slovenia.

Building A, constructed in 1973 and partially renovated in 2002 is a branch of Gorica Elementary School. It features conventional brick masonry construction, with a heated usable surface of 587.0 m², a net heated volume of 1875.0 m³, a thermal envelope of 1460.0 m² and a shape factor of 0.638 m⁻¹. It houses classrooms, playrooms, washrooms, a kitchen, offices, hallways, and a boiler room. Building B, an adjacent multipurpose hall serves as the school’s gymnasium and includes an apartment, offices, conference rooms and restrooms for local community use. Built with the same masonry method, it has a heated usable surface of 1360.6 m², a net heated volume of 6698.0 m³, a thermal envelope of 3160.99 m², and a shape factor of 0.407 m⁻¹. It underwent energy renovation in 2020, adding EPS insulation, XPS under construction, and a rock wool fire barrier.

Both buildings share a central heating system located in Building A’s basement, with Building B connected via an underground shaft. They are owned directly or indirectly (through the district government Vinska Gora) by the Municipality of Velenje. The demonstration pilot primarily focused on Building A, while Building B was also considered due to its connection to the central heating system, its large roof suitable for solar power generation and its potential use for thermal storage or other applications requiring large volumes or surfaces. Before the renovation the heat was generated solely by a low temperature, three pass condensing high efficiency combustion oil boiler. The boiler room is placed in the basement of the primary school (building A). There were no preexisting ventilation systems, monitoring and regulation systems nor renewable energy production on-site. The renovation aimed to replace the oil boiler as the main heating source with a high-efficiency electricity-based system and ventilation for utilization of waste heat to be supplied from onsite renewable energy from solar PV. The general details of the main upgrades are summarised in Table 10 below.

Table 10. Existing system and key upgrades in the Velenje demo site

METRIC →	STATUS	KEY UPGRADES				
BUILDING/ SIZE [m ²] ↓	INTER.	Demand-side		Supply and storage		Control and monitoring
		HVAC systems		RES	BESS	BMS
		Heating & cooling	Ventilation	Production	Storage	Management
Building A 587 m ²	<i>Before</i>	Oil boiler (200 kWt)	/	/	/	/
	<i>After</i>	3 units HT HP (134,4 kWt)	Central - with heat recovery	Hybrid PV (37,31 kW _p)	Lithium-ion (60 kWh)	BMS/EMIS
Building B 1360.6 m ²	<i>Before</i>	Oil boiler (200 kWt)	/	/	/	/
	<i>After</i>	3 units HT HP (134,4 kWt)	/	Hybrid PV (40,04 kW _p)	Lithium-ion (30 kWh)	BMS/EMIS

Commissioned: The demonstration prototype was put into operation in Q4 2024, meeting the administrative deadline for connecting the photovoltaic (PV) system to the distribution network. The operational integration of the HVAC system followed in early 2025. Development and synchronisation of the Building Management System (BMS) continued throughout H2 2025.

Implemented upgrades

Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning systems (HVAC)

The heating system is upgraded with three (3) high temperature air-water heat pumps with a thermal capacity of 44,8 kW per unit connected into a cascade configuration. The heat pumps are installed on the western side of building A and are integrated into the main heating pipeline located in the existing boiler room. The heat pumps are connected to the existing main heating line via an electronically controlled valve. For improved flexibility and stability of the system, two (2) inertia tanks are also integrated into the system. The main inertia tank has a capacity of 1,5 m³ and is used for space heating (hot water). The hot water generated by the heat pumps is stored in the inertia tank, reducing the frequency of start/stop cycles and improving efficiency. The control system monitors temperature and pressure, adjusting the operation of the heat pump and boiler to optimise performance and energy efficiency. The second smaller inertia tank with a volume of 500l serves a dual function, i.e. provides additional heat storage capacity in the heating season, but can also be utilized for space cooling during the warmer months. The heat pump cascade features a hydraulic model and a connection to the central air ventilation unit. A 3-way diverting valve enables a transition of the HVAC system from winter (heating) to summer (cooling) operation. In addition, an individual heat pump for sanitary hot water place is placed adjacently to the boiler room.

Figure 26. Heat-pump and ventilation unit assembly (commissioning stage)

Figure 27. Heat-pump and ventilation unit assembly placement

Figure 30. Boiler room renovation (integration of RES based heating system)

The figure below represents the overall schematic layout of the individual subsystems and their integration (Source Projekt izvedenih del – PID²)

Figure 31. Schematic of installed systems (as-built project)

² Renovation of energy supply systems Vinska Gora, As-built project documentation, R2M (PARadISe)/HTZ, 2024

The heating distribution system (radiators) available at the demonstration building was originally oversized and was well suited for heat pump utilization, thus has remained unchanged.

The HP cascade setup is integrated with a two-level high-capacity ventilation system with waste heat recovery with an airflow rate of 7200 m³/h and a sensible heat recovery efficiency of 88.4%. The central external unit is placed next to the heat pump assembly on the western side of building A (Figure 30) and enclosed with a protective fence. The ventilation is routed with internal ducts to each individual space in the school. The ventilation ensures sufficient air quality (microclimate, pollution) and transfer, but also functions as an additional vector for space heating or cooling, depending on the regime of operation.

Figure 32. Example of the ventilation distribution system in classrooms

The existing oil boiler will be primarily retained to ensure adequate heating of the buildings under extreme operating conditions (prolonged duration of very low temperatures as well as e.g. natural disasters and grid failure scenarios). The local project development team is also considering the potential future adaptation of the boiler to be supplied by waste cooking oil from the joint kitchens of the branch school and kindergarten. In the context of existing (2024) and likely future legislative changes for distribution network surcharges on the national level, the existing boiler may be utilized for potential cost optimization (reducing peak loads from the electricity grid, operating heat pumps at an optimal COP with potential supplementary heating from the oil boiler).

Figure 33. Existing oil boiler integrated as a back-up energy source

Renewable energy production systems

On-site renewable energy production is provided by two roof-top solar photovoltaic power plants installed in a hybrid (grid-tied and off-grid operation) setup on both buildings. The system installed on building A features the maximum coverage of the southern roof with 82 monocrystal modules and a capacity of 36,80 kW_p. The module connections are equipped by power optimizers. The modules are connected in six (6) strings with three (3) units of 3-phase hybrid inverters (12 kVA, 400 V), altogether 36 kVA of capacity. The second solar power system placed on building B is positioned on the southeastern side and features 87 modules once again in a six (6) string configuration with three (3) units of 3-phase hybrid inverters (12 kVA, 400 V) with nominal power output of 40,02 kW_p.

Figure 34. PV installation on building A

Figure 35. PV installation on building B

The photovoltaic (PV) production is primarily used to meet the building's electrical consumption. Surplus energy is primarily stored in the battery for later use (load shift). The setup however allows for grid-tied operation (PS.3A connection scheme) which is still necessary due to unavailability of economically viable technological equipment for long-term energy storage with sufficient capacity.

Battery Electric Storage Systems (BESS)

The configuration features two independent BESS to maximize the on-site renewable energy utilization and energy self-sufficiency. Both systems are based on a modular battery system based on Lithium Iron Phosphate - LiFePO₄ (LFP), with 30 kWh of capacity (51,2 V). The system in building A features two units with a total capacity of 60 kWh (placed in a separate space next to the boiler room), while the system in building B features a single unit at 30 kWh and is located on a separated space on the eastern side. The batteries are connected to the battery ports/terminal on the hybrid inverters (parallel, FG160R16 2x95 mm²).

Figure 28. Battery Electric Storage System (building A)

BMS

The proposed Building Management System (BMS) is carried out under the integration of all the subsystems (including thermal and ventilation system, PV system and BESS) of the building to grant total control of the installation while providing the best and greatest use of information to enhance the results of building management. This system also provides the site with air quality monitoring including humidity, temperature, CO₂, formaldehyde, VOC (Volatile Organic Compounds) and concentration of particulate matter. The air quality sensors connected to the system are physically placed in several locations (covering all classrooms and hallways) in building A.

The platform has a system for managing energy data; the BMS system can manage histories, trending as many energy variables as necessary, partialising, totalising, etc.

The system has the option of managing alarms with functions that, for example, prevent the operator from hiding or temporarily getting rid of alarms, reactivating them automatically at a certain time.

System navigation is map-based, to display information only as needed for detailed and intuitive navigation, and support touch control for quick use and training, with the ability to view and manage multiple facility systems in one place, including information on the efficiency and energy performance of the building in real time.

Operator and occupant training/onboarding

Operator training: The operator trainings were structured with a two-tiered approach focused on specific categories of involved persons: 1. personnel working on-site the demonstration buildings and 2. internal personnel at KSENA as the energy manager of public buildings in the City municipality of Velenje (remote monitoring and management). The trainings in the former category regularly included building custodians, the responsible IT manager and representatives of subcontractors in charge of regular system maintenance, warranty and post-sale technical support. For this category the trainings were principally carried out on-site the buildings in which comprehensive know-how and specific instructions about individual components, system operations, data acquisitions, risk mitigation, setpoints, safety issues and other important aspects of the demonstration building were addressed and conveyed. The operator trainings were physically conducted on a regular basis following the system commissioning and operational testing in 2025. Delayed delivery of the final version of the BMS system allowed for two expert workshops for remote system management, which were carried out in April and May 2025. The workshop covered an introduction to system features and user interface, system actuation and operation of individual technological components, documentation of system performance, etc.

On the side of training of internal staff at KSENA the activity was based on the establishment of a task force including 3 senior energy managers in late 2023. At the time of demonstration system development and commissioning the task force met regularly to address pending challenges, expectations and requirements of the BMS/demonstration system operation. The task force was actively involved in the codesign procedure and BMS design (user interface, functions, notifications and troubleshooting, documentation, etc.)

System maintenance and operation training with technology providers was also carried out on-site with the OEMs (technology suppliers), installers (subcontractors), building custodians and KSENA.

Occupant training: The demonstration system is designed to minimize the capacity of building user to independently operate the systems, which follow highly automated operation based on optimization algorithms, prediction of operation and pre-defined setpoints.

The occupants however (including the headmaster of the schools, teachers and other school employees, president and members of the district government of Vinska Gora, etc.) have been closely included in the project implementation through full transparency and timely disclosure of project objectives, advancements in project implementation, achieved performance and so forth.

An awareness raising campaign was facilitated in May 2025, which was concluded with a practical workshop on-site the branch elementary school in Vinska Gora. The workshop was tailored to younger pupils and introduced participants to main types of RES: solar, wind, hydro, geothermal, biomass and hydrogen technologies through an PowerPoint presentation and hands-on demonstrations. The session detailed how photovoltaic panels, wind turbines, hydropower plants and geothermal systems convert natural flows into electricity or heat, outlined battery, thermal and grid storage strategies and compared several types of heat pumps (air/ground/water). The presentation was backed by live demonstrations, including mini PV setup, wind turbine models, a hydrogen electrolyser and fuel cell, to demonstrate electrolysis process and usage of produced hydrogen through fuel cell and power consumers like electromotors and LED lamps. Thus the theory was directly translated into observable effects of energy transformations.

Second part of the training was dedicated to presentation of installed PV system and battery storage system at the school, along with the presentation of installed heating/cooling system, based on air-air heat pumps system.

The presentation included also live presentation of solar powerplant electronic management system, showcasing the energy flows from PV - energy storage - energy users (heating and cooling system) and emitting the excessive power to the grid. The presentation of installed heating/cooling EMS was also presented with data analytics, trends, scheduling and basic setups of the system.

Attendees reported an increased confidence in installed systems schools and homes as well as appreciation for clear explanations of technical jargon and practical experiment-based presentation.

Challenges overcome at the site

Existing capacity of local electricity distribution network

Challenge and cause: The planned prototype included the installation of electrical equipment for which permits (connection permits) were mandatory. The process of permit acquisition was constrained by the capacity of the existing transformer station, which was oversaturated on the demand/supply side. Prior to choosing the demonstration site, the member of the buyers group and coordinator for the demonstration site in Vinska Gora KSENA checked the status with the distribution system operator Elektro Celje d.d. (DSO). The DSO disclosed plans that the existing transformer station will be comprehensively renovated, i.e. a new one with higher capacity was to be constructed in 2022. The buildings would on the basis of this be granted permission to increase capacity of existing metering points and connect new electrical equipment. However, the planned construction of the new transformer station was tied to the construction project of a multiapartment building planned nearby the demonstration site. The building construction project had a big impact on the planned construction of the local transformer station, whereby the private investment was foreseen to also cover a large part of the new transformer station cost. Planned

construction of the multiapartment building next to demonstration site in Vinska Gora was rescheduled several times during the project (private investor). The uncertainty and lack of transparency led to substantial delays as well as difficulty in project development. Following several postponements the construction of the multiapartment building was halted for an unspecified duration. The investment into the new transformer station was thereby also put on hold indefinitely, constituting a physical limitation and no possibility of connecting any additional loads to the distribution network. The situation was exacerbated by the impact of natural disasters in Slovenia (most notably the extreme flooding event in August 2023) which forced new demands on the DSO for investing into damaged infrastructure, shifting priorities from non-critical renovation and further limiting resources.

Mitigation actions:

- Regular communication and coordination with the DSO (communication through telephone, email and in-person meetings).
- Drafting official letters addressed to DSO management and department leaders.
- Searching for alternative investment sources to cover co-financing for the new TS construction.
- Exploring alternative ways to introduce active load-management and demand side response on the basis of network saturation in near real time.
- Preparing and revising the applications for connection.
- Active cooperation with the local government (municipality and district government) in identifying opportunities to reduce system load by reorganizing/renovating connections in other areas on the boundary between local transformer stations.

Solution: Partially rewiring of a district on the boundary between local transformer stations, effectively reducing the load of the adjacent transformer station TP VINSKA GORA: 2750 which facilitated the possibility for connection.

Existing capacity and state of internal electrical connections

Challenge and cause: The internal electrical infrastructure of the demonstration buildings was neither dimensioned nor maintained to support the addition of new high-power loads (e.g., heat pumps, ventilation units, battery systems). Outdated wiring, undersized circuit breakers and lack of spare capacity in electrical cabinets posed serious safety and technical constraints. The initial on-site technical inspection carried out within WP1 did not immediately reveal the scope of renovation challenges as the electrical schematics did not reflect the as-built state. In some cases, previous undocumented upgrades or temporary fixes introduced safety risks and non-compliance with current standards.

Mitigation actions:

- Implementation of a detailed technical audit of internal electrical installations with certified electricians.
- Preparation of updated electrical plans reflecting the real state of the installations.
- Development of comprehensive project development plans for cabling, circuit breakers, and electrical cabinets (PZI, PID).
- Coordination with the building owner, facility managers and subcontractors to schedule shutoffs during low-usage hours and holidays.
- Introduction of internal sub-metering to better control and monitor loads after renovation.

Solution: Targeted renovation and upgrading of internal wiring and distribution panels in critical zones allowed (including a comprehensive overhaul of electrical cabinets housing the metering point connection) for safe integration of new electrical equipment without compromising building safety or compliance.

Limited space for hardware installation

Challenge and cause: The demonstration buildings lacked designated technical rooms or sufficient utility space for the installation of new HVAC systems, electrical inverters battery storage units and communication infrastructure (e.g., data loggers, BMS gateways). Historic building layouts and protected structural elements further limited the possibilities for invasive works or layout modifications. In some areas, access and safety clearances for equipment maintenance could not be guaranteed, posing regulatory issues.

Mitigation actions:

- PCP procuRE supplier consortium PARadISE carried out a comprehensive site assessment and produced a detailed 3D model of the building.
- Optimization of equipment layout using modular and wall-mounted hardware options.
- Revision of the installation project for ventilation (local internal units replaced by centralized unit placed externally).
- Engagement of structural engineers to verify load-bearing capacities of attic and basement zones.
- Installed key technical components externally on an outlying location on the northwestern secluded side of the building that was non-problematic to building users (e.g., central ventilation unit and heat-pump assembly).
- Coordinated with the fire inspector and safety authorities to ensure compliance with evacuation and clearance regulations.

Solution: A combination of custom hardware configuration, structural assessments and creative use of vertical or external space enabled the safe and compliant installation of all required technical systems.

Availability and state of building documentation

Challenge and cause: Accurate and up-to-date building documentation (electrical plans, structural layouts, HVAC diagrams, etc.) was largely missing or outdated. Much of the original design documentation was either lost or no longer reflected the current state of the buildings due to undocumented renovations over the years. This lack of reliable data led to significant delays in the preparation of project designs, permit applications, and safety analyses. A substantial challenge was the issue of structural integrity analysis of the roof in building B, whereby through further analysis a misrepresentation in the available documentation was discovered, indicating that additional measures are necessary to improve load bearing capacity.

Mitigation action:

- In-depth on-site surveys to reconstruct missing documentation (as-built condition reports).
- 3D (CAD and BIM models) development for accurate floorplan measurements and technical schematics.
- Coordinated closely with municipal archives and former contractors to retrieve any available legacy documentation.

- Once warned about the risks, the municipality has obtained project documentation for improving structural load-bearing capacity of the roof in building B and will finance the construction projects (outside procuRE).

Solution: The project team developed a comprehensive and accurate digital model of the building infrastructure, which enabled more precise planning and facilitated smooth permitting and contractor coordination.

Policy shift prompted and revision of local budget for building renovation

Challenge and cause: In the course of the project, a change in local government policy direction due to external circumstances (COVID-19, supply chain disruptions and price increases of pending local utility projects, natural disasters – namely flooding event in 2023, etc.), resulted in a re-evaluation of municipal budget priorities. Initially secured funding for co-financing the building renovation in Vinska Gora (covering the financing gap), particularly for the planned refurbishment of the thermal envelope, was delayed indefinitely. This uncertainty in co-financing firstly disrupted scheduling and later had an impact in terms of increased overall requirements for the technical equipment performance.

Mitigation action:

- Maintained close communication with municipal representatives and involved them in decision-making.
- Submitted updated financial scenarios and impact assessments to justify continued investment.
- Explored phased implementation models to align with revised budget timelines.
- Sought complementary funding through national recovery and resilience funds (unsuccessfully).

Solution: System designed included the requirements for efficient technical operation despite increased energy losses and increased performance demand. The renovation of passive energy system in the demonstration site are scheduled to be completed at a later point. Existing oil boiler maintained in the system for reserve and back-up in case of extreme weather events.

Availability of sufficiently qualified local subcontractors and supply chain disruptions

Challenge and cause: The period of project implementation (in particularly during demonstration pilot development) the availability of skilled subcontractors — particularly for specialized tasks such as, high-efficiency HVAC installation, and advanced electrical works, BMS integration — was severely limited. The overheated construction sector which saw record demand with increased financial liquidity in public and private budgets post the COVID-19 respite and the competition with other post-flood recovery projects stretched available human resources. Smaller projects such as the development of the pilot demonstration sites were comparatively less attractive to service providers. Scheduling conflicts and high-standards in terms of required references of service providers to work on the public buildings became limiting factors for maintaining timelines and system performance standards.

Mitigation action:

- Started early engagement with subcontractors to pre-book their services.
- Broadened the search area to include regional providers willing to travel.

- Prioritized subcontractors with prior experience in EU-funded or public sector energy projects.
- Provided clear technical documentation and supervision to ensure quality assurance.
- Introduced penalty/bonus clauses into subcontractor agreements to incentivize timely delivery.

Solution:

Through strategic planning, early engagement and quality oversight, the project team secured the necessary expertise and minimized delays in implementation caused by labour shortages.

2.3.6 Villa Nova de Gaia, Portugal (SEBR)

The Centro Escolar Manuel António Pina in Vila Nova de Gaia, covering 4,075 m² includes various educational facilities and is equipped with a natural gas boiler for heating, VRF units (heat pump) for cooling of management rooms (no cooling for classrooms), and a solar thermal plant covering 50% of the domestic water heating needs. The building also features a building management system (BMS) that controls shading, lighting, and room sensors, though it does not control each room temperature and doesn't have energy consumption monitoring. The renovation focused on integrating additional renewable energy sources and upgrading the BMS to include full HVAC system control and energy monitoring capability.

Table 11. Existing system and key upgrades in the Villa Nova de Gaia demo site

METRIC →	STATUS	KEY UPGRADES				
BUILDING/ SIZE [m ²] ↓	INTER.	Demand-side		Supply and storage		Control and monitoring
		HVAC systems		RES	BESS	BMS
		Heating & cooling	Ventilation	Production	Storage	Management
4,075	<i>Before</i>	Gas boiler, air-water HP, VRF	present	-	Solar thermal for DHW with low efficiency	-
	<i>After</i>	1 air-water HP (235 kW _{th})	No interv.	-	Solar Thermal for DHW improved hydraulics and control PV (119 kWp)	BESS (172 kWh)

Implemented upgrades

HVAC system

Air conditioning of the pre-intervention building is provided by various systems. The general system is based on 2 gas boilers with a two-pipe water/air distribution that heats the building and also takes care of DHW production. In addition to this, there are 2 AHUs with dedicated VRFs that provide diffuse heating and cooling in the north wing of the building. In some rooms, also in the north wing, there are individual VRFs (with indoor and outdoor apparatus) for additional customised climate control.

The gas boiler is replaced with an air-water heat pump with a heat output of 230 kW for cooling and 235 kW for heating, allowing not only heating from a possibly renewable source but also cooling throughout the building, improving the building's adaptability to climate change. In order to allow cooling in the hot season without changing the two-pipe distribution system and without compromising the possibility of DHW during the hot season, Energaia adjusted the existing solar panel system by connecting the 2 DHW tanks resistance and 1 gas boiler (backup) to function as storage and backup. The resistance of the DWH tanks are connected to the BMS which will then control the ON/OFF if the temperature of the tanks are below 50°C. Also, the BMS will control the

solar thermal panels energy delivery. The hydraulic and BMS control system was designed to prioritize solar thermal always, if the HP is in heating mode, thermal energy can be provided to the DHW tanks when solar thermal isn't appropriate to be used. When the HP is in cooling mode the resistance will then be the backup for the DHW, since as mentioned, solar thermal system has priority.

The hydraulic change allowed also to proceed with schedule Legionella treatment through the BMS.

Figure 30. Heat Pump installation on EBMAP

PV system

A 119 kWp PV system is installed on the roof. The PV production is primarily used to cover building electric consumption. If there is a PV surplus, this is firstly stored in the battery for later usage or, in case the battery is already fully charged, this is sent to the grid. A collective self-consumption registration will be done in order to use the surplus at other municipal buildings in the near surroundings, namely High-Performance Center, support building of Lavandeira Green Park and Municipal sports Stadium.

Electric battery

An electric battery with a nominal capacity of 172 kWh is installed. To ensure the safety of the battery system from external influences, it was decided to locate the batteries outside the building, in one outdoor patio. A protective metal fence was built around the batteries to prevent intrusion and possible hits. Within this fence, the PV inverters were also installed.

Figure 31. PV installation and Batteries on EBMAP

BMS

A new BMS is deployed to the demo. It monitors the different systems installed, i.e. the HVAC system, the PV system, the battery, electricity consumption of the building per floor and HVAC as well as indoor environment conditions (temperature, humidity, level of CO₂). The existing BMS is integrated inside the Mondas Platform, a SaaS system which allows to gather every information of the building, from performance of the systems to internal air quality, and compare it with external data and forecast. Moreover, it allows the implementation of specific controls for the HVAC and lighting systems.

Figure 32. BMS installation on EBMAP

Operator and occupant training / onboarding

Operator training:

The operators' training focused on the new building systems, namely the PV, BESS, heat pump and BMS.

The training objectives were to give understanding of the installed systems, actions for normal operation and actions on failure events.

Occupant training:

The supplier offered a training and awareness session on **May 29** for the school staff, focusing on raising awareness about climate and energy issues, informing them about the technologies used in the renovated school, and co-designing games they could use with children.

Challenges for the site

HVAC system

Challenge and cause: Heat Pump Location, planned location was on the roof of the building.

Mitigation Action: The final location of the HP was on the floor, thus closer to the boiler room.

The advantage was the weight of the equipment, on the roof needed validation in terms of the structure support. Also, in terms of logistics, it was easier and faster to place it on the floor instead on the roof.

Challenge and cause: Electrical power for the heat pump required a new 95 mm² cable.

Mitigation Action: The electrical connection for the heat pump could not be made on the boiler room cabinet, it required a new cable and a connection to the main electrical cabinet, located at a

considerable distance from the optimal installation site (>100 m). The final solution required additional time and budget due to unforeseen complexities, mainly the new cable.

Challenge and cause: Over voltage at the building transformer not allowing the heat pump first commissioning in May 2024

Mitigation Action: The over voltage correction had to be done before a new commissioning of the heat pump could be done. The process for the completion of the work had a delay due to the needed intervention of Vila Nova de Gaia Municipality technicians.

PV system

Challenge and cause:

Don't have a proper location to install the equipment related to the PV System

Mitigation Action: The inverters were to be installed inside the building in a technical area. Due to the temperature rise foreseen in the room, the equipment's were installed at an external area created for the PV invertors and BESS,

Challenge and cause: Changed the location of a part of the PV System (initially planned to install on top of the gym)

Mitigation Action: Due to the need for weight verification of the PV system on the roof top of the sports hall, it was analysed the possibility to have all the PV panels at the main building roof maintaining the PV power. With the technical analysis it was verified that there was space to include all the PV panels at the roof thus facilitating the system installation.

Challenge and cause: Unloading of the PV equipment's on the building roof

Mitigation Action: The delivery and unloading of the photovoltaic (PV) panels also posed challenges. To avoid the risk of damaging the children's playground, the unloading had to be conducted from the main street using a heavy-duty crane with an extended arm reach. This operation, which required blocking the road on a Saturday, resulted in additional costs.

Electric battery

Challenge and cause: Supplier information for the battery distribution within the technical area, was wrong

Mitigation Action: Planning phase for the distribution of the battery cabinets, sent by the supplier was changed at the implementation phase, causing an extra analysis and time to evaluate the correct distribution of the equipment's so that commissioning of the BESS was possible.

BMS

Challenge and cause: Total electrical consumption of the building

Mitigation Action: The analysis to the total electrical consumption and the total energy production (grid, battery and PV) was difficult to relate since the consumption was higher to the production.

It was found that the electrical meters were wrongly parameterized at the BMS system.

Challenge and cause: Internet failures

Mitigation Action: Due to the internet failures, the system needed to be full restarted a few times, but communication failures are occurring a few times a month.

Upgrade of HVAC solution during the deployment

Initially, the project scope was limited to providing heating for the school. However, the installers proposed a solution that also included cooling by introducing minor modifications to the existing infrastructure. These changes involved separating the climatization system from the domestic hot water (DHW) system. As these adjustments fell within the procure budget and were partially funded by Energaia and Vila Nova de Gaia Municipality, the proposal was approved.

3 Testing methodology

To thoroughly evaluate the outcomes of the procuRE pilots, the testing methodology was split into two distinct areas: Building Performance and User Experience. This split was necessary because the success of the renovations hinges not only on achieving technical benchmarks in energy efficiency and system integration but also on how well these systems are received and used by the building occupants and operators.

Building Performance focuses on quantifying the effectiveness of the integrated systems in meeting energy and environmental goals, using Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) such as energy consumption, renewable energy share, and indoor environmental quality as defined in the Challenge Brief.

User Experience addresses the experience of **procures** with the co-design process as well as the roll-out and training at the site. It covers accounts for the perspective of the building users in how they interact with the changed building and the new systems, their satisfaction with the indoor environment, and the usability of the technological solutions implemented.

3.1 Building performance

The methodology for testing building performance in the procuRE project was designed to rigorously evaluate the effectiveness of integrated systems in achieving energy efficiency, high indoor environmental quality (IEQ), and a significant reduction in environmental impact. The approach combined advanced HVAC systems, renewable energy sources (RES), and energy storage solutions, all managed through Continuous Commissioning. This process allowed for real-time monitoring and adjustments, ensuring that the buildings operated at peak efficiency throughout the testing period.

The Renovation Approach at each pilot site was tailored to the specific challenges and opportunities presented by the building and its environment. The integration of systems was key to ensuring that the buildings could achieve the maximum techno-economically feasible renewable energy share.

3.1.1 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

The performance of the renovated buildings was assessed using a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that provided a quantitative basis for evaluating the success of the renovations in achieving the project's goals. All KPIs used are extensively presented in the RfT TD2 "Challenge Brief". However, for the sake of clarity, in the following, the KPIs are briefly explained.

For the sake of clarity, the KPIs are divided into three groups that focus on aspects related to Energy efficiency and renewable energy production and consumption, indoor environmental quality, and environmental aspects.

Energy, Indoor environmental quality and Environmental KPIs should be assessed with at least an hourly time resolution for at least one year. However, due to the lack of enough monitoring data, it has been decided to assess these KPIs using dynamic simulations of the specific buildings and related systems (HVAC, PV systems). To ensure the results obtained from the models are reliable, the model has been validated against the monitored data available. The methodology followed and some results of the models' validation process are reported in Appendix 2.

Energy KPIs

The Energy KPIs are assessed starting from hourly data for an entire year.

The hourly data used for the KPIs calculation come from the validated models of the specific pilot sites. The same energy KPIs are calculated for the “before intervention” case based on the available buildings’ energy bills.

The energy KPIs used are the following:

- Final Energy Consumption (E_F): The total energy consumed by the building, measured in megawatt-hours per year (MWh/y) and kilowatt-hours per year (kWh/(m²·y)).
- On-Site Renewable Energy Production (RE_P): The amount of energy generated on-site from renewable sources, measured in MWh/y and kWh/(m²·y).
- Renewable Energy Share (RE_Sh): The percentage of the building’s total energy consumption met by renewable energy sources (in percentage).
- Renewable energy production to consumption ratio (RE_PCR): The ratio between the renewable energy produced in a certain hour and the building’s energy consumption in the same hour (in percentage).
- On-site renewable energy utilisation (RE_UT): The fraction of renewable energy produced on-site that is contemporaneously consumed or stored on-site (in percentage)

Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ) KPIs

- Temperature (IEQ_T): The number of hours per year (h/y) that the indoor temperature stays within a specified comfort range. In the procuRE project, the comfort range is defined in the range of 21 °C – 25 °C. If different ranges are considered, this is specified in the text.
- Air Quality (IEQ_AQ): Measured in parts per million (ppm) of CO₂, this KPI assesses the indoor air quality, focusing on ventilation and occupant comfort. The relevant indicator is the number of hours per year (h/y) in which the limit defined within the procuRE project (equal to 1000 ppm) is exceeded.
- Lighting conditions (IEQ_L) (valid only where the lighting system renovation is considered): This KPI evaluates the lighting comfort for the users at some desks/tables. The evaluation is done considering three indicators, which are the illuminance value (in lux), the Unified Glare Rating (UGR), and the Colour Rendering Index (CRI).

Environmental KPI

- CO₂ Emissions (E_CO2): The total CO₂ emissions associated with the building’s energy use, measured in tons of CO₂ per year (tCO₂/y).

Although for less than an entire year, these KPIs were continuously monitored to ensure that the buildings met or exceeded the performance targets. The data gathered was critical for making real-time adjustments through Continuous Commissioning, thereby maintaining optimal performance.

3.1.2 BMS, sensors and other data collection tools to ensure continuous performance

Continuous Commissioning was central to the testing methodology, enabling the real-time monitoring and adjustment of building systems to optimise performance. The process relied on several advanced tools and techniques:

- **Advanced Building Management Systems (BMS):** The BMS at each site served as the central hub for monitoring and managing the building’s energy systems. It collected real-time data from various sensors and adjusted HVAC settings, energy distribution, and storage to optimise energy use and maintain comfort.
- **Data Analytics:** Data collected by the BMS was used advanced to identify opportunities for optimisation. This allowed for proactive adjustments, preventing performance issues before they occurred.
- **Energy Monitoring Dashboards:** These dashboards provided visual representations of energy usage, RES generation, and storage levels. They were accessible to building managers, enabling them to make informed decisions about energy management.
- **Occupant Feedback Systems:** In some pilots, systems were in place to gather feedback from occupants about comfort and satisfaction. This feedback was integrated into the commissioning process, ensuring that the buildings met the needs of their users.

3.1.3 Smart Readiness Indicators (SRI) assessment

The procuRE project applied ex ante/ex post assessment (also called pre/post-renovation assessment in the following) with the Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) to evaluate the smartness of buildings. As reported on the webpage dedicated to SRI ⁴ the “smartness” of a building refers to its ability to sense, interpret, communicate and actively respond in an efficient manner to changing conditions in relation to the operation of technical building systems, the external environment (including energy grids) and the demands from building occupants. More details about this indicator can be found in the same reference.

SRI assessment process in procuRE

The SRI assessment method used is the detailed one (method B). This method has been chosen (instead of the simplified method A) as it allows for obtaining a more accurate assessment, and is the suggested method, especially in complex buildings, as the pilot sites considered in this project are (medium/large non-residential buildings).

The SRI assessment process in the procuRE project was structured around the use of the available documentation from [SRI2MARKET](#) Tool Suite⁵ and the excel file used as the basis for the tool development. The following steps were involved in the assessment process:

- **Pre-Renovation SRI Assessment:** Baseline SRI scores were established. This involved detailed checklists that assessed the presence and functionality of smart systems, providing a reference point for post-renovation comparisons.
- **Post-Renovation SRI Assessment:** After renovations were completed, a second SRI assessment was conducted to measure improvements in the building's smart readiness.

For all the pilot sites, the pre and post-renovation assessment is reported in section 4.1.

For each pilot site, the results presented are:

- The overall SRI score and related SRI class

⁴Details on SRI are available at: https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-efficient-buildings/smart-readiness-indicator_en

⁵Information about SRI to market platform available at: <https://sri2market.eu/>

- The specific scores for the seven impact criteria (energy efficiency, maintenance and fault prediction, comfort, convenience, health, well-being and accessibility, information to occupants, energy flexibility and storage)
- The specific scores for the nine technical domains (heating, cooling, domestic hot water, ventilation, lighting, dynamic building envelope, electricity, electric vehicle charging, monitoring and control). None of the six pilot sites has implemented specific interventions for electric vehicle charging, as this was not within the scope of the procuRE project. The project focuses primarily on buildings and the utilization of locally produced renewable energy. For this reason, no results are reported for the electric vehicle charging domain.

In general, in all buildings, there has been an improvement in the SRI between pre and post-renovation, with the overall SRI score passing from 15-30% (pre-renovation) to 60-80% (post-renovation), depending on the specific pilot site. While the pre-renovation situation was simply the existing status, the main limits for the post-renovation SRI are related to limitations specific to the pilot sites (e.g., some building services have been simply maintained in many cases) and to the fact that some aspects used in the SRI assessment were not part of the scope of the procuRE project (e.g., flexibility services to the electric grid).

It is also important to mention that, in the smart ready service assessment, it has been decided to assess the smart readiness services that are potentially available in the building. In other words, if a service is potentially available but not effectively used in a certain pilot site, it is assessed in any case as available, and the related functionality level is considered. One example to clarify this point could be represented by the possibility for the BMS to accommodate requests from the local Distributor Service Operator (DSO) managing the electric grid. In fact, the interaction with the electric grid and the accommodation of services in response to requests by the electric grid operator is an aspect that was not part of the scopes of the procuRE project. On the other hand, it is considered in the assessment of the SRI. In the SRI assessment done, it was considered that this kind of service is available from the BMS in all six pilot sites. This is because the BMS implemented by both suppliers can be managed remotely and can change the system control based on external inputs. This implies that, in principle, the BMS can handle inputs coming also from the local electric grid operator.

3.2 User experience

Understanding how operators and occupants perceive and interact with the new systems is critical to the overall success of the project. To capture these insights, a comprehensive user experience assessment approach has been developed, focusing on qualitative feedback collection through structured surveys.

This section provides an overview of how user satisfaction and interaction with the renovated buildings were assessed. The following aspects of user experience were systematically evaluated:

- Co-design process for procurers
- Survey for operators

3.2.1 Co-design process for procurers

The primary goal of the expanded co-design survey is to assess the preparedness of building operators and key stakeholders in managing the newly implemented building systems. Originally, the survey was focused on evaluating the effectiveness of the co-design process between suppliers

and procurers, ensuring a collaborative approach to developing Renovation Packages that could deliver high shares of renewable energy.

Key aspects of the co-design survey are:

- **Toolkit Accessibility:** Questions assessed whether the toolkit provided easy access to both the current and previous versions of the Renovation Packages, and whether it facilitated the involvement of external experts.
- **Communication and Decision-Making Processes:** Procurers evaluated their understanding of the communication and decision-making processes between suppliers and procurers.
- **Information Quality:** The survey included questions about the adequacy, transparency, and quality of the information provided regarding the renovation solutions.
- **Renovation Package Overview:** Procurers were asked to provide feedback on the initial overview of the Renovation Package and how it compared to standard building renovation solutions, focusing on the major features introduced by the co-design procedure.

Timing

The survey was implemented as a scorecard, filled out periodically (Phase I, Phase II start and Phase II end, as well as Phase III) by each procurer team to monitor and improve the co-design process. In Phase III, the remaining Suppliers are only rated by the Procurer they worked with.⁶

Additionally, as part of the deployment of Phase III activities, procurers have had access to the training materials to provide early feedback. Their evaluations have been collected as part of the documentation process to assess the training and awareness component in terms of

- **Training Effectiveness:** to evaluate the clarity, relevance, and practical application of the training, ensuring that operators and stakeholders are adequately prepared.
- **System Usability:** to collect feedback on the integration of the new systems into daily operations, emphasising ease of use and identifying any challenges.
- **Identifying Gaps:** to encourage procurers and operators to highlight areas where the training or system implementation might need further improvement.

3.2.2 Survey for operators

A separate survey was conducted with building operators to gather their insights on managing the new systems. This survey focused on key areas including the usability of the Building Management System (BMS), the effectiveness of the training received, and any challenges encountered during daily operations.

Key Areas of Focus:

- **System Usability:** The survey assessed how user-friendly the new Building Management System and other technologies were. It examined whether operators could perform their duties efficiently and identified areas where the system required improvement.
- **Training Effectiveness:** The survey evaluated the training provided to operators, determining how well it had prepared them to manage the new systems. It also identified any gaps in knowledge or confidence that required further training.

⁶ Given that in Phase III there were two suppliers, the procurers were distributed so that each supplier would work with three procurers only.

- **Operational Challenges:** The survey captured any challenges operators faced during system operation, including issues with system integration, maintenance, or technical problems that affected efficiency.
- **Maintenance Requirements:** Operators provided feedback on the maintenance needs of the new systems compared to previous ones. This helped to assess whether the new systems had simplified maintenance tasks or introduced new complexities.
- **Impact on Energy Performance:** The survey gathered operators' views on the impact of the new systems on the building's energy performance. Their feedback was crucial for understanding whether the renovations met energy efficiency goals.

The survey for operators is provided in Appendix 1 of this document.

Timing

The survey was conducted two to three months after the systems became operational. The aim of this timing was to allow operators to familiarise with the systems and identify any issues early on during the implementation so that suppliers could fix them and facilitate support, whenever needed.

4 Pilot outcomes

4.1 Building performance

The outcomes indicate successful integration of systems and potential for replication of project goals in terms of renewable energy supply and reduced emissions.

The following sub-sections report, for the six pilot sites, the KPIs presented in section 3.1. The results are reported at yearly level with some specific analysis at a shorter time frame when this is useful to highlight some aspects related to the building and related systems' operation.

The results reported in this section concerning the post-renovation status are obtained from dynamic simulations of a model of each pilot site (including the building and the related energy systems) that has been validated against monitored data according to the procedure specified in the Appendix 2. The use of a model instead of using directly monitored data is because not enough monitored data were available to calculate the KPIs as described in Appendix 3 (taken from the Challenge Brief). The validation procedure that both suppliers performed was an important step to prove that the simulation results are representative of the building's operation and related energy consumption.

The following figure summarises the improvements of absolute performance indicators measured in MWh/y with full detail provided for each site below. Final energy consumption (E_F) from fossil fuels is cleared except for Vila Nova de Gaia and Istanbul. Final electricity consumption increases at sites that switch from fossil fuel boilers to heat pump systems, while it decreases slightly at other sites that already use heat pump systems thanks to improved efficiency. Renewable energy production (RE_P) passes from 0 (except Barcelona) to the technical and economical maximum feasible

Figure 33. Overview of absolute key performance indicators across six pilot sites

The following figure summarises the improvements of relative performance indicator. Renewable energy share (RE_Sh) passes from 0 (except Barcelona where production was in place before) to a range of 30 – 100 % depending on the site. The ratio of renewable energy production to electric demand (RE_PCR) passes from 0 (except Barcelona) to a range of 30 – 150 % depending on the site. The utilisation of renewable energy produced (RE_UT) passes from 0 (except Barcelona) to a range of 40 – 100 % depending on the site.

Figure 34. Overview of relative key performance indicators across six pilot sites

4.1.1 Nuremberg, Germany (SEBR)

Energy KPIs

Two different post-renovation simulations have been performed in general by SEBR consortium, one with standard control logic (the ones initially applied in the pilot site) and one with an optimized control logic developed by the supplier to reduce energy consumption, ensuring (or improving) at the same time the comfort conditions in the building during occupancy hours. The simulation results with both control logics are reported in the related renovation package, while in this document, only the results of the optimized simulation are presented and compared with the pre-intervention status. This choice has been made to highlight the possible improvements related not only to the installation of new systems but also to their control. Although not applied yet, the developed optimized control is ready to be applied, and it is planned to be applied through the MONDAS platform in the next winter season, as the optimized control is focused on improvements related to the system management in the cold season.

The energy KPIs, already briefly described in section 3.1, are reported for the pre and post-intervention status for the Nuremberg pilot site in **Error! Reference source not found..** In this table it can be noted how the gas consumption was mainly used for space heating purposes before the renovation. This consumption, in the range of 7550 m³/y or 70⁷ MWh_{th}/y is reduced to 0 (or a minor contribution can be assumed in particular weather conditions like extreme cold days throughout the year, if present) after renovation. On the other hand, the use of the newly installed heat pump system to cover the building’s space heating load resulted in an increased post-renovation electrical consumption (passing from around 49 MWh_{el}/y to around 71 MWh_{el}/y).

Regarding the renewable energy production, before the renovation, any on-site renewable energy system was installed in Nuremberg, resulting in all the other energy KPIs reported in Table 10 equal to 0 for the pre-intervention situation. The installation of the PV and battery system resulted in a

⁷ This value is calculated starting from the gas consumption in m³/y and considering for the calculation a Net Heating Value (NHV) for gas of 0.9*GCV (Gross Calorific Value) according to the IEA report available at:

https://iea.blob.core.windows.net/assets/3bd426e0-86f5-4b05-90d5-4552dc842963/Gas_documentation.pdf

For Germany, the GCV is 37383 kJ/m³ according to “Consumption” column in pag. 66 of the previously mentioned IEA document

yearly PV production in the range of 83 MWh/y (around 955 kWh/(kWp·y)), a value aligned with the prediction from the PVGIS interactive tool⁸.

The Renewable Energy Share (RE_Sh) indicates that, over the entire year, 53 % of the building’s electric consumption is covered using renewable electricity produced on-site (both produced and instantaneously consumed or temporarily stored in the battery). The main reason that limits this value is the temporal mismatch with the period with the highest building’s electric consumption (the winter season), which corresponds to the minimum PV production, and the period with the lowest building’s electric consumption, which corresponds to summer and is associated with the highest PV production.

The Renewable Energy Production to Consumption Ratio (RE_PCR) resulted higher than 100 % (116 %). This means that, over the entire year, the renewable energy produced is higher than the building’s electric consumption.

Regarding finally the Renewable Energy Utilisation (RE_UT), the value reported in the table below (46 %) indicates that around half of the PV production is used within the building (instantaneously or after being temporarily stored in the battery), while the rest is sent to the grid. This export to the grid is mainly concentrated in summer months for the already mentioned temporal mismatch between the building’s consumption and PV production.

As better explained in the renovation packages specific for the site, strategies to improve renewable energy share and renewable energy utilisation KPIs could benefit from a deeper study on load shifting to hours with higher local renewable energy production, ensuring, in any case, the users comfort conditions. Other possible aspects to investigate in the future, although they resulted not techno-economically feasible actually, regard the study of the feasibility of seasonal storages (thermal, H₂) and/or the participation in an energy community, where the surplus of renewable energy produced on-site can be eventually exploited at a higher economic value.

Table 12. Yearly energy KPIs for the Nuremberg pilot site before and after intervention.

Building size		Energy KPIs, energy vector(s), and related units			Before/after intervention	
Floor area [m ²]	Energy KPI	Energy vector	Unit	Before	After	
3,072	Final Energy Consumption (E_F)	Gas	MWh/y / (kWh/m ² /y)	70.656 (23.0)	0 (0)	
		Electricity	MWh/y / (kWh/m ² /y)	49.260 (16.0)	71.372 (23.2)	
	Renewable Energy Production (RE_P)	Electricity	MWh/y / (kWh/m ² /y)	0 (0)	83.113 (27.1)	

⁸ PVGIS tool available at: https://re.jrc.ec.europa.eu/pvg_tools/en/

Renewable Energy Share (RE_Sh)	Electricity	%	0	53
Renewable Energy Prod. to Cons. Ratio (RE_PCR)	Electricity	%	0	116
Renewable Energy Utilisation (RE_UT)	Electricity	%	0	46

Note: The values of final energy consumption (E_F) and on-site renewable energy production (RE_P) are reported both in MWh/y and, in brackets, in kWh/m²/y

In addition to the yearly KPIs reported in the table above, the following paragraphs aim to give a more detailed assessment, analysing the Energy KPIs and the electric energy flows in three weeks considered representative of the building’s operation in winter, mid-season, and summer respectively.

Figure 35 shows, for the first week of February, the simulation results in terms of building electric consumption and PV production. The other Energy KPIs (RE_Sh, RE_PCR, RE_UT, all in percentage) are also reported and should be read on the right y-axis of the figure.

As can be noted in the first week of February, the building's electric consumption is distributed in the period between 5-6 A.M. to 5 P.M. The main consumption is due to the heat pump system used to cover the space heating building’s needs. The PV production is limited and up to around 30 kW due to the low solar availability in this period. This is valid for all days except the 3rd and the 4th presented in the figure, as these two are weekend days, where the system is switched off, and a minor consumption can be seen.

The limited PV production and the relatively high electric consumption resulted in a low Renewable Energy Share (RE_Sh) that, in the first two and in the last two days of the first week of February is equal to the Renewable Energy Production to Consumption ratio (RE_PCR), as the PV production is entirely instantaneously self-consumed.

On the weekend days (3rd and 4th days in the figure), the PV production is almost always enough to completely cover the building’s electric consumption, resulting in a RE_Sh equal to 100 %. Moreover, in the same two weekend days, the RE_PCR shows values higher than 100 %, indicating that in some hours of the day, the PV production is higher than the building's electric consumption. In these hours, the battery can be charged, and this energy is used as soon as the building's electric consumption is higher than the PV production (beginning of the 5th day).

Finally, the Renewable Energy Utilisation (RE_UT) is equal to 100 % for most of the periods with PV production. This indicates that the PV production is almost always instantaneously self-consumed or, eventually, stored in the battery. The only period in which the RE_UT is between 0 and 1 is in the afternoon of the 4th day. In that moment, the PV production is higher than the building's electric consumption, and the battery is already fully charged. This implies that the PV surplus is, in that case, sent to the grid.

This description of the Energy KPIs also explains the Figure 36. This figure shows the electric energy flows within the building. In addition to the building's electric consumption and PV production shown in Figure 35, Figure 36 highlights the energy flows to and from the battery, to and from the electric grid, and the battery State of Charge (SoC) in percentage.

Figure 35. Nuremberg Energy KPIs (1-7 February)

Note: The quantities reported are: building electric consumption (red), PV production (yellow), Renewable Energy Share (RE_Sh, green, right y-axis), Renewable Energy Production to Consumption Ratio (RE_PCR, blue, right y-axis) and Renewable Energy Utilisation (RE_UT, purple, right y-axis). Hourly values for the period 1-7 February

Figure 36. Nuremberg electric energy flows and battery State of Charge (1-7 February).

Note: The quantities reported are: building electric consumption (red), PV production (yellow), energy to (light green) and from (dark green) battery, energy to (light blue) and from (dark blue) electric grid, battery SoC (dark green, line, right y-axis). Hourly values for the period 1-7 February

Figure 37 and Figure 38 show the same simulated quantities of Figure 35 and Figure 36 respectively, but for the period 15 – 22 March.

This period is considered as it is characterized by milder external temperatures, and, therefore, lower building space heating demand, representing a possible period of the mid-season. In addition, the period is characterized by higher PV production in comparison to the first week of February due to the higher solar irradiation.

As can be noted in Figure 37, the peaks in electric consumption generally occur in the early morning to re-establish the users’ comfort conditions after the night in which the indoor temperature set point is reduced and the heating system is generally switched off. These peaks are in the same range as the PV production peaks.

The RE_Sh is, for most of the time, equal to 100 %, indicating that the PV production and the battery capacity are sufficient to completely cover the building consumption at least in the last five days in the figures.

Moreover, on all days, there are some hours in which the PV production is higher than the electric consumption (RE_PCR higher than 100 %). In these moments, PV production is first used to charge the battery and then eventually sent to the grid.

The battery is generally charged in the hours just after noon, due to the still notable solar availability and the reduced electric consumption due to the fact that the building has already reached the indoor temperature set point, and a minor consumption is necessary to maintain this temperature. On the contrary, it is discharged generally in the early morning, when the heat pump system starts and there is no PV production yet.

Regarding the interaction of the building with the electric grid, the energy taken from the grid is concentrated in the early morning hours, just after the heating system switches on, when the energy from the PV and battery system is not enough to cover the building’s electric consumption. On the other hand, locally produced electricity is injected into the grid in the afternoon after the battery is fully charged. The amount of electrical energy sent to the grid is limited on the weekdays (all days except the 3rd and the 4th in Figure 37 and Figure 38), while on weekend days, most of the PV production is sent to the grid due to the limited building’s electric consumption.

Figure 37. Nuremberg Energy KPIs (15-22 March)

Note: The quantities reported are: building electric consumption (red), PV production (yellow), Renewable Energy Share (RE_Sh, green, right y-axis), Renewable Energy Production to Consumption Ratio (RE_PCR, blue, right y-axis) and Renewable Energy Utilisation (RE_UT, purple, right y-axis). Hourly values for the period 15-22 March

Figure 38. Nuremberg electric energy flows and battery State of Charge (15-22 March).

Note: The quantities reported are: building electric consumption (red), PV production (yellow), energy to (light green) and from (dark green) battery, energy to (light blue) and from (dark blue) electric grid, battery SoC (dark green, line, right y-axis). Hourly values for the period 15-22 March

Finally, Figure 39 and Figure 40 show the same variables presented above for the week 15-22 July, which is considered representative of a typical summer week.

As can be seen in the Figure 39, differently from the winter and mid-season analysed weeks, in the considered summer week there is a higher electric consumption during night because the mechanical ventilation is on during night to allow free-cooling of the building. This is the main consumption on weekend days (the 1st and the 7th day), while in the weekdays (from the 2nd to the 6th day) there is a higher electric consumption due to the typical use of the building. However, the building’s electric consumption in this week is notably lower than the one observed in previous figures for the winter and mid-season weeks. The electric consumption peaks are concentrated in the morning hours, they are similar among different weekdays, and in the range of 20 kW.

The PV production is instead higher than in the winter and mid-season week presented above due to the higher solar availability, with peaks in the range of 50 kW in the considered week. The PV and battery system can completely cover the building’s electric load in the considered week (RE_Sh equal to 100 % for the entire week), with the PV production that is higher than the electric consumption for most of the hours of the considered summer week (RE_PCR higher than 100 %). Moreover, PV production is used completely within the building generally only in the morning hours (RE_UT equal to 100 % in these hours).

Figure 40 highlights the electrical energy flows and the interactions among the PV system, battery, electric grid, and the building’s electric load. In this figure it is possible to note the battery charge occurring generally in the morning hours (light green area) and the battery discharge during night (dark green area). The battery discharge is in the range of only 30 % during the night. This suggests that possible future analysis could investigate more in detail the economic convenience and the technical feasibility of selling the stored electrical energy to the grid in specific periods (e.g., during the evening hours).

Regarding the interactions with the electric grid in the considered week, electricity is never taken from the grid, while it is sent to the grid generally in the afternoon, as soon as the battery is fully charged.

Figure 39. Nuremberg Energy KPIs (15-22 July)

Note: The quantities reported are: building electric consumption (red), PV production (yellow), Renewable Energy Share (RE_Sh, green, right y-axis), Renewable Energy Production to Consumption Ratio (RE_PCR, blue, right y-axis) and Renewable Energy Utilisation (RE_UT, purple, right y-axis). Hourly values for the period 15-22 July

Figure 40. Nuremberg electric energy flows and battery State of Charge (15-22 July).

Note: The quantities reported are: building electric consumption (red), PV production (yellow), energy to (light green) and from (dark green) battery, energy to (light blue) and from (dark blue) electric grid, battery SoC (dark green, line, right y-axis). Hourly values for the period 15-22 July

Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ) KPIs

Indoor environmental quality indicators are based on indoor temperature and CO₂ assessment. These indicators are assessed only during occupation hours (in the Nuremberg pilot equal to 1910 h/y) and in some building zones defined to extract useful indications about the indoor comfort conditions. In the Nuremberg pilot site, the assessment is done in two classrooms, one South-West oriented and one North oriented, to assess comfort in general and also overheating and underheating risks depending on the different zones’ orientation. In addition, the assessment is also done in one common zone to evaluate the comfort conditions in a differently used space.

Regarding the indoor temperature, the procuRE project defined in the RFT TD2 “Challenge Brief” the comfort range between 21 °C and 25 °C. However, it is considered useful to analyse not only the number of occupancy hours with indoor temperature in this range but also to assess the number of

hours outside this range, dividing them by different ranges (lower than 18 °C, between 18 °C and 21 °C, between 25 °C and 28 °C, and higher than 28 °C). This resulted in a more complete overview of the indoor temperature.

As summarized in **Error! Reference source not found.**, the procuRE comfort range is ensured for just over half of the occupancy hours in both classrooms. Nevertheless, for the rest of the occupancy hours, the indoor temperature is in any case in an acceptable range, with only a few hours lower than 18 °C and higher than 28 °C. This is also a result of the optimized control logic considered in the simulation, in which it is considered acceptable that the temperature is slightly below 21 °C in winter and slightly above 25 °C in summer. Moreover, in the same table it is possible to note, as expected, the higher number of cold hours (with indoor temperature lower than 21 °C) in the North-oriented classroom, and the higher number of hot hours (with indoor temperature higher than 25 °C) in the South-West oriented classroom.

Regarding the common zone, in comparison to the classrooms, a lower number of hours with indoor temperature in the procuRE comfort range can be noted in the same table, with, in particular, a higher number of cold hours. However, these are for the majority in the range of 18 °C and 21 °C and, also due to the usage of the common zone, can be considered not a problem.

Based on the reported results, it is considered that the post-intervention status is able to ensure the needed level of indoor comfort in terms of indoor temperature.

Table 13. Number of hours over the year with indoor temperature in defined ranges.

Indoor temperature range	Considered zones		
	Classroom S-W oriented (0.17 EG S-W Classroom)	Classroom N oriented (0.11 OG N Classroom)	Common zone
Below 18 °C	0	2	38
Below 21 °C	129	348	792
procuRE comfort range (21-25 °C)	1,086	11,61	717
Above 25 °C	672	399	363
Above 28 °C	23	0	0
Total	1,910	1,910	1,910

Note: In Nuremberg, the analysis is performed in three different zones: one classroom South-West oriented, one classroom North oriented, and a common zone

For what regards the CO₂ assessment in the same three building zones analysed above, the simulations show that, with the ventilation strategy considered, the limit fixed in the RfT TD2 “Challenge Brief” (equal to 1000 ppm) is never reached and the obtained CO₂ levels are always lower.

Environmental KPIs

The implemented renovation package resulted in a shift of the consumption for covering space heating building needs from gas to electricity, which can be partly covered using locally produced renewable electricity.

Accounting for the different emission factors of the different energy vectors, the yearly CO₂ emissions passed from 33.1 tCO₂/y (pre-intervention) to 12.8 tCO₂/y (post-intervention) with a reduction in the range of 61 % as summarized in Table 14. This calculation does not consider the beneficial effects in terms of CO₂ emission reduction due to the PV surplus exported to the grid.

Table 14. Yearly CO₂ emissions of pre and post-intervention situation and related savings. Nuremberg pilot site

Status	Energy vector	Final Energy consumption	CO ₂ factor	CO ₂ emission	CO ₂ emission savings	
		[MWh/y]	[tCO ₂ /MWh]	[tCO ₂ /y]	[tCO ₂ /y]	[%]
Before	Gas	70.560	0.202 ⁹	14.2	-	-
	Grid el.	49.260	0.383 ¹⁰	18.9	-	-
	Total	-	-	33.1	-	-
After	Gas	0	0.202 ⁹	0	-	-
	Grid el.	33.404	0.383 ¹⁰	12.8	-	-
	Total	-	-	12.8	20.3	61 %

Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI)

As reported in Table 15, in Nuremberg, the pre-intervention overall SRI score is in the range of 20 %, while the post-intervention value is in the range of 64 %. The main factors limiting the pre-intervention value were associated with the absence of any on-site renewable energy production and eventual storage system, and the absence of a proper BMS able to control and monitor the heating system.

The installation of a PV and battery system, the replacement of the existing gas boiler with a heat pump system, and the integration of all these systems and IEQ measurements in a unique BMS are the upgrades made at the pilot site, which lead to improvements also in the overall SRI score.

⁹ Standard value from IPCC, 2006 from Annex I available at:

<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/278ae66b-809b-11e7-b5c6-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

¹⁰ Value for the considered country from Table 2 IPCC GHG for the year 2021 (for Turkex and Israel the value is taken from Table 5 Other IPCC GHG for the year 2020), taken from: Bastos, Joana; Monforti-Ferrario, Fabio; Melica, Giulia (2024): GHG Emission Factors for Electricity Consumption. European Commission, Joint Research Centre (JRC) [Dataset] PID: <http://data.europa.eu/89h/919df040-0252-4e4e-ad82-c054896e1641>

Figure 42 shows the SRI for the different impact criteria. As can be noted in the figure, the criteria with the biggest improvements are related to energy flexibility, maintenance and fault detection, and occupants' information. The BMS is solely responsible for the improvement of the last two (maintenance and fault detection, and occupants' information) and partly responsible (with the rest due to the PV and battery installation) for the first (energy flexibility).

Regarding the analysis of the SRI calculated for the different technical domains, Figure 42 shows improvements in heating and ventilation technical domains due to the new heat pump system installed and to its control that can be based on different IEQ measurements, thanks to the connection and management through the BMS system. The improvements in the electricity and monitoring and control technical domains are instead partly due to new PV and battery systems and partly to the BMS (electricity) or solely to the BMS (monitoring and control). DHW, lighting and dynamic building envelope technical domains are instead equal in both pre- and post-intervention scenarios. This is because any intervention has been made on these technical domains.

Table 15. SRI overall score and related class before and after renovation, Nuremberg pilot site

Characteristic	Before intervention	After intervention
SRI overall score	21.0 %	63.6 %
SRI class	Between 20 % and 35 %	Between 50 % and 65 %

Figure 41. SRI for the different impact criteria. Nuremberg pilot site

Figure 42. SRI for the different technical domains. Nuremberg pilot site

4.1.2 Barcelona, Spain (SEBR)

Energy KPIs

The Table 16 reports the Energy KPIs for the Barcelona pilot site. As for the Nuremberg pilot site, the values are obtained from simulations using models validated against monitored data and an optimised system control.

As can be noted in this table, the building relies only on electricity both before and after renovation, and the renovation applied led to a modest decrease in the building's final energy consumption. The reasons, as better explained in the related renovation package, are mainly due to two aspects. First, the building hosts a municipal data centre that constitutes an important base load electric consumption. Second, in the optimization control strategy simulated, the priority was to improve the users' comfort as the post-renovation baseline, and also the user experiences, highlighted that comfort was an open point that deserves more attention.

Regarding the Renewable Energy Production (RE_P) KPI, before the renovation, a 5 kWp PV system was present. Considering that, from monitoring data of the building's electric consumption pre-intervention, a base load consumption in the range of 14 kW was always present, it is considered that the entire production of the PV system present before the renovation was self-consumed.

The main limiting factors in the renovation for what regards PV installation are related to the limited space available on the roof (which must also accommodate the main components of the HVAC system) and the fact that no PV can be installed on the façade because the building is under protection. For these reasons, the adopted solution focused on exploiting the maximum space available on the roof and installing also an additional PV system in the building vicinity. The overall PV system (with a peak power of 66 kWp) resulted in a yearly energy production of around 98 MWh/y, a value aligned with the PVGIS tool⁸ forecasts for the considered location. As already explained, the PV system installed is divided into two different systems, one on the roof and one on a pergola in the building vicinity. For the calculation of the Energy KPIs, the production of both parts of the PV system is considered as if the system is unique and directly connected to the building. Although this is not the actual status, with the electricity production of the PV pergola system that is actually injected into the electric grid, this represents a feasible option through the use of, for example, a remote self-consumption contract. Although there are some further steps needed to activate this kind of regime, this represents the final goal for the PV system operation.

Due to the already mentioned relatively high electric consumption and the limited space available for PV installations, the Renewable Energy Share (RE_Sh) is relatively low (32 %) compared to the project's original objectives, but, on the other hand, constitutes the optimal techno-economic solution based on all the boundary conditions encountered.

The same reasons explain also the relatively low, in relation to the project initial objective, but everything considered good value of Renewable Energy Production to Consumption Ratio (RE_PCR), which is in the range of 38 %.

Regarding the Renewable Energy Utilisation (RE_UT), it resulted equal to 84 %, indicating that the majority of the PV production is directly consumed within the building.

The last three KPIs mentioned above (RE_Sh, RE_PCR, RE_UT) could, in principle, benefit from the installation of a battery system. However, the installation of a battery system has been discarded as, actually, it is not (especially economically) a feasible option. This is mainly due to the high base

load consumption of the considered building and the limited PV excess production that is sent to the grid (value in the range of 15 MWh/y, or 16 % of the PV production, which corresponds to the complementary fraction to the 84 % represented by the RE_UT).

Table 16. Yearly energy KPIs for the Barcelona pilot site before and after intervention.

Building size		Energy KPIs, energy vector(s), and related units			Before/after intervention	
Floor area [m ²]	Energy KPI	Energy vector	Unit	Before	After	
2,350	Final Energy Consumption (E_F)	Electricity	MWh/y / (kWh/m ² /y)	270.832 (115.2)	260.736 (111.0)	
	Renewable Energy Production (RE_P)	Electricity	MWh/y / (kWh/m ² /y)	7.500 ¹¹ (3.2)	97.801 (41.6)	
	Renewable Energy Share (RE_Sh)	Electricity	%	3	32	
	Renewable Energy Prod. to Cons. Ratio (RE_PCR)	Electricity	%	3	38	
	Renewable Energy Utilisation (RE_UT)	Electricity	%	100	84	

Note: The values of final energy consumption (E_F) and on-site renewable energy production (RE_P) are reported both in MWh/y and, in brackets, in kWh/m²/y

The Figure 43, Figure 44, and Figure 45 present, for three different weeks representative of possible weeks in the cold, mid, and hot season respectively, the hourly time series of the building's electric consumption, PV production, and the three Energy KPIs calculated in percentage (RE_Sh, RE_PCR, RE_UT).

As can be noted in all three figures, and as already described in the previous paragraphs, the building presents a base load electric consumption in the range of 14 kW that is present through the entire year and mainly due to the data centre and the stand-by consumption of the different electric devices present in the building. In addition, as this pilot does not present any battery, the eventual PV surplus can only be injected into the grid.

As can be seen in Figure 43, in the considered winter week (1-7 February), the building's electric consumption varies between 14 and 80 kW, with the highest peaks concentrated in the morning and a decreasing trend in the afternoon when the building is already at the desired indoor temperature. The PV production reaches peaks up to around 35 kW due to the limited solar irradiation in the winter period and is almost always completely and instantaneously self-consumed within the building, resulting in RE_UT equal to 100 %.

¹¹ The PV production before intervention was estimated considering the size of the system present (5 kWp) and a specific production of 1500 kWh/(kWp·y), value aligned to the forecast from PVGIS tool⁸ for a PV system in the considered location, with slope 15° and azimuth 0 (south)

Moreover, the fraction of the electric load covered by the PV system reached up to 50 % in the hours around noon. As the PV production is instantaneously consumed within the building and any battery is present in this pilot site, the RE_Sh is equal to RE_PCR when there is no PV surplus.

The previous considerations are valid for all days except the 3rd and 4th day of the considered winter week. The reduced electric consumption on these days is because these are weekend days, with the building closed and the heating and cooling system switched off.

Figure 43. Barcelona Energy KPIs (1-7 February)

Note: The quantities reported are: building electric consumption (red), PV production (yellow), Renewable Energy Share (RE_Sh, green, right y-axis), Renewable Energy Production to Consumption Ratio (RE_PCR, blue, right y-axis) and Renewable Energy Utilisation (RE_UT, purple, right y-axis). Hourly values for the period 1-7 February

Figure 44 shows the same quantities but for a milder week (15-22 March). In comparison to the considered week in February, in the considered week in March the electric consumption is lower due to the lower building’s space heating load, which is a consequence of the milder external temperature. On the other hand, the PV production is higher in comparison to the considered February week due to the higher solar irradiation. These effects resulted in higher (up to around 70 %) RE_Sh in comparison to the considered February week. Nevertheless, the PV production on weekdays is, in any case, totally instantaneously self-consumed (RE_UT equal to 100 %).

Figure 44. Barcelona Energy KPIs (15-22 March)

Note: The quantities reported are: building electric consumption (red), PV production (yellow), Renewable Energy Share (RE_Sh, green, right y-axis), Renewable Energy Production to Consumption Ratio (RE_PCR, blue, right y-axis) and Renewable Energy Utilisation (RE_UT, purple, right y-axis). Hourly values for the period 15-22 March

Finally, Figure 45 presents the same hourly Energy KPIs already shown above, but for the considered summer week (15-22 July). In this period, the electric consumption peaks are shifted from the morning to the hours around noon, with peaks up to around 85 kW. This is mainly due to the space cooling thermal load that is maximum around noon.

Although the electric consumption and PV production peaks are now more in phase, and the PV production is at its maximum due to the high solar irradiation in July, the PV production covers only partially (up to around 70 %) the building’s electric consumption.

Figure 45. Barcelona Energy KPIs (15-22 July)

Note: The quantities reported are: building electric consumption (red), PV production (yellow), Renewable Energy Share (RE_Sh, green, right y-axis), Renewable Energy Production to Consumption Ratio (RE_PCR, blue, right y-axis) and Renewable Energy Utilisation (RE_UT, purple, right y-axis). Hourly values for the period 15-22 July

Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ) KPIs

In the Barcelona pilot site, as the lighting system renovation constituted an important part of the renovation package, in addition to the assessment in terms of indoor air temperature (in terms of number of discomfort hours per year) and indoor air quality (through the assessment of the CO₂ level), also the comfort related to the lighting system is evaluated.

Regarding the assessment in terms of indoor temperature situation, this is made considering only the occupancy hours and is focused on some spaces representative of or particularly important for the building’s usage. More specifically, five different zones are considered in the analysis. These are the plenary hall located in the basement, the citizen service counters (OMAP), which is a front office open to the public, located on the ground floor, and three offices located on the first, second, and third floors.

The Table 17 reports not only the number of hours in which the indoor temperature falls within the procuRE defined comfort range (21 °C – 25 °C) but also indications about how many hours are within a slightly larger range, which could be considered still a comfortable or almost comfortable situation (18 °C – 28 °C), and how many hours are below 18 °C and above 28 °C, situations characterized by a more important users’ discomfort.

From this analysis, it emerged that, in general, the discomfort is more related to underheating than overheating, and this affects all the analysed building zones. This is a characteristic of the considered building that was present also before the renovation, as it has been confirmed also through users' feedback.

For this reason, the optimized control strategy developed focused more on improving users' comfort, trying to reduce the number of discomfort hours. The optimized strategy, in comparison to the base control logic applied just after the renovation and related to system components typical operations and set points, improved only partially the users' comfort. More specifically, the optimized control strategy reduces the overheating problems present with the base control logic, but leads to limited improvements in terms of underheating hours.

Regarding the analysis on the single zones, the plenary hall presents an intermittent and limited usage over the year (used only 180 h/y). However, the dedicated HVAC system is well-sized and able to ensure, almost always, conditions that can be considered in a comfortable range, with few hours presenting temperatures in the range 18 °C – 21 °C and, basically, never lower than 18 °C. Moreover, the same zone does not present overheating problems based on the performed simulations.

Regarding the other zones considered (OMAP and the three offices on different floors), the situation, in terms of discomfort, is similar. These zones are used for around 2000 – 2700 h/y and present, for around 60% of the time, an indoor temperature in the range of 21 °C - 25 °C. Considering instead a slightly wider comfort range (18 °C – 28 °C), it emerged that the indoor temperature is in this range for more than 90 % of the time, highlighting, however, that temperatures in the range 18 – 21 °C are notably more common than temperatures in the range of 25 – 28 °C. A non-negligible amount of hours (up to around 9 % for the first floor analysed office) resulted in uncomfortable conditions and underheating, with zone temperatures lower than 18 °C.

Table 17. Number of hours over the year with indoor temperature in defined ranges.

Indoor temperature range	Considered zones									
	Plenary hall		OMAP		Office P1		Office P2		Office P3	
	Before	After	Before	After	Before	After	Before	After	Before	After
Below 18 °C		1		136		245		136		182
Below 21 °C		21		507		688		442		460
procuRE comfort range (21-25 °C)		158		1,675		16,22		1,331		1,277
Above 25 °C		0		149		109		89		79
Above 28 °C		0		17		0		0		0
Total		180		2,484		2,664		1,998		1,998

Note: In Barcelona, the analysis is performed in the Plenary hall, the citizen service counters (OMAP) and three offices located on the three floors (P1, P2, P3)

Regarding the CO₂ assessment in the considered five building zones, the simulations show that, with the ventilation strategy considered, which include mechanical ventilation system always in operation and also a contribution from natural ventilation in the typical occupancy hours (7:00 – 19:00), the limit fixed in the RfT TD2 “Challenge Brief” (equal to 1000 ppm) is never reached. The CO₂ level remains instead more in the range of 400 – 550 ppm. In principle, this information could be used to assess eventual different control logic reducing the mechanical ventilation system operation, aiming at reducing electric consumption but ensuring, at the same time, the comfort in terms of indoor air quality.

The lighting system renovation focused on part of the building and represented an important part of the overall renovation package. The renovation has been complemented by a simulation work to better define and estimate the renovation effects on the visual comfort of occupants and compliance with the actual standard.

The newly installed lighting system ensured the comfort requirements in terms of illuminance value (500 lux on the desks), Unified Glare Ratio (UGR), value always lower than 19, as suggested for office buildings, and in terms of Colour Rendering Index (CRI), value in the range of 90, which is considered excellent.

These results have been reached after a fine-tuning process in which some lights have been dimmed, some disconnected, and on some of them a vinyl film has been applied to reduce reflections. This tuning step was needed after some users expressed visual discomfort, mentioning an excessive brightness on some desks.

The figures below show the situation in terms of illuminance level (in lux) on the desks on the second floor of the building before renovation (Figure 46) and after the renovation and the above-mentioned tuning interventions (Figure 47). By comparing these two figures, it can be noted the improved level of illuminance, which passes from generally 170 lux – 400 lux to a range of 400 – 750 lux.

Figure 46. Illuminance (lux) on the tables on 2nd floor before renovation. Barcelona pilot site

Figure 47. Illuminance (lux) on the tables on 2nd floor after renovation and tuning. Barcelona pilot site

Environmental KPIs

Also before the intervention, the Barcelona pilot building was relying only on electricity as energy vector to cover all building’s energy needs.

The improvements in the HVAC system performance and lighting system resulted in minor electrical energy savings because the optimized control logic focused more on improving users’ comfort and not on saving energy only. The main improvements in terms of CO₂ emission reduction are associated with the replacement (and expansion) of the PV system.

On a yearly basis, the CO₂ emissions decreased from around 46 tCO₂/y (pre-intervention) to around 31.2 tCO₂/y (post-intervention), resulting in a percentage decrease in the range of 32 % as summarized in Table 18. This calculation does not consider the beneficial effects in terms of CO₂ emission reduction due to the PV surplus exported to the grid. This contribution would be in any case limited in the Barcelona pilot, as only a minor fraction of the PV production (around 15 MWh/y, equivalent to around 16 % of the total yearly PV production) is exported to the grid.

Table 18. Yearly CO₂ emissions of pre and post-intervention situation and related savings. Barcelona pilot site

Status	Energy vector	Final Energy consumption	CO ₂ factor	CO ₂ emission	CO ₂ emission savings	
		[MWh/y]	[tCO ₂ /MWh]	[tCO ₂ /y]	[tCO ₂ /y]	[%]
Before	Grid el.	263.619	0.175 ¹⁰	46.1	-	-
	Total	-	-	46.1	-	-
After	Grid el.	178.289	0.175 ¹⁰	31.2	-	-

Total	-	-	31.2	14.9	32 %
-------	---	---	------	------	------

Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI)

In the Barcelona pilot site, the overall SRI score passed from around 20 % (pre-intervention) to around 60 % (post-intervention) as reported in Table 19. In this pilot site, the main improvements are related to the installation of a BMS able to control and monitor the main building systems (HVAC, PV) based on the monitored IEQ conditions. In addition, the BMS can contribute to the maintenance of the main systems (heat pump, PV) through the analysis of the monitored data. The rest of the improvements can be associated with the renovation of the main heat pump system, the lighting system, and the PV system.

Figure 49 shows pre and post-renovation SRI scores for the different impact criteria. As highlighted in the figure, the main improvements are associated with impacts dependent only on the BMS (maintenance and fault prediction, information to occupants).

Regarding the SRI score for the different technical domains, as reported Table 19, the new heat pump system and the BMS are responsible for the improvements in the heating, cooling, and ventilation domains, while the new PV system and its monitoring through the BMS are responsible for the improvements in the electricity technical domain. Finally, the BMS is solely responsible for the improvement in the monitoring and control technical domain.

Table 19. SRI overall score and related class before and after renovation, Barcelona pilot site

Characteristic	Before intervention	After intervention
SRI overall score	19.3 %	60.4 %
SRI class	Lower than 20 %	Between 50% and 65%

Figure 48. SRI for the different impact criteria. Barcelona pilot site

Figure 49. SRI for the different technical domains. Barcelona pilot site

4.1.3 Vila Nova de Gaia, Portugal (SEBR)

Energy KPIs

In Vila Nova de Gaia, the renovation package shifted the energy consumption for space heating and DHW from gas to electricity with the installation of a heat pump system and some modifications to the existing DHW hydraulic circuit. However, as the building also hosts a kitchen preparing meals for the children, a certain gas consumption for the use in the kitchen remained also after the renovation. This consumption has been estimated through simulations starting from past gas bills and resulting in the range of 30% of the total gas consumption before renovation.

Also in this case, the reported KPIs are obtained from simulations. However, contrary to Nuremberg and Barcelona pilot sites, some problems have been encountered in the validation procedure for what regards the building's electric consumption. The discrepancies between different meter readings have been analysed both from remote and on-site, but some differences remained, and, for this reason, a proper calibration of the building's energy consumption was not possible. On the other hand, the PV system production foreseen by the model has been successfully validated against measured values.

Overall, the building's gas consumption passed from around 15000 m³/y (around 153 MWh/y⁷) to around 4600 m³/y (46 MWh/y⁷) due to the use in the kitchen. It is worth mentioning that, depending on the considered year, the gas consumption was quite variable and in the range 100 MWh/y - 150 MWh/y. The values reported above (153 MWh/y in total, 46 MWh/y for the kitchen) are slightly different from those reported in the RfT TD2 "Challenge Brief", but they are considered more reliable as they are always calculated based on simulations but starting from more recent gas bills. On the other hand, the electricity consumption increased from around 131 MWh/y to around 250 MWh/y. The increase in electric consumption is partly due to the electrification of the heating and DHW loads through the installation of the new heat pump system and partly because a substantial additional building part can now be conditioned during summer.

It is important to note that, through the electrification of the thermal building loads, it is now possible to cover the HVAC system consumption with locally produced renewable electricity directly produced by the PV system and consumed instantaneously or temporarily stored in the battery.

Regarding the Renewable Energy Production (RE_P) KPI, this pilot site presents two solar renewable energy systems: a solar thermal system, already present before the renovation and maintained also after the intervention, and a new PV and battery system.

The solar thermal system is composed of 20 panels, for a total net area in the range of 38 m² and produces around 25 MWh/y. This energy is totally self-consumed within the building and represents 69 % of the total building DHW demand and around 16 % of the total building heating demand (due to heating, DHW, and the use of the kitchen).

The PV system is instead new and its production is in the range of 172 MWh/y, indicating a specific production in the range of 1450 kWh/(kWp/y), in accordance with the forecast from the PVGIS tool⁸ for the considered system and location.

In terms of Renewable Energy Share (RE_Sh), the PV production and the presence of the battery ensure that around half (47 %) of the electricity consumed by the building is covered by renewable electricity locally produced. For what concerns the solar thermal system, as already written above,

its contribution covers around 69 % of the DHW demand and around 16 % of the thermal demand due to space heating, DHW, and the part due to kitchen use.

The Renewable Energy Production to Consumption Ratio (RE_PCR) for the electrical part results in the range of 68 %, indicating that, over the entire year, the PV production is around 2/3 of the building's electric consumption. The RE_PCR for the solar thermal system is instead equal to the RE_Sh as the entire solar thermal production is consumed within the building.

Finally, the Renewable Energy Utilization (RE_UT) for the PV and battery system is in the range of 69 %, indicating that around 2/3 of the PV production is used within the building instantaneously or after being stored in the battery. For what regards instead the solar thermal system, since the total solar thermal production is entirely used within the building, this indicator results equal to 100 %.

Table 20. Yearly energy KPIs for the Vila Nova de Gaia pilot site before and after intervention.

Building size	Energy KPIs, energy vector(s), and related units			Before/after intervention		
Floor area [m ²]	Energy KPI	Energy vector	Unit	Before	After	
4,075	Final Energy Consumption (E_F)	Gas	m ³ /y / (kWh/m ² /y)	153.109 (37.5)	46.144 ¹² (11.3)	
		Electricity	MWh/y / (kWh/m ² /y)	130.868 (32.1)	250.063 (61.3)	
	Renewable Energy Production (RE_P)	Electricity	MWh/y / (kWh/m ² /y)	0 (0)	172.603 (42.5)	
		Thermal	MWh/y / (kWh/m ² /y)	25.198 (4.5)	25.198 (4.5)	
	Renewable Energy Share (RE_Sh)	Electricity	%	0	47	
		Thermal	%	16 ¹³	16 ¹³	
	Renewable Energy Prod. to Cons. Ratio (RE_PCR)	Electricity	%	0	69	
		Thermal	%	16 ¹³	16 ¹³	
			Electricity	%	0	68

¹² After the renovation a certain gas consumption associated with the use in the kitchen remains. Based on analysis of past gas bills of the period before intervention, this contribution was in the range of 30% of the total gas consumption pre-intervention, resulting in a consumption in the range of 4600 m³/y that is considered also after renovation.

¹³ According to calculations, the solar thermal system present before intervention and maintained also after the renovation was producing around 25.198 MWh/y, equivalent to around 16% of the building overall thermal demand due to space heating, use in the kitchen and DHW. As the solar thermal system contributes only to cover part of the DHW demand also the related fraction has been accounted. The solar thermal system covers around 69% of the yearly DHW demand. As the entire production is used on-site, the RE_UT KPI results equal to 100 % and the RE_PCR results equal to RE_Sh

Renewable Utilisation (RE_UT)	Energy	Thermal	%	100 ¹³	100 ¹³
----------------------------------	--------	---------	---	-------------------	-------------------

Note: The values of final energy consumption (E_F) and on-site renewable energy production (RE_P) are reported both in MWh/y and, in brackets, in kWh/m²/y

The following paragraphs report a more detailed analysis of the Energy KPIs, analysing their hourly time series and the electric energy flows and the interactions among PV, battery, grid, and building’s load for three weeks considered representative of typical building’s operation in cold, mid, and hot seasons.

From Figure 50 it can be noted that the building’s electric consumption presents typical peaks in the early morning, when the HVAC system is switched on to re-establish the indoor comfort conditions in terms of indoor temperature. As soon as the various building zones start reaching the desired indoor temperature, the building’s space heating demand, and therefore the HVAC system’s electric consumption, start decreasing.

Due to the limited solar irradiation and the non-optimal PV panel slope for the considered period, the PV production is limited to around half the installed power (around 60 kW out of the 119 kWp installed) and the production is almost always instantaneously self-consumed, with the battery that is not used and the resulting RE_Sh (equal to RE_PCR) which is lower than 100 % for all weekdays of the considered week (all days except the 3rd and the 4th that are instead weekend days).

On the weekend days of the considered week, there is a PV surplus due to the limited building’s electric consumption, mainly because the school is unoccupied and the HVAC system is switched off. On these days, the PV production is first used to charge the battery as visible in Figure 50 (RE_UT equal to 100 % until around noon on the 3rd day of the analysed week) and in Figure 51 (light green area), and then the eventual further PV surplus is sent to the electric grid. The battery is discharged (dark green area in Figure 51) as soon as the building’s electric consumption is higher than the PV production, and this occurs on the morning of the first weekday (5th day in Figure 51).

Regarding the interaction with the electric grid, Figure 51 shows that the energy taken from the grid during weekdays shows a pattern quite repetitive with two peaks, the highest concentrated in the morning when the HVAC system starts, and the second concentrated on the evening, when the PV production decreases, as, in the considered weekdays, the battery capacity is never exploited (except on the morning of the 5th day of the considered week).

Figure 50. Vila Nova de Gaia Energy KPIs (1-7 February).

Note: The quantities reported are: building electric consumption (red), PV production (yellow), Renewable Energy Share (RE_Sh, green, right y-axis), Renewable Energy Production to Consumption Ratio (RE_PCR, blue, right y-axis) and Renewable Energy Utilisation (RE_UT, purple, right y-axis). Hourly values for the period 1-7 February

Figure 51. Vila Nova de Gaia electric energy flows and battery State of Charge (1-7 February).

Note: The quantities reported are: building electric consumption (red), PV production (yellow), energy to (light green) and from (dark green) battery, energy to (light blue) and from (dark blue) electric grid, battery SoC (dark green, line, right y-axis). Hourly values for the period 1-7 February

Figure 52 and Figure 53 show the same quantities already discussed above, but in this case for the week 15-22 March, which is considered representative of a mid-season week.

In this week, the building’s electrical consumption presents some peaks similar to those of the considered winter week (and in the range of 120 kW), but, as visible comparing Figure 52 and Figure 50 these peaks are shorter in time and less frequent in the considered mid-season week. On the contrary, the higher solar availability resulted in a higher PV production, always in comparison to the considered winter week, as visible by comparing again the two figures. In addition, for most of the time in the considered mid-season week, the PV and battery system can cover entirely the building’s electric consumption (RE_Sh equal to 100 % in Figure 52).

Figure 53 shows instead the electric energy flows and the interactions between PV, battery, grid, and the building’s electric consumption. As can be noted in this figure, on all weekdays of the

considered mid-season week (all except the 3rd and the 4th day), there are some hours in which the PV production is higher than the building’s electric consumption.

When this occurs, the PV surplus is first used to charge the battery, and the stored energy is used as soon as the building’s electric consumption is higher than the PV production. The battery charge generally occurs in the hours around noon and finishes in the afternoon. The energy stored is instead used in the late afternoon when PV production decreases.

Thanks to this energy patterns, with building’s consumption higher than PV production after hours with PV surplus, in the considered mid-season week the battery storage capacity is effectively exploited with an almost full charge-discharge battery cycle (with a variation in the battery State of Charge (SoC) of at least 70%) on four out of five weekdays.

Regarding the interaction with the electric grid, in general, on weekdays, the electricity taken from the grid is concentrated on the early morning hours as the PV production is still low or equal to zero, and the battery is empty as it was discharged on the evening of the previous day. During the evening, the battery can cover the totality or the majority of the building’s electric demand, with the grid contribution limited, in terms of both absolute value and duration.

Finally, on weekend days (3rd and 4th day of the considered mid-season week), basically, no or very limited building’s electric consumption is considered. This is not totally correct, as a minor building’s electric consumption is always present due to the standby consumption of the different devices installed. In any case, on these days, the PV production is notably higher than the building’s electric consumption, and this production is first used to charge the battery, and then, the further PV surplus is sent to the electric grid.

Figure 52. Vila Nova de Gaia Energy KPIs (15-22 March)

Note: The quantities reported are: building electric consumption (red), PV production (yellow), Renewable Energy Share (RE_Sh, green, right y-axis), Renewable Energy Production to Consumption Ratio (RE_PCR, blue, right y-axis) and Renewable Energy Utilisation (RE_UT, purple, right y-axis). Hourly values for the period 15-22 March

Figure 53. Vila Nova de Gaia electric energy flows and battery State of Charge (15-22 March).

Note: The quantities reported are: building electric consumption (red), PV production (yellow), energy to (light green) and from (dark green) battery, energy to (light blue) and from (dark blue) electric grid, battery SoC (dark green, line, right y-axis). Hourly values for the period 15-22 March

On a typical summer week, as visible in Figure 54, the peak electric consumption is in the same range as the peak PV production, but with the PV production that, for most of the time, is higher than the building’s electric consumption (RE_PCR higher than 100 %). Moreover, contrary to the heating period, the building’s electric consumption and the PV production are more in phase. As can be seen in Figure 54, the PV and battery system can almost completely cover the building’s electric consumption in the considered week (RE_Sh equal to 100%).

From Figure 55 it is possible to note that, during weekdays, the battery contributes to cover the building’s electric consumption especially in the early morning (using energy stored on the previous day), when PV production is still low or equal to zero. The PV production surplus is then used to charge the battery first and, generally in the afternoon, when the battery is already fully charged, it is sent to the grid. As the PV production is often higher than the building’s electric consumption, the battery is generally only partially discharged, except on the 5th day, which shows a complete discharge of the electric storage (see dark green line in Figure 55), and also a limited amount of energy taken from the grid.

Figure 54. Vila Nova de Gaia Energy KPIs (15-22 July)

Note: The quantities reported are: building electric consumption (red), PV production (yellow), Renewable Energy Share (RE_Sh, green, right y-axis), Renewable Energy Production to Consumption Ratio (RE_PCR, blue, right y-axis) and Renewable Energy Utilisation (RE_UT, purple, right y-axis). Hourly values for the period 15-22 July

Figure 55. Vila Nova de Gaia electric energy flows and battery State of Charge (15-22 July).

Note: The quantities reported are: building electric consumption (red), PV production (yellow), energy to (light green) and from (dark green) battery, energy to (light blue) and from (dark blue) electric grid, battery SoC (dark green, line, right y-axis). Hourly values for the period 15-22 July

Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ) KPIs

The pilot site in Vilanova de Gaia presents spaces with different usages. In fact, in addition to the classrooms, the building hosts also zones as auditorium, canteen, activity room, library, archive office, which present specific usage.

For an overall assessment of the IEQ through indoor temperature and level of CO₂ in ppm, the analysis focuses only on some spaces selected as the most important in the building, and representative also of spaces that can be generally found in a typical school. For this reason, in the following, the analysis focuses on three classrooms with different orientations, the auditorium, and the library. The Table 21 reports, for the different zones considered, the number of hours with indoor temperature in the different ranges and the total occupancy hours. The renovation package dedicated to this building includes a more detailed analysis of these and also other spaces present in the building, analysing ten zones in total.

Although the procuRE comfort range is defined between 21 °C and 25 °C, also indoor temperatures in the range of 18 °C – 21 °C can be considered acceptable, especially if limited to defined and short periods.

In general, all the analysed zones show a non-negligible number of hours with temperature lower than 18 °C with underheating problems, while overheating is less problematic. The underheating hours are mainly concentrated in the first occupancy hours in the morning, with the North-oriented classroom that shows, as expected, more underheating hours in comparison to the other analysed classrooms.

The comfort in terms of indoor temperature in the auditorium, although it seems not too problematic, should be taken carefully due to the high volume of this zone and its typical intermittent usage.

Table 21. Number of hours over the year with indoor temperature in defined ranges.

Indoor temperature range	Considered zone				
	Classroom S-W oriented	Classroom N-W oriented	Classroom S-E oriented	Library	Auditorium
Below 18 °C	93	169	91	221	8
Below 21 °C	296	398	290	380	164
procuRE comfort range (21-25 °C)	542	730	603	1,668	563
Above 25 °C	46	71	48	224	5
Above 28 °C	5	4	5	28	0
Total	1,072	1,072	1,072	2,272	732

Note: In Vila Nova de Gaia, the analysis reported focused on five different zones: three classrooms with different orientations, the library and the auditorium

For what regards the CO₂ assessment, in all ten analysed zones, the simulations show that, with the natural and mechanical ventilation strategy adopted, the CO₂ levels remain always below the limit of 1000 ppm. The values are, in general, in the range of 600 – 900 ppm, with the highest values concentrated in the classrooms in the summer period.

Environmental KPIs

The implemented renovation package resulted in a shift of the consumption for covering space heating and, partly DHW building needs from gas to electricity that can be partly covered using locally produced renewable electricity.

Accounting for the different emission factors of the different energy vectors, the yearly CO₂ emissions decreased from 54.6 tCO₂/y (pre-intervention) to 33.2 tCO₂/y (post-intervention) with a reduction in the range of 39 % as summarized in Table 22.

The reduction obtained is important but at the same time, it is limited by mainly three aspects, shortly described in the following.

First, due to the use in the kitchen, a non-negligible part of the gas consumption remained also after renovation (around 30 % of the pre-intervention total gas consumption).

Second, the situation after renovation allows for conditioning in summer a higher part of the building. This results in a higher building’s electric consumption that, although more temporarily aligned to the PV production in comparison to the space heating demand, cannot always be covered entirely using electricity from PV or battery, resulting in additional energy taken from the grid.

Third, the optimized control logic applied in the simulations aims to focus not only on energy savings but also on users’ comfort improvements, as users’ dissatisfaction in terms of comfort was highlighted, especially in some building zones in the past.

Last, as in the calculation of the other pilot sites, this calculation does not consider the beneficial effects in terms of CO₂ emission reduction due to the PV surplus exported to the grid.

Table 22. Yearly CO₂ emissions of pre and post-intervention situation and related savings. Vila Nova de Gaia pilot site

Status	Energy vector	Final Energy consumption	CO ₂ factor	CO ₂ emission	CO ₂ emission savings	
		[MWh/y]	[tCO ₂ /MWh]	[tCO ₂ /y]	[tCO ₂ /y]	[%]
Before	Gas	153.109	0.202	30.9	-	-
	Grid el.	130.868	0.181	23.7	-	-
	Total	-	-	54.6	-	-
After	Gas	46.144	0.202	9.3	-	-
	Grid el.	132.083	0.181	23.9	-	-
	Total	-	-	33.2	21.4	39 %

Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI)

The pre-intervention overall SRI score was one of the lowest among the six pilot sites and in the range of 20%. The main factors responsible for this low value are associated with the operation control of the existing heat generator, where both gas boiler and Air Handling Units (AHUs) were controlled with a fixed supply water temperature. Moreover, no PV and battery were installed and the existing BMS was only partially working, with many sensors not integrated. The only on-site renewable energy system was a solar thermal system used to contribute to the covering of the building’s DHW demand. The renovation, focused mainly on the installation of a new heat pump system for both heating, cooling, and DHW, of a PV and a battery system, and of a new BMS, allowed to improve the overall SRI to around 60 %. Table 23 summarises the pre and post-intervention overall SRI score and the related class.

As can be noted in Figure 57, the improvements affect all impact criteria, with the installation of a proper operating BMS system mainly responsible for these improvements. In addition, the installation of the new heat pump, PV, and battery systems is partly responsible for the improvements in the Energy efficiency and Energy flexibility and storage impact criteria.

Looking instead at technical domains level, as shown in Figure 57, the improvements are solely (monitoring and control) or partly (the other improved technical domains) due to the new BMS. The new heat pump system is partly responsible for the improvements in heating, cooling, DHW and ventilation technical domains, while the PV and battery system contribute to improve the electricity technical domain.

Table 23. SRI overall score and related class before and after renovation, Vila Nova de Gaia pilot site

Characteristic	Before intervention	After intervention
SRI overall score	19.5 %	60.5 %
SRI class	Lower than 20 %	Between 50% and 65%

Figure 56. SRI for the different impact criteria. Vila Nova de Gaia pilot site

Figure 57. SRI for the different technical domains. Vila Nova de Gaia pilot site

4.1.4 Velenje, Slovenia (PARadISE)

Energy KPIs

Table 24 reports the Energy KPIs for the Velenje pilot site before and after the renovation.

Before the renovation, the space heating and part of the DHW demand were covered by the oil boiler, resulting in an oil consumption in the range of 9244 l/y, which, considering the Lower Heating Value (LHV) of 10.06 kWh/l as used in the RfT TD2 “Challenge Brief”, resulted in an oil consumption of 93 MWh/y. In the same pre-renovation situation, the same document (RfT TD2 “Challenge Brief”), reported an electric consumption in the range of 46.6 MWh/y.

The installation of a heat pump system and a centralized mechanical system with heat recovery resulted in the shift from oil to electricity as the energy vector used to cover the space heating and part of the DHW building’s thermal loads. The oil boiler is maintained as a back-up and is planned to be used in eventual specific moments, for example, in case of particularly cold winter days or in case one or more heat pumps are temporarily not working. Consequently, the oil final energy consumption is reduced to zero, while the electrical consumption is almost doubled to around 91.6 MWh/y due to the heat pump and mechanical ventilation system consumption.

However, the installation of a PV (with a peak power of 77 kWp) and battery system allows for covering part of the electric consumption with locally produced renewable electricity. The validated simulations show a PV system production in the range of 89 MWh/y, aligned to forecasts from the PVGIS tool⁸ (1155 kWh/(kWp·y)).

Although the period with the highest building’s electric consumption is the winter period, concurrent with the minimum PV production, thanks also to the presence of the battery, the PV electricity ensures, on a yearly basis, to cover around half of the yearly building’s electric consumption (RE_Sh equal to 51 %). This implies that the electricity taken from the grid after renovation is in the range of 44.8 MWh/y, lower than the pre-intervention value (equal to 46.6 MWh/y).

The Renewable Energy Production to Consumption Ratio (RE_PCR) is instead equal to 97 % indicating that the PV system installed produces, on a yearly basis an amount of energy similar to the one consumed by the building in the same period (RE_PCR equal to 97 %).

Finally, the Renewable Energy Utilisation (RE_UT), which is equal to 53 %, indicates that around half of the PV production is consumed instantaneously within the building or after being stored in the battery. A bigger battery could improve, in principle, the RE_Sh and RE_UT KPIs, but the temporal mismatch between maximum building’s electric consumption (occurring in winter) and maximum PV production (occurring in summer) limits the improvements associated with the additional storage capacity, making the choice of a bigger battery less economically viable.

Table 24. Yearly energy KPIs for the Velenje pilot site before and after intervention.

Building size		Energy KPIs, energy vector(s), and related units			Before/after intervention	
Floor area [m ²]	Energy KPI	Energy vector	Unit	Before	After	
1,947	Final Energy Consumption (E_F)	Oil	MWh/y / (kWh/m ² /y)	93.000 (47.8)	0 (0)	
		Electricity	MWh/y / (kWh/m ² /y)	46.605 (23.9)	91.600 (47.0)	
	Renewable Energy Production (RE_P)	Electricity	MWh/y / (kWh/m ² /y)	0 (0)	89.000 (45.7)	
	Renewable Energy Share (RE_Sh)	Electricity	%	0	51	
	Renewable Energy Prod. to Cons. Ratio (RE_PCR)	Electricity	%	0	97	
	Renewable Energy Utilisation (RE_UT)	Electricity	%	0	53	

Note: The values of final energy consumption (E_F) and on-site renewable energy production (RE_P) are reported both in MWh/y and, in brackets, in kWh/m²/y

As for the other pilot sites, the following paragraphs report an hourly analysis of the Energy KPIs and the electrical energy flows for three weeks considered representative of the typical building’s operation in winter, mid-season, and summer, respectively. This detailed analysis aims to give a detailed assessment of the interactions among PV, battery, and electric grid to cover the building’s electric consumption and the related effects on the calculated Energy KPIs.

Figure 58 shows the Energy KPIs for the considered winter week (1-7 February). As can be noted in this figure, the building’s electric consumption (red area) presents relatively high variations within the same day, with the peaks associated with the ON-OFF operation of the three air-water heat pumps installed.

The PV production (yellow area) is relatively low in comparison to the installed power (the maximum PV power in the considered winter week is in the range of 30 kW, while the installed power is 77 kWp) due to the low solar availability in the winter period. Most of the PV production is used to cover part of the building’s electric consumption, resulting in its instantaneous self-consumption (RE_Sh lower than 100 %).

Nevertheless, on all days of the considered winter week, there are at least some hours in which the PV production exceeds the building’s electric consumption. In this case, the PV surplus is used first to charge the battery (RE_PCR higher than 100 % and RE_UT equal to 100 %, while if the battery is already fully charged, the PV surplus is sent to the electric grid (RE_PCR higher than 100 % and RE_UT lower than 100 %). The only case in which there is a PV surplus high enough to be injected

into the grid is on the 2nd day of the considered winter week. Being this day a Sunday, the school is closed, and its consumption is reduced as the indoor temperature set point is decreased and the electric consumption due to the other electrical devices used in the building is limited in comparison to a normal weekday.

Figure 59 shows the electrical energy flows, highlighting the electrical energy sent and taken from the battery and from the grid to cover the building’s electric consumption.

As can be noted in this figure, most of the electric consumption is covered using electricity taken from the grid (dark blue area). A minor part of the PV production is used to charge the battery (light green area), and this generally occurs in the central hours of the day, when PV production is at its maximum. The energy stored in the battery is totally consumed in a few hours in the afternoon, relying entirely on the electric grid for the rest of the hours until the next day when PV starts producing again.

Figure 58. Velenje Energy KPIs (1-7 February)

Note: The quantities reported are: building electric consumption (red), PV production (yellow), Renewable Energy Share (RE_Sh, green, right y-axis), Renewable Energy Production to Consumption Ratio (RE_PCR, blue, right y-axis) and Renewable Energy Utilisation (RE_UT, purple, right y-axis). Hourly values for the period 1-7 February

Figure 59. Velenje electric energy flows and battery State of Charge (1-7 February)

Note: The quantities reported are: building electric consumption (red), PV production (yellow), energy to (light green) and from (dark green) battery, energy to (light blue) and from (dark blue) electric grid, battery SoC (dark green, line, right y-axis). Hourly values for the period 1-7 February

Figure 60 and Figure 61 show the same quantities presented in Figure 58 and Figure 59, respectively and described in the previous paragraphs, but, in this case, for the considered mid-season week (15-22 March).

As can be noted by comparing Figure 60 and Figure 58, also in the considered mid-season week, the building's electric consumption pattern is quite discontinuous, with peaks and valleys associated with the ON-OFF operations of the three air-water heat pumps installed. However, comparing the two figures, in comparison to the considered winter week, the peaks in the mid-season week are lower and up to around 30 kW. On the other hand, the PV production in the considered mid-season week is higher in comparison to the considered winter week due to the higher solar irradiation.

The result of these two effects is that the PV production can cover a higher portion of the building's electric consumption, both with electricity produced and instantaneously consumed, and with electricity produced, temporarily stored in the battery, and used as soon as the PV production is no longer able to entirely cover the building's electric load.

In terms of KPIs, the two effects mentioned above resulted in the increase of the RE_Sh and RE_PCR in the mid-season week in comparison to the winter week considered. On the other hand, it is more frequent to have hours in which there is PV surplus, and the battery is already fully charged. In this case, the PV surplus is sent to the grid, and this implies a reduction of the RE_UT KPI.

The same conclusions can also be drawn by looking at Figure 61, which shows the electrical energy flows and the interactions between PV, battery, and grid to cover the building's electric load.

In the considered mid-season week, the PV surplus can completely charge the battery (battery SoC passing from 0 % to 80 - 100 %) on most days (five days out of seven, including a Sunday (2nd day of the considered mid-season week)). In the other two days (4th and 6th day of the considered mid-season week), the battery is charged only partially. This is due to the particularly low PV production in these days, which are characterized by cloudy conditions and limited solar irradiation.

Regarding the interactions with the electric grid, electricity is taken from the grid especially in the night and early morning hours, as the battery capacity is not enough to cover the building's electric consumption until the PV re-starts producing on the next day.

Figure 60. Velenje Energy KPIs (15-22 March)

Note: The quantities reported are: building electric consumption (red), PV production (yellow), Renewable Energy Share (RE_Sh, green, right y-axis), Renewable Energy Production to Consumption Ratio (RE_PCR, blue, right y-axis) and Renewable Energy Utilisation (RE_UT, purple, right y-axis). Hourly values for the period 15-22 March

Figure 61. Velenje electric energy flows and battery State of Charge (15-22 March).

Note: The quantities reported are: building electric consumption (red), PV production (yellow), energy to (light green) and from (dark green) battery, energy to (light blue) and from (dark blue) electric grid, battery SoC (dark green, line, right y-axis). Hourly values for the period 15-22 March

Finally, Figure 62 show the same quantities already described above and presented in previous figures, but for the considered summer week.

As the school is not used in this period of the year, its consumption is limited in comparison to the previously analysed periods. On the other hand, the PV production is at its maximum, due to the high solar radiation available.

This results in the PV production covering almost the entire building’s consumption (RE_Sh equal to 100 %), with exceptions in case of cloudy days (as the 1st day in Figure). Moreover, the fact that PV production is higher than the building’s electric consumption results in RE_PCR higher than 100 % for most of the time. On the other hand, the high PV production and the limited storage capacity result in the injection of most of the PV production into the electric grid. This means that a minor

fraction of the PV production is used within the building (both instantaneously used or stored), leading to RE_UT values often lower than 100 %.

Similarly to Figure 61, Figure 63 shows the electrical energy flows and interactions between PV, battery, electric grid, and the building’s electric consumption for the considered summer week. As can be noted in the figure, the battery is generally charged in the morning hours, and its energy is more than enough to completely cover the building’s electric consumption in the hours without PV production. The statement saying that the battery capacity is more than enough to completely cover the building’s electric consumption is because the battery's SoC (green line in Figure) decreases by only around 50 % during the discharging period on most days.

Regarding the interactions with the electrical grid, energy is taken from grid only in days with limited PV production due to cloudy weather conditions (1st day of the considered summer week), while, for the rest of the week, energy is injected into the grid as soon as the battery is fully charged and there is still PV surplus.

Figure 62. Velenje Energy KPIs (15-22 July)

Note: The quantities reported are: building electric consumption (red), PV production (yellow), Renewable Energy Share (RE_Sh, green, right y-axis), Renewable Energy Production to Consumption Ratio (RE_PCR, blue, right y-axis) and Renewable Energy Utilisation (RE_UT, purple, right y-axis). Hourly values for the period 15-22 July

Figure 63. Velenje electric energy flows and battery State of Charge (15-22 July).

Note: The quantities reported are: building electric consumption (red), PV production (yellow), energy to (light green) and from (dark green) battery, energy to (light blue) and from (dark blue) electric grid, battery SoC (dark green, line, right y-axis). Hourly values for the period 15-22 July

Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ) KPIs

To assess the indoor temperature KPI in the Velenje pilot site, the number of hours in which the indoor temperature is outside the procuRE-defined comfort range (21 °C – 25 °C) is considered.

For a more detailed analysis, the hours in which the indoor temperature is outside the procuRE range are also analysed more in detail, assessing the number of hours presenting an indoor temperature only slightly higher or lower the procuRE defined boundaries (18 °C – 21 °C and 25 °C – 28 °C), and the number of hours with temperature below 18 °C and above 28 °C which represents a non-negligible users’ discomfort situation.

Considering that the building is a school not used during the summer season, and considering the climatic conditions of the location, the focus is on the analysis of discomfort hours for indoor temperatures lower than 21 °C. However, as the HVAC system conditioning the school also provides heating to one apartment in building B, space heating is always considered available, without hours in which the HVAC system is, by default, considered switched OFF.

Although the model used for the simulations considered 51 different zones, the analysis reported here focused on two classrooms, with the results reported in terms of the number of hours per year with an indoor temperature in the different ranges in Table 25. These zones are those with the highest value of discomfort hours in terms of underheating during the year from the dynamic simulations performed. All the other zones present a limited number of underheating discomfort hours during the year, always lower than 10 h/y.

The two analysed classrooms are one North-East and one South-East oriented, and both are placed on corners of building A. The fact that these zones are placed on building’s corners resulted in a higher external wall area and, consequently, in higher thermal losses and a higher number of discomfort hours due to underheating. It is also possible to note in Table 25 the lower number of discomfort hours of the South-East oriented classroom (15 h/y) in comparison to the North-East oriented one (34 h/y).

Table 25 reports also a relatively high number of hours in which the indoor temperature in the two analysed classrooms is above 25 °C. Although these numbers suggest an uncomfortable situation, they are limited to the summer period, a period in which the school is closed. Therefore, they can be considered not a real problem.

Table 25. Number of hours over the year with indoor temperature in defined ranges.

Indoor temperature range	Considered zone	
	Classroom N-E	Classroom S-E
Below 18 °C	0	0
Below 21 °C	34	15
procuRE comfort range (21-25 °C)	7,934	8,448
Above 25 °C	791	297
Above 28 °C	1	0
Total	8,760	8,760

Note: In Velenje, the analysis is performed in four different zones: two classrooms located on the North-East and South-East corners of building A

For what regards the CO₂ level inside the considered classrooms, the simulations indicate that during the occupancy hours, the CO₂ levels in the two classrooms considered above tend to increase and can reach up to around 1200 – 1300 ppm. The hours of the year in which the limit is surpassed is in the range of 3200 - 3300 h/y (considering as the base for the calculation all the 8760 hours of the year). This trend is seen not only in the two classrooms analysed but is common in general to all classrooms. As these CO₂ level indicates slightly uncomfortable conditions in terms of air quality for the occupants, the real ventilation strategy implemented in the building will be re-checked on-site and eventually revised, if the monitored CO₂ levels in the classrooms result higher than the limit considered (equal to 1000 ppm).

Environmental KPIs

The implemented renovation package resulted in a shift of the consumption for covering space heating and part of the DHW building needs from oil to electricity, which can be partly covered using locally produced renewable electricity.

Accounting for the different emission factors of the different energy vectors, the yearly CO₂ emissions passed from 34.5 tCO₂/y (pre-intervention) to 9.2 tCO₂/y (post-intervention) with a reduction in the range of 73 % as summarized in Table 26. This calculation does not consider the beneficial effects in terms of CO₂ emission reduction due to the PV surplus exported to the grid.

Table 26. Yearly CO₂ emissions of pre and post-intervention situation and related savings. Velenje pilot site

Status	Energy vector	Final Energy consumption	CO ₂ factor	CO ₂ emission	CO ₂ emission savings	
		[MWh/y]	[tCO ₂ /MWh]	[tCO ₂ /y]	[tCO ₂ /y]	[%]
Before	Oil	93.001	0.268 ⁹	24.9	-	-
	Grid el.	46.605	0.205 ¹⁰	9.6	-	-
	Total	-	-	34.5	-	-
After	Oil	0	0.268 ⁹	0.0	-	-
	Grid el.	44.884	0.205 ¹⁰	9.2	-	-
	Total	-	-	9.2	25.3	73 %

Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI)

The overall SRI score in the Velenje pilot passed from 14.9 % (pre-renovation) to 64.8 % (post-renovation) as reported in Table 27. This pilot site presented one of the lowest overall SRI scores for the pre-intervention status, mainly due to the absence of a monitoring and control system and the absence of any on-site renewable energy production and storage system. The applied renovation involved different systems, from the heat generator to PV and battery installation.

The installation of a new heat pump system and a new mechanical ventilation system, together with the possibility to monitor and control them through the BMS are responsible for the improvements in the energy efficiency impact criteria, while the energy flexibility and storage criteria benefits from the installation of the new PV and battery system and the possibility to control them through the BMS. The other impact criteria improvements are mainly or solely due to the implementation of the BMS. The main improvements can be seen for the health, well-being and accessibility criteria thanks to the monitoring of IEQ variables and the possibility to use them for controlling the HVAC system, for the maintenance and fault prediction, thanks to the possibility for the BMS to benchmark system performance with historical or simulated data, and for the information to the occupants criteria, thanks to the use of a specific monitor, connected to the BMS, to make the occupants aware about the main systems' performance. The various SRI scores for the different impact criteria are reported for pre and post-intervention status in Figure 64.

At the technical domain level, as shown in Figure 65, the improvements in the SRI scores are associated partly with the new heat pump system and mechanical ventilation system (heating, DHW, ventilation domains), and with the new PV and battery systems (electricity domain). The remaining part of the improvements can be ascribed instead to the implemented BMS.

Table 27. SRI overall score and related class before and after renovation, Velenje pilot site

Characteristic	Before intervention	After intervention
SRI overall score	14.9 %	64.8 %
SRI class	Lower than 20 %	Between 50 % and 65 %

Figure 64. SRI for the different impact criteria. Velenje pilot site

Figure 65. SRI for the different technical domains. Velenje pilot site

4.1.5 Istanbul, Turkey (PARadISE)

Energy KPIs

In this pilot site, the RE_Sh KPI is almost identical to the RE_PCR, indicating that there are very limited periods in which PV production is sent to the grid, and, instead, almost the entire PV production is instantaneously consumed within the building. This conclusion can also be reached by looking at the RE_UT KPI (RE_UT equal to 96 %). In fact, RE_UT indicates how much of the energy produced is used within the building instantaneously or after being temporarily stored in an eventual battery. The fact that almost the entire PV production is instantaneously self-consumed motivates the choice of not considering an electric battery in the renovation package, as the advantages related to the battery use would be very limited.

Table 28 reports the Energy KPIs for the Istanbul pilot site in the pre- and post-renovation situations.

As already described, the building presents an electric consumption quite high, as it is a bakery school with industrial ovens and fridges used regularly. This electric consumption remains high also after the renovation, as only the lighting system renovation leads to net electrical energy savings. The replacement/addition of some VRF units (13 VRF indoor units in total), although with improved efficiency, resulted in higher electric consumption as the focus was not only on reducing the HVAC system consumption but also on improving comfort in some parts of the building that experienced discomfort conditions in terms of underheating and overheating throughout the year based on the procurer's feedback.

In addition to the electrical consumption that constitutes the main building's consumption, there was a gas consumption due to the DHW production in the pre-renovation situation. The gas boiler has been maintained and, therefore, the related consumption is considered also in the post-renovation situation.

Based on the previous statements, in terms of Final Energy consumption, the building presents the same gas consumption (3161 m³/y or around 30.4 MWh_{th}/y⁷) before and after the renovation. The electrical consumption is also aligned in the pre (582.9 MWh_{el}/y) and post-renovation (589.0 MWh_{el}/y) situation due to the improved energy efficiency of the lighting system and part of the HVAC system, which is counterbalanced by the additional consumption of the HVAC system to improve comfort conditions in spaces where users' discomfort conditions were recorded in the past.

The main improvement in terms of Energy KPIs is associated with the installation of a PV system on almost the entire roof's available area. The PV system production is in the range of 180.0 MWh/y, in accordance with forecasts from the PVGIS tool⁸, estimating, for the considered system, a specific production in the range of 1200 - 1300kWh/(kWp·y).

Although the PV system covers almost all the available roof area, it can cover only part of the building's electric consumption as this is particularly high for the specific building's usage as already described. For these reasons, on a yearly basis, only 29 % of the building's electric consumption is covered by the PV production (RE_Sh equal to 29 %).

In this pilot site, the RE_Sh KPI is almost identical to the RE_PCR, indicating that there are very limited periods in which PV production is sent to the grid, and, instead, almost the entire PV production is instantaneously consumed within the building. This conclusion can also be reached by looking at the RE_UT KPI (RE_UT equal to 96 %). In fact, RE_UT indicates how much of the energy produced is used within the building instantaneously or after being temporarily stored in an

eventual battery. The fact that almost the entire PV production is instantaneously self-consumed motivates the choice of not considering an electric battery in the renovation package, as the advantages related to the battery use would be very limited.

Table 28. Yearly energy KPIs for the Istanbul pilot site before and after intervention.

Building size	Energy KPIs, energy vector(s), and related units			Before/after intervention	
Floor area [m ²]	Energy KPI	Energy vector	Unit	Before	After
3900	Final Energy Consumption (E_F)	Gas	MWh/y / (kWh/m ² /y)	30.420 (7.8)	30.420 (7.8)
		Electricity	MWh/y / (kWh/m ² /y)	582.912 (149.5)	589.000 (151.0)
	Renewable Energy Production (RE_P)	Electricity	MWh/y / (kWh/m ² /y)	0 (0)	180.000 (46.2)
	Renewable Energy Share (RE_Sh)	Electricity	%	0	29 %
	Renewable Energy Prod. to Cons. Ratio (RE_PCR)	Electricity	%	0	31 %
	Renewable Energy Utilisation (RE_UT)	Electricity	%	0	96 %

Note: The values of final energy consumption (E_F) and on-site renewable energy production (RE_P) are reported both in MWh/y and, in brackets, in kWh/m²/y

The following paragraphs present a detailed analysis of the hourly patterns of the Energy KPIs in three non-consecutive weeks, each chosen to represent building operation during one winter week, one mid-season week, and one summer week.

Figure 66 refers to the period 1-7 February, which is considered representative of the building’s operation in a typical winter week.

As can be noted in this figure, the building’s electric consumption is particularly high and always higher than the PV production, with peaks up to 400 kW concentrated generally in the morning when the indoor temperature set point is increased to re-establish the users’ comfort temperature after the night period in which it is reduced, and the building started to be normally used. Due to the limited solar irradiation available in this period, the production of the PV system is limited to around 70 kW, around half of the peak power installed (150 kWp). Consequently, the PV production is entirely instantaneously self-consumed (RE_UT always equal to 100 %), with the hourly value varying a lot from almost 0 % to 80 % depending on the simultaneous building’s electric consumption and PV production. As there is no battery and the PV production is entirely and instantaneously self-consumed, the RE_Sh is equal to the RE_PCR.

Figure 66. Istanbul Energy KPIs (1-7 February)

Note: The quantities reported are: building electric consumption (red), PV production (yellow), Renewable Energy Share (RE_Sh, green, right y-axis), Renewable Energy Production to Consumption Ratio (RE_PCR, blue, right y-axis) and Renewable Energy Utilisation (RE_UT, purple, right y-axis). Hourly values for the period 1-7 February

Similarly to Figure 66, Figure 67 shows the Energy KPIs for the considered mid-season week (15-22 March).

In comparison to the considered winter week, the considered mid-season week shows a slightly lower building’s electric consumption, with peaks up to 350 kW still concentrated in the morning hours for the same reasons explained above.

On the other hand, in comparison to the considered winter week, the slightly higher solar availability in the considered mid-season week resulted in a similar PV production in terms of peak power (60 kW – 70 kW) but a slightly higher number of hours in which this production is available. This is the reason for the more evident peaks in RE_Sh and RE_PCR peaks in the morning hours, when the PV starts producing and the building is not occupied and used yet. As for the considered winter week, also in the considered mid-season week, the PV production is entirely and instantaneously self-consumed (RE_Sh and RE_PCR always lower than 100 % and RE_UT always equal to 100 % when there is PV production).

Figure 67. Istanbul Energy KPIs (15-22 March)

Note: The quantities reported are: building electric consumption (red), PV production (yellow), Renewable Energy Share (RE_Sh, green, right y-axis), Renewable Energy Production to Consumption Ratio (RE_PCR, blue, right y-axis) and Renewable Energy Utilisation (RE_UT, purple, right y-axis). Hourly values for the period 15-22 March

Finally, Figure 68 presents the same Energy KPIs for the considered summer week (15-22 July).

In the considered summer week, the building’s consumption is the lowest among the three weeks considered, with peaks up to around 300 kW, while the PV production is the highest due to the higher solar availability, and up to around 120 kW.

In the same week, there are a few hours, especially in the early morning and in the late afternoon, when the PV production is slightly higher than the building’s base load electric consumption. In these few hours, the PV surplus is injected into the grid because no battery is installed at this pilot site for the already explained reasons. These few hours are characterized by RE_Sh equal to 100 % (building’s electric load completely covered by the PV production), RE_PCR higher than 100 % (PV production is higher than the building’s electric consumption) and RE_UT lower than 100 % (part of the PV production is not used within the building and is exported to the electric grid).

Figure 68. Istanbul Energy KPIs (15-22 July)

Note: The quantities reported are: building electric consumption (red), PV production (yellow), Renewable Energy Share (RE_Sh, green, right y-axis), Renewable Energy Production to Consumption Ratio (RE_PCR, blue, right y-axis) and Renewable Energy Utilisation (RE_UT, purple, right y-axis). Hourly values for the period 15-22 July

Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ) KPIs

Similarly to the other pilot sites, the indoor environmental quality is assessed in the Istanbul pilot site based on the number of hours in which the indoor temperature is outside the procuRE defined comfort range (21 °C – 25 °C) and the number of hours in which the CO₂ level is higher than 1000 ppm.

Regarding the indoor temperature criteria, the Table 29 reports not only the number of hours per year in which the indoor temperature is within the procuRE comfort range but also the number of hours per year in which the indoor temperature is in other ranges. The aim is to identify in this way conditions that are slightly higher (25 °C – 28 °C) or lower (18 °C - 21 °C) in terms of indoor temperature in comparison to the defined comfort range, which can be considered not problematic if limited to specific periods, and conditions characterized by indoor temperatures lower than 18 °C and higher than 28 °C that, instead, should be accounted as discomfort conditions.

The analysis is focused on zones that are considered representative of the considered buildings and also of other buildings with the same usage (schools). For this reason, the analysed zones are two classrooms and one office. Nevertheless, it has been verified that all the simulated zones behave similarly. Moreover, the evaluation is made only in the occupancy hours, excluding the hours in which the building is not used and the indoor temperature set point is modified (e.g., decreased during the night period in the winter season).

Based on the simulation results, the building’s after renovation does not show underheating problems, with only a minor number of hours (13 h/y) of discomfort in the office.

Regarding overheating, instead, all three considered zones show a non-negligible number of hours with temperatures above 25 °C. However, it has been verified that not only these hours present temperature in the range 25 – 28 °C, but the range is always closer and between 25 °C and 26 °C. This means that the discomfort condition due to overheating is very limited based on the performed simulations.

Table 29. Number of hours over the year with indoor temperature in defined ranges.

Indoor temperature range	Considered zones		
	Classroom 1	Classroom 2	Office
Below 18 °C	0	0	0
Below 21 °C	0	0	13
procuRE comfort range (21-25 °C)	1,744	1,804	1,722
Above 25 °C	866	806	875
Above 28 °C	0	0	0
Total	2,610	2,610	2,610

Note: In Istanbul, the analysis is performed in three different zones: two classrooms and one office

The analysis of the CO₂ level inside the considered classrooms indicated that, with the natural and mechanical ventilation strategies adopted, the comfort conditions, in terms of indoor air quality, are always ensured. This is because the values obtained from simulations are always in the range of 400 - 700 ppm (well below the considered limit equal to 1000 ppm). It has also been verified that this range is valid not only for the analysed zones but in general for all the zones considered in the simulations.

Environmental KPIs

In terms of CO₂ emissions reduction during operation, the most relevant intervention in the Istanbul pilot site was the installation of a PV system on the roof. The renovation/addition of some VRF units resulted in higher comfort inside the building, but also in slightly higher electric consumption in comparison to the pre-intervention status.

Due to the peculiarity of the considered building, which is a school but with a specific usage and a particularly high electric consumption due to industrial ovens and fridges used, the building's electric consumption and, therefore, the related CO₂ emissions were particularly high in the pre-renovation situation. The PV system installed can only partially cover the building's electric consumption, as already discussed in the previous section, where the Energy KPIs are presented.

Accounting for the different emission factors of the different energy vectors, with the grid electricity CO₂ emission factor which is higher in comparison to the majority of the analysed countries where the pilot sites are located, the yearly CO₂ emissions passed from 289.4 tCO₂/y (pre-intervention) to 208.5 tCO₂/y (post-intervention) with a reduction in the range of 28 % as summarised in Table 14. This calculation does not consider the beneficial effects in terms of CO₂ emission reduction due to the PV surplus exported to the grid. This contribution, for the Istanbul pilot site, is in any case limited as the PV production is almost completely (95.8 %) consumed instantaneously within the building.

Although the percentage reduction in CO₂ emissions seems limited, due also to the relatively high emission factor of the Turkey electric grid, the reduction in absolute terms is in the range of 80 tCO₂/y. For a comparison, this value is in the range of one and a half time the yearly CO₂ emission of the Vila Nova de Gaia pilot site in the pre-intervention situation.

Table 30. Yearly CO₂ emissions of pre and post-intervention situation and related savings. Istanbul pilot site

Status	Energy vector	Final Energy consumption	CO ₂ factor	CO ₂ emission	CO ₂ emission savings	
		[MWh/y]	[tCO ₂ /MWh]	[tCO ₂ /y]	[tCO ₂ /y]	[%]
Before	Gas	30.4	0.202 ¹⁴	6.1	-	-
	Grid el.	582.9	0.486 ¹⁰	283.3	-	-
	Total	-	-	289.4	-	-
After	Gas	30.4	0.202 ⁹	6.1	-	-
	Grid el.	416.4	0.486 ¹⁰	202.4	-	-
	Total	-	-	208.5	80.9	28 %

Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI)

In the case of the Istanbul pilot site, the SRI calculated before intervention was in the range of 30%. This value is the highest pre-renovation value among the six pilots. This is mainly due to the fact that at least some variable speed VRF units and a mechanical ventilation system allowing for night cooling were already used before the renovation. The renovation, focused on the addition of VRF units, the installation of a new PV system, the renovation of the lighting system, and the

¹⁴ Standard value from IPCC, 2006 from Annex I available at:

<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/278ae66b-809b-11e7-b5c6-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

implementation of a BMS system, allows to improve the overall SRI score to almost 70%. Both pre- and post-renovation overall SRI and the related class are reported in Table 31.

As can be seen in Figure 70, the biggest improvements are associated with aspects related to the implementation of the BMS (maintenance, information to occupants), while also the improvements in the heating/cooling and lighting system and the installation of a new PV system are responsible of the improvements in energy efficiency, flexibility comfort and convenience.

Regarding instead the analysis at the technical domain level, the improvements in SRI on all technical domains visible in Figure 69 are partly due to the use of a new unique BMS, able to monitor and control the different systems. The rest of the improvements are due to the improved heating/and cooling system, lighting system, the new PV system and to their control/operation options.

Table 31. SRI overall score and related class before and after renovation, Istanbul pilot site

Characteristic	Before intervention	After intervention
SRI overall score	29.8 %	69.9 %
SRI class	Between 20% and 35%	Between 65% and 80%

Figure 69. SRI for the different impact criteria. Istanbul pilot site

Figure 70. SRI for the different technical domains. Istanbul pilot site

4.1.6 Eilat, Israel (PARadISE)

Energy KPIs

As better described, the Eilat pilot site was equipped with 50 heat pumps, ensuring the coverage of the space cooling load, which represents the main building load.

The energy KPIs are reported in Table 32 for both pre- and post-renovation status for an easy comparison.

On a yearly basis, the electric consumption pre-intervention was in the range of 144 MWh/y. The replacement of the existing cooling system with a new and more efficient VRF system is the main source of the final energy consumption reduction obtained after the renovation. The after-intervention electric consumption is in the range of 114 MWh/y.

Before the renovation, no on-site renewable energy production and storage systems were in place, resulting in the remaining energy KPIs equal to 0 for the pre-intervention status. On the other side, the installed PV system resulted in a yearly PV production of about 170 MWh/y, a value aligned to forecasts from the PVGIS tool⁸ (1876 kWh/(kWp·y)) for the considered system.

The Renewable Energy Share (RE_Sh) resulted the highest among all six pilot sites and indicates that, basically, all the building electric consumption is covered using electricity produced locally by the PV system (99.8 %). This is due mainly to the temporal alignment between the main building consumption (associated with space cooling and therefore occurring in the summer season) and the PV production (also maximum in summer) and to the installation of an electric battery with a

particularly high storage capacity for the considered building and PV system, based on specific requests from the procurer as better explained in section **Error! Reference source not found.**

Regarding instead the Renewable Energy Production to Consumption Ratio (RE_PCR), the obtained value (149 %) indicates that, on a yearly basis, the PV production is around one and a half times the yearly energy consumption.

Finally, the Renewable Energy Utilisation (RE_UT) (66 %) shows that around 2/3 of the PV production is used to cover the building’s electric consumption, both instantaneously or after being temporarily stored in the battery. Although the installed battery has a particularly high storage capacity, around 1/3 of the PV production cannot be used instantaneously or stored in the battery and, eventually, could be sold to the electric grid.

Table 32. Yearly energy KPIs for the Eilat pilot site before and after intervention.

Building size		Energy KPIs, energy vector(s), and related units			Before/after intervention	
Floor area [m ²]	Energy KPI	Energy vector	Unit	Before	After	
700	Final Energy Consumption (E_F)	Electricity	MWh/y / (kWh/m ² /y)	144.725 (206.8)	114.302 (163.3)	
	Renewable Energy Production (RE_P)	Electricity	MWh/y / (kWh/m ² /y)	0 (0)	170.720 (243.9)	
	Renewable Energy Share (RE_Sh)	Electricity	%	0	99.8	
	Renewable Energy Prod. to Cons. Ratio (RE_PCR)	Electricity	%	0	149.3	
	Renewable Energy Utilisation (RE_UT)	Electricity	%	0	66.8	

Note: The values of final energy consumption (E_F) and on-site renewable energy production (RE_P) are reported both in MWh/y and, in brackets, in kWh/m²/y

The following paragraphs analyse in more detail the hourly patterns in terms of Energy KPIs and electrical energy flows due to the interactions between the building’s electric consumption, PV, battery, and electric grid in two weeks considered representative of the building’s operation. Contrary to the analysis made for the other pilot sites, in the case of Eilat, only two weeks are used in this analysis as representative of the winter and summer period, respectively. No mid-season weeks are analysed as their trends for both Energy KPIs and electrical energy flows are similar to those obtained in the considered winter week.

Figure 71 shows the building’s electric consumption (red) and the PV production (yellow) in the considered winter week (1-7 February). In addition, the same figure reports also the hourly values of the other Energy KPIs (RE_Sh, RE_PRC, RE_UT).

Due to the specific climatic conditions of Eilat, the thermal demand for space heating is absent or very limited in both absolute values and duration, and, in the simulations performed, no space heating is provided to the building. In the first week of February, the building shows a base load electric consumption in the range of 7 kW due to the presence of a small data center always active and the standby consumption of the electric devices. During the weekdays (all days except the 1st and the 7th in the considered winter week), when the building is normally used, the electric consumption increases up to around 20 kW in the hours around noon, while on the weekend days (1st and 7th day of the considered winter week) the base load consumption is almost constant throughout the entire day.

In the same winter week, the peak PV production varies in the range 50 - 70 kW based on the solar availability.

Based on the reported building's electric consumption and PV production, and thanks to the presence of a battery with a particularly high storage capacity for the considered building and PV system (194 kWh), during the considered winter week the building's electric consumption is always covered entirely with electricity locally produced from the PV system and eventually temporarily stored in the battery (RE_Sh equal to 100 % over the entire considered winter week).

On the other hand, in all days of the considered winter week, there are hours in which the PV production is higher than the building's electric consumption, resulting in RE_PCR values higher than 100 %.

Finally, the RE_UT is always equal to 100 % (if there is PV production), except in those hours in which the building's electric consumption is lower than the PV production and the battery is already fully charged. This situation generally occurs in the afternoon.

From Figure 72 it is possible to note the interactions between the building's electric consumption, PV, battery, and electric grid.

As can be noted in this figure, the battery is generally charged during the morning, while it is discharged during the evening/night/morning of the following day, before the PV starts producing again. The covering of the building's electric consumption in the hours without PV production resulted in a discharge of the battery that is generally in the range of 50 % – 70 % in terms of battery SoC.

Regarding the interactions with the electric grid, no electricity is taken from the grid in the considered winter week, while electricity is injected into the grid generally in the afternoon, as soon as there is PV surplus and the battery is already fully charged.

Figure 71. Eilat Energy KPIs (1-7 February)

Note: The quantities reported are: building electric consumption (red), PV production (yellow), Renewable Energy Share (RE_Sh, green, right y-axis), Renewable Energy Production to Consumption Ratio (RE_PCR, blue, right y-axis) and Renewable Energy Utilisation (RE_UT, purple, right y-axis). Hourly values for the period 1-7 February

Figure 72. Eilat electric energy flows and battery State of Charge (1-7 February).

Note: The quantities reported are: building electric consumption (red), PV production (yellow), energy to (light green) and from (dark green) battery, energy to (light blue) and from (dark blue) electric grid, battery SoC (dark green, line, right y-axis). Hourly values for the period 1-7 February

In Eilat, as already said, due to the climatic conditions of the location, space cooling is the most important building thermal demand. For this reason, the highest hourly building’s electric consumption values are obtained in the summer season. In the following, the same detailed analysis at hourly level for one week, considered representative of the building’s operation in the summer period, is presented. The considered week is the period 15 – 22 July.

As can be noted by comparing Figure 71 and Figure 73, in summer, the building’s electric consumption reached peaks up to around 40 kW (around 2 times the peak electric consumption observed in the considered winter week).

On the other side, comparing the same two figures, it is also possible to note that the PV production peaks increased from around 50-70 kW to 80 kW due to the higher solar availability.

The just-mentioned two aspects regarding the building's electric consumption and PV production in the considered winter and summer weeks indicate that the higher building's electric consumption occurs in the period with the maximum PV production. This means that there is no temporal mismatch over the year between the building's electric consumption and PV production, as in all cases where space heating is the dominant building's thermal demand (e.g., in the Nuremberg and Velenje pilot sites). This results, in the end, in higher Energy KPIs, particularly in higher RE_Sh at both hourly and yearly basis.

Regarding the considered summer week, the PV production, thanks to the presence of the battery, is able to cover entirely the building's electric consumption (RE_Sh equal to 100 %).

Moreover, although the building's electric consumption is higher than the respective values in the considered winter week, on all days of the considered summer week, there are hours with the PV production that is higher than the electric consumption (RE_PCR higher than 100 %), allowing for battery charge in these hours.

Lastly, the RE_UT indicates that the PV production is entirely used within the building in the morning hours until around noon, when the battery is already fully charged and there is generally still PV surplus. After some hours, however, the RE_UT increased again to 100 %, due to the reduced PV production that is in this period instantaneously entirely used to cover the building's electric load, as instantaneous self-consumption is always prioritized in comparison to the battery usage. The RE_UT then falls to zero when the solar irradiation ceases.

Figure 74 presents the electric energy flows and the interactions between the building's electric consumption, PV, battery, and grid.

The battery is used similarly to the considered winter week, with charging during morning hours and discharge during evening/night/morning of the following day. However, the higher building's electric consumption in the morning resulted in an almost complete (with a decrease in the battery SoC up to 80 %) discharge of the battery on all the weekdays of the considered summer week (all days except the 4th and the 5th).

Regarding the interaction with the electric grid, energy is never taken from the grid; instead, part of the PV surplus is injected into the grid on all days. In comparison to what happens in the considered winter week, in the considered summer week, during the weekdays, less energy is injected into the grid, mainly due to the higher building's electric consumption that more than cancels out the higher PV production. On the weekend days, instead, most of the PV production is injected into the grid (as in the weekend days of the considered winter week) mainly due to the low building's electric consumption on these days.

Figure 73. Eilat Energy KPIs (15-22 July)

Note: The quantities reported are: building electric consumption (red), PV production (yellow), Renewable Energy Share (RE_Sh, green, right y-axis), Renewable Energy Production to Consumption Ratio (RE_PCR, blue, right y-axis) and Renewable Energy Utilisation (RE_UT, purple, right y-axis). Hourly values for the period 15-22 July

Figure 74. Eilat electric energy flows and battery State of Charge (15-22 July).

Note: The quantities reported are: building electric consumption (red), PV production (yellow), energy to (light green) and from (dark green) battery, energy to (light blue) and from (dark blue) electric grid, battery SoC (dark green, line, right y-axis). Hourly values for the period 15-22 July

Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ) KPIs

The indoor temperature discomfort in the Eilat pilot site is evaluated through the number of hours in which the indoor temperature is outside the procuRE defined comfort range (21 °C – 25 °C). For a more detailed analysis, the hours in which the indoor temperature is outside the procuRE defined comfort range are also subdivided into multiple clusters to assess hours in which the indoor temperature is in the range 18 °C – 21 °C and 25 – 28 °C which can be considered as slightly discomfort conditions and acceptable, if limited to short periods, and hours with indoor temperature lower than 18 °C and higher than 28 °C that are instead indicative of a non-negligible users’ discomfort condition.

In Eilat, due to the climatic conditions of the location, discomfort hours are associated with overheating situations only (temperature higher than 25 °C).

The analysis is performed considering only the hours in which the building is occupied (3289 h/y) and at the zone level, with in total 59 zones (single offices, halls, common zones) analysed through simulations. From this analysis, it emerged that the majority of the zones present a number of discomfort hours (for overheating) in the range of 10 – 30 h/y. The Table 33 reports the situation in terms of the number of discomfort hours in three offices, having a number of discomfort hours due to overheating per year in the range of 18 - 25 h/y.

This number can be considered acceptable on a yearly basis, especially considering the building space cooling demand due to the climatic conditions of the location and the fact that the indoor temperature is in any case lower than 28 °C.

For the sake of completeness Table 33 reports also the number of hours in which the indoor temperature in the three offices considered is in the range 18 °C – 21 °C or lower than 18 °C. Although from simulations it resulted that a non-negligible number of hours per year is characterized by indoor temperature in the range of 18 °C – 21 °C (around 300 h/y in all three considered offices) and some hours also present indoor temperature lower than 18 °C, these conditions are obtained from simulations without considering the possibility to use the new HVAC system in heating mode. In fact, although minor, a space heating demand could be present on some days in the coldest months. As the new HVAC system can also cover the eventual building’s space heating demand, this condition does not represent a real problem in terms of users’ comfort.

Table 33. Number of hours over the year with indoor temperature in defined ranges.

Indoor temperature range	Considered zone		
	Office 1	Office 2	Office 3
Below 18 °C	33	29	28
Below 21 °C	305	303	294
procuRE comfort range (21-25 °C)	2,932	2,932	2,949
Above 25 °C	19	25	18
Above 28 °C	0	0	0
Total	3,289	3,289	3,289

Note: In Eilat, the analysis is performed in three different offices

Regarding the indoor air quality in terms of CO₂ level inside the three analysed offices, a non-negligible number of hours with CO₂ levels higher than the considered limit (equal to 1000 ppm) resulted from simulations. In the three considered offices, but this is valid in general for most of the offices present in the building, there are around 1400 h/y in which the CO₂ limit is exceeded. However, after a more detailed analysis, it emerged that the hours with values higher than the considered limit are concentrated in days in which the building should be officially closed but, as happens in reality, the building is partly occupied and so it is considered in the simulations. In these

days, the mechanical ventilation system is considered switched off, or, in any case, it gives a minor contribution to the indoor air renewal, and this has resulted in CO₂ levels up to around 2000 - 2500 ppm. On the contrary, on working days, when the mechanical ventilation system works properly, the CO₂ limit of 1000 ppm is always ensured.

Environmental KPIs

The renovation package installed in Eilat resulted in a reduction of the electricity consumption due to the new VRF system installed, while the PV and battery system can cover almost entirely (99.8 %) the building’s electrical consumption, as reported in previous paragraphs.

Considering the grid electricity emission factor for Israel¹⁰, which is the highest among the countries where the six pilot sites are located, the yearly CO₂ emissions passed from 80.5 tCO₂/y (pre-intervention) to 0.5 tCO₂/y (post-intervention) with, basically, a complete elimination of CO₂ emissions due to the electricity consumed within the building. These results are reported in Table 34. As in the other pilot sites, this calculation does not consider the beneficial effects in terms of CO₂ emission reduction due to the PV surplus exported to the grid.

Table 34. Yearly CO₂ emissions of pre- and post-intervention situation and related savings. Eilat pilot site

Status	Energy vector	Final Energy consumption	CO ₂ factor	CO ₂ emission	CO ₂ emission savings	
		[MWh/y]	[tCO ₂ /MWh]	[tCO ₂ /y]	[tCO ₂ /y]	[%]
Before	Grid el.	144.725	0.556 ¹⁰	80.5	-	-
	Total	-	-	80.5	-	-
After	Grid el.	114.302	0.556 ¹⁰	63.6	-	-
	Total	-	-	63.6	16.9	21 %

Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI)

As reported in Table 35, the Eilat pilot site shows one of the lowest pre-intervention overall SRI and the highest post-intervention overall SRI, indicating that the interventions made resulted in the biggest improvements in terms of overall SRI score.

Reasons for the low pre-intervention values are associated with the absence of any local renewable energy production and storage system (PV and battery), the absence of the mechanical ventilation system, the use of a notable number of single heat pumps (50 heat pumps) working only in cooling mode, and the absence of a overall control and monitoring system.

The implemented interventions focused on both replacing existing units with more efficient systems (5 VRF units in replacement of the 50 stand-alone heat pumps), as well as installing new mechanical ventilation, PV and battery systems and a unique BMS able to control the main building systems. All these interventions are particularly beneficial to improve the SRI score, accounting for better and more flexible management of the main system components, controlled using a unique BMS, able to

manage the system using both inputs from local sensors (e.g., temperature, humidity, CO₂ sensors) and remote ones as, in principle, external operators requests (e.g., requests from the local DSO).

Figure 76 shows the SRI scores for the different impact criteria. The improvements in the energy efficiency, comfort, and energy flexibility and storage criteria are partly due to the installation of new VRF and mechanical ventilation systems (energy efficiency and comfort) and new PV and battery systems (energy flexibility and storage). Another contribution to the SRI improvements in these criteria is also associated with the new BMS managing these systems. The same BMS is solely responsible for the improvements in the maintenance and fault prediction, and information to occupants criteria.

Looking at the SRI scores for the different technical domains (Figure 76), it can be noted that the new VRF system is also able to cover eventual space heating demand (although, due to the considered location, cooling is the prevalent building’s thermal demand). Moreover, the use of new VRF and mechanical ventilation systems, managed through the developed BMS, results in a SRI score relatively high for heating, cooling, and ventilation. The improvements in the electricity technical domain are instead related to the newly installed PV and battery system and their control and monitoring through the developed BMS. Finally, the BMS is solely responsible for the improvement in the monitoring and control technical domain.

Table 35. SRI overall score and related class before and after renovation, Eilat pilot site

Characteristic	Before intervention	After intervention
SRI overall score	16.4 %	77.2 %
SRI class	Lower than 20 %	Between 65 % and 80 %

Figure 75. SRI for the different impact criteria. Eilat pilot site

Figure 76. SRI for the different technical domains. Eilat pilot site

4.2 User experience

The user experience encompasses the procurer's feedback on the co-design phase, which was extended to incorporate insights into the effectiveness of training activities from their perspective. This has been complemented with insights from the occupants' and operators' surveys.

The co-design was a continuous procedure envisioned as a cornerstone of the renovation packages to be developed along the three phases of the procuRE project. It was intended to capture input from procurers to ensure that all necessary actions were taken by the relevant project stakeholders. It was designed to consider the following principles:

- It is **inclusive** as it includes representatives from all stakeholder groups involved in the future service delivery and utilises feedback, advice and decisions from procurers, operators, possibly occupants and other professionals in the field.
- It is **actor-centred** as each step consists of the actions of individual or collective entities (persons or organisations) and is described, enacted, and analysed from that perspective.
- It is **iterative** in its overall approach and steps, as changes and adaptations are a natural part of the process.
- It is **evaluative** since each step, its alignment with the previous ones (summative perspective) and its anticipated impacts on following steps (formative perspective) are evaluated empirically.

- It is **outcome-focused** as it is designed to achieve outcomes, where the potential solutions can be rapidly tested, effectiveness measured, and the scaling of these solutions can be developed with stakeholders and in context.

Following these principles, some dimensions were developed to assess the quality and effectiveness from one phase to another and provide evidence of the entire renovation process. They focused on the following features and activities during the respective co-design procedure's phase:

- **Communication process:** clarity, consistency, and responsiveness in interactions.
- **Decision-making process:** how well decisions were made between suppliers and procurers.
- **Information-gathering and quality process:** the thoroughness and relevance of the data used to understand challenges, as well as the clarity and completeness of the updates or technical information.
- **Effort intensity:** whether the co-design process required reasonable or excessive effort.
- **Transparency:** how openly the renovation package and its rationale were shared
- **Alignment:** How clearly the project scope and objectives (for each phase) were explained at the beginning of each phase.

Methodologically, this was implemented by a sequence of surveys targeting the procurers at the end of the respective phase. Each procurer had to submit a response per supplier active in each phase. The following subsections analyse the results of the co-design process for the two suppliers that remained active throughout all phases. The analysis combines the assessments submitted by all procurers and normalises the dimensions' scores to a 1-5 scale.

4.2.1 [SEBR] Assessment of co-design procedure

The procurers' assessment of the co-design procedure with the SEBR consortium reveals an overall positive trajectory across phases, indicating a gradual improvement in the implementation of the renovations as the project matured.

The procurers' feedback during Phase I indicates that although they recognise potential benefits of the co-design procedure, these may not have materialised at that point due to the relatively short period of this phase (approx. three months). This finding is consistent with observations from Phase II, where procurers noted that communication between procurers and suppliers was enhanced due to the use of ICT infrastructure complemented with regular meetings to streamline the decision-making process.

Most of the benefits highlighted by the procurers were realised during Phase III, as there had been considerable time for awareness among relevant stakeholders, and the changes were tangible, given that the hardware's installation was finalised. Particularly, some procurers observed that the PCP approach and the co-design procedure offered a higher degree of flexibility and agility in the procurement and tendering processes, which materialised when acquiring the necessary equipment for the renovations. This facilitated a swift decision-making process, which was further enhanced by the emphasis on consensus among stakeholders.

With the implementation of the awareness and training component in Phase III, the procurers referred to an effective collaboration between procurers and suppliers facilitated by the co-design procedure. The constant interaction and flexibility in the decision-making process benefited the project by enabling the deployment of necessary changes to address project challenges, such as installation delays.

Moreover, the involvement of additional, yet relevant stakeholders, such as teachers and staff, facilitated user buy-in as it allowed them to understand the project’s goals before they were implemented, rather than viewing them once the new hardware was installed. Several procurers expressed that this bottom-up approach offered the possibility of translating policy objectives into concrete insights for building occupants.

Procurers also highlighted the opportunity presented by the co-design procedure to develop creative and responsive solutions to technical and functional requirements, as well as site-specific challenges that emerged during the renovations. This observation was coupled with the procedure’s potential for optimised resource allocation, where procurers also noted that investments were directed toward the most effective solutions, thereby avoiding unnecessary costs and inefficiencies. Examples of creative solutions include the noise reduction fence for the heat pump and cable-routing alternatives to avoid safety issues, both in Nuremberg.

Still, even with regular meetings and feedback alternatives in place, the procurers’ feedback suggests that a local contact point is needed to manage issues that are likely to occur during the project deployment, such as the handling of subcontractors during the installation phases. Additionally, it was noted that although the co-design procedure offers a quicker revision time, this is to some extent hindered when working with local municipalities (governments) that have their own internal processes. Thus, the co-design procedure would benefit from a more comprehensive mapping of internal municipal processes (and departments) to anticipate potential bottlenecks.

Figure 77 presents the normalised scores for the seven dimensions across the three phases for the provider SEBR.

Figure 77. Assessment of features and activities during the co-design procedure - SEBR

Notes: *Phase II values represent the phase average, as the assessment was done in two mid-points, namely, for the first half and the second half of Phase II

4.2.2 [PARadISE] Assessment of co-design procedure

The trajectory of the co-design procedure, led by the PARadISE consortium, reveals a more complex landscape, as the evolution across phases is only gradual between the first and second. Afterwards, the procurer’s assessment for all dimensions shrinks. It is worth noting that compared to SEBR, the aggregated evaluation begins with a higher normalised score as Figure 2 shows. Since the suppliers’

assessment considers all procurers, this indicates a higher perception of the co-design procedure components presented at the beginning of the project.

Similar to the previous case, the feedback from Phase I also suggests that the phase's short period did not allow the materialisation of the procedure benefits, i.e., reaffirming that although the co-design seeks to facilitate processes by reducing management and implementation times, this still requires a time frame so that all stakeholders familiarise with its components and the procedure matures.

The use of ICT infrastructure (e.g., platforms for virtual meetings or file sharing) is perceived as a value-added feature from the co-design procedure compared to traditional approaches to renovation. However, the adherence to a single platform or technology is mentioned by procurers as a lesson learnt, as in the beginning the use of multiple ones decreased efficiency or duplicated processes and generated confusion.

During Phase II, the procurers observed that once all parties were familiar with the collaborative tools, the supplier-procuer exchange proceeded smoothly, indicating the time gains achieved through the co-design procedure. Additionally, the use of innovative technologies, such as digital twins (Matterport) of the demonstration buildings, was highlighted as an exemplary outcome of the co-design process, which in turn facilitated the integration with the energy modelling and BIM technology, enabling the team to generate feasibility studies and document preliminary investment efforts and needs. The procurers noted that the consortium demonstrated significant improvements in this phase and employed innovative and flexible methodologies, such as design thinking, which provided greater clarity to the renovation approach to be implemented afterwards. This is consistent with the scores obtained at the end of the phase, which were the highest across phases.

As part of Phase III, procurers also highlighted that the co-design procedure offered efficiency gains, mostly through the streamlined communication frameworks and proactive challenge identification. Some procurers' experience suggests that the potential advantages envisioned by the co-design procedure (e.g., early risk mapping and iterative feedback) require a degree of familiarity to realise its full potential, as there may be issues regarding fragmented data collection processes, unclear responsibility assignment, and insufficient validation protocols. The decrease in scores observed during this phase is attributed to challenges faced in implementing the renovations. These challenges stemmed from a combination of external factors—most notably the political situation in Israel—and delays in the subcontracting process. As a result, a tailored approach was required, diverging from the standard framework established by the co-design procedure. Figure 78 summarises the results graphically.

Figure 78. Assessment of features and activities during the co-design procedure - PARadISE

Notes: *Phase II values represent the Phase average, as the assessment was done in two mid-points, namely, for the first half and the second half of Phase II.

4.2.3 Operators – Survey Results

The survey results shed light on operators’ experiences with the new technologies installed in the demonstration sites. The collected feedback comes mostly from the facility managers and offers qualitative indications about overall satisfaction with the technical aspects of the solutions. On average, operators expressed that they were generally satisfied with the new systems; however, there were some observations, which are summarised in the following subsections. The results are grouped into three analytical categories to provide specific insights on the systems’ performance and usability, as well as the systems’ maintenance and training effectiveness.

Systems performance and usability

The feedback on the **BMS** experience across sites indicates that it is somewhat difficult to use. Operators mentioned both integration and usability challenges. In Barcelona, the coexistence of the legacy BMS with the new platform creates confusion regarding control responsibilities and system response. Nuremberg reports difficulties with configuring and operating the heat pump, as well as ensuring effective communication between the heat pump and the ventilation system. In Velenje, full integration of installed technologies such as photovoltaics, batteries, heat pumps, and ventilation is still lacking, with no cross-system optimization or predictive controls for occupancy and weather. The system's user interface is considered complex, with a steep learning curve and limited capacity for intuitive control or custom scenarios. Eilat notes technical access issues through the remote platform (*AnyDesk*), poor graphical interfaces, and low user-friendliness. Similarly, Vila Nova de Gaia highlights a learning curve for using the platform, along with differences between adjusting basic parameters (like temperature or schedules) and performing more advanced functions or system configuration.

On the contrary, operators reported the **Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning system (HVAC)** was relatively easier to use. Still, the feedback regarding the HVAC experience points to challenges in both system setup and data accessibility. In Nuremberg, for instance, assigning addresses and ensuring proper communication between different system components proved relatively difficult.

In Vila Nova de Gaia, users reported that accessing data and system information is only possible through the supplier's platform via an API, limiting direct or flexible access to information.

Regarding the **PV** system, operators reported that it was easy or very easy to use. Still, challenges were reported on data retrieval in Vila Nova de Gaia and Nuremberg.

Overall, the feedback indicates that most sites have observed either moderate or significant improvements in the building's energy performance since the installation of the new systems, with only one site reporting no noticeable change (Velenje). The responses suggest a generally positive impact, though the extent of improvement varies across locations.

Systems maintenance

It should be noted that operators have had limited experience with the new systems, and as the hardware is entirely new, maintenance requests may not have yet arisen, and some operators have noted this. Thus, the feedback is based on the information received from contractors and issues detected during installations (e.g., issues with lighting in Istanbul and with the heat pump in Vila Nova de Gaia, both already addressed). All in all, maintenance requirements following the installation of the new systems present a mixed picture. Across the sites, two locations (Barcelona, Eilat) reported no noticeable change in maintenance needs, two others (Velenje, Vila Nova de Gaia) indicated slightly more maintenance is now required. In contrast, two responses (Nuremberg and Istanbul) noted slightly reduced maintenance demands to be expected.

Training effectiveness

The overall assessment of the training provided for managing the new systems reflects a generally adequate experience across sites, where most operators rated it 'somewhat effective', indicating that the training met basic professional needs but left room for improvement. The procuRE project envisaged assistance after installation. The implementation of this requirement was also explored as part of the survey, and most operators said they were offered support to navigate the platform (BMS), including remote assistance, as well as access to a hotline and email from the suppliers. Still, operators mentioned isolated gaps in meeting operational requirements.

Additionally, the survey explored whether the training increased operators' confidence in managing the building's new systems. On average, respondents indicated they felt 'somewhat confident', suggesting that while the training provided a basic level of preparedness, there remains room for improvement. Notably, some operators highlighted that no training was provided in advance on managing system alarms. This specific gap is expected to be addressed through ongoing, case-by-case support after the installation was completed.

4.2.4 Occupants – Insights from the Awareness-raising Activities for

In phase III, the suppliers (PARadISE and SEBR consortia) implemented a series of awareness-raising and training activities. These materials were targeted at the building occupants to make them aware of the solutions' key components and particularly, their contribution to decarbonisation of the energy matrix at the local level. The following subsections present the main insights of the two suppliers.

SEBR

The SEBR consortium carried out the training and awareness-raising activities in Barcelona, Nuremberg and Vila Nova de Gaia, i.e., in one office building and two schools, respectively. Given

the varied user profiles within these demonstration sites, the activities differ between purely office and school-related populations. There was a further breakdown among the latter (school-related population) to distinguish between adults and students (pupils, particularly).

The materials were produced in local languages and accompanied by a workshop-like session led by a supplier’s facilitator. These resources highlighted key advantages of the solutions tailored to the demonstration sites in the context of rising temperatures linked to global warming, emphasising their contribution from a non-technical perspective. Moreover, to maximise the engagement of the younger populations (relevant for Nuremberg and Vila Nova de Gaia), the suppliers prepared an illustrated booklet to address the issue of rising temperatures and provide general recommendations for adaptation and mitigation of global change. A sample of these materials is included in Figure 79 below.

Figure 79. Awareness-raising and training materials samples (SEBR)

Note: These are a selection of the resources produced for Nuremberg, Vola Nova de Gaia (one for children, another for the adult occupants and a screenshot of the booklets) and Barcelona, in German, Portuguese and Spanish, respectively. The full materials are available upon request. SEBR authored these materials.

The procurers obtained feedback about these activities as part of their regular interaction with the building users. They reported that the digital booklets were among the most valuable materials, since these were perceived as visually appealing and offered the possibility to be reused in other classes, which is instrumental in fostering engagement with these topics and in discussing the solutions’ potential in this context.

PARadISE

The PARadISE consortium provided renovation services for offices in Eilat; a vocational, education and training facility in Istanbul and a school in Velenje. The awareness and training content was adjusted to fit the relatively larger adult population in this subset of demonstration sites.

The supplier implemented an awareness campaign presenting the building retrofits for energy efficiency at each site, followed by an interactive session designed based on the needs expressed by the sites’ representatives. For the school in Velenje, additional materials were produced, including a series of suggested classroom activities to be implemented by teachers. Figure 80 presents a selected sample of the materials prepared by the supplier.

Figure 80. Awareness-raising and training materials samples (PARadISE)

The figure displays four sample pages from the PARadISE materials. The top-left page is titled '1. Giriş' (Introduction) and discusses the 'EU's objective' and 'Net sıfır sera gazı (GHG) emisyonu ile 2050 yılına kadar iklim nötrlüğüne ulaşmak' (Achieving climate neutrality by 2050 with net zero GHG emissions). The top-right page is titled '3בנייני אפס אנרגיה' (3 Zero Energy Buildings) and lists 'אסטרטגיות סביביות' (Environmental strategies) and 'אסטרטגיות אקטיביות' (Active strategies). The bottom-left page is titled '1.1 Sustainable School Challenge' and includes an objective to encourage creative sustainability solutions and a challenge to divide students into teams. The bottom-right page is titled '1.2 Eco schools program' and describes the program's goal to promote environmental education in schools.

Note: These are a selection of the resources produced for Istanbul, Eilat and Velenje (focus on materials for students and teachers) in Turkish, Hebrew and English, respectively. The full materials are available upon request. PARadISE authored these materials.

The procurers acknowledged that while the sessions successfully integrated site-specific content, the overall awareness activities showed a high degree of similarity across sites. They suggested that, should the project be replicated elsewhere, it may be beneficial to explore opportunities for greater contextual adaptation. This observation stems from the need to balance a consistent overarching approach with the distinct characteristics and use cases of each site.

APPENDIX 1: OPERATOR SURVEY

This survey aims to gather feedback from operators (facility managers, maintenance staff, etc.) who interact directly with the newly installed systems. Your feedback will help us evaluate the usability, integration, and performance of these systems, as well as the effectiveness of the training and support provided.

General Information

Question	Description	Answer Options	Mandatory
Procurer Name	Please identify the procurer responsible for the building.	Barcelona, Gaia, Eilat, Istanbul, Nuremberg, Velenje	Yes
Role in the Project	What is your role in the building? (e.g., Facility Manager, Maintenance Staff)	Dropdown (Facility Manager, Maintenance Staff, etc.)	Yes

System Performance and Usability

Question	Description	Answer Options	Mandatory
Systems interaction	Which of the following systems have you interacted with in your role? (Select all that apply)	Multiple option: BMS / HVAC / PV / Lighting	Yes

If Systems Interacted with = BMS

Question	Description	Answer Options	Mandatory
BMS Usability	How would you rate the overall usability of the new BMS?	Very Easy to Use / Easy to Use / Somewhat Difficult to Use / Difficult to Use	Yes
BMS Challenges	Have you encountered any specific challenges in using the BMS?	Yes / No / If yes, please specify: _____	Yes (additional details optional)

If Systems Interacted with = HVAC

Question	Description	Answer Options	Mandatory
HVAC Usability	How would you rate the usability of the new HVAC system?	Very Easy to Use / Easy to Use / Somewhat Difficult to Use / Difficult to Use	Yes
HVAC Challenges	Have you encountered any specific challenges in using the HVAC system?	Yes / No / If yes, please specify: _____	Yes (additional details optional)

If Systems Interacted with = PV

Question	Description	Answer Options	Mandatory
----------	-------------	----------------	-----------

PV Usability	How would you rate the usability of the PV system?	Very Easy to Use / Easy to Use / Somewhat Difficult to Use / Difficult to Use	Yes
PV Challenges	Have you encountered any specific challenges in using the PV system?	Yes / No / If yes, please specify: _____	Yes (additional details optional)

If Systems Interacted with = Lighting

Question	Description	Answer Options	Mandatory
Lighting Usability	How would you rate the usability of the Lighting system?	Very Easy to Use / Easy to Use / Somewhat Difficult to Use / Difficult to Use	Yes
Lighting Challenges	Have you encountered any specific challenges in using the Lighting system?	Yes / No / If yes, please specify: _____	Yes (additional details optional)

Once operator declared all interactions

Question	Description	Answer Options	Mandatory
Energy efficiency performance	To what extent have you noticed an improvement in the building’s energy performance since the new systems were installed?	Significant improvement / Moderate improvement / No noticeable change / Decrease in performance	Yes

Systems Maintenance

Question	Description	Answer Options	Mandatory
Maintenance Requirements	To what extent have the maintenance requirements of the new systems changed compared to the previous systems?	Significantly less maintenance required / Slightly less maintenance required/ No Noticeable Change / Slightly more maintenance required / Significantly More Maintenance	Yes
Unexpected Maintenance Issues	Have you encountered any unexpected maintenance issues?	Yes / No / If yes, please specify: _____	Yes (additional details optional)
System Interoperability Challenges	Have you noticed any issues with system interoperability (between systems like BMS, HVAC, PV, and lighting)?	Yes / No / If yes, please describe: _____	Yes

Training Effectiveness

Question	Description	Answer Options	Mandatory
----------	-------------	----------------	-----------

Training Quality	Based on your professional needs, how effective was the training provided for managing the new systems?	Very effective / Very Somewhat effective / Somewhat ineffective / Not effective at all	Yes
Training Coverage	Did the training cover all necessary aspects of system operation?	Yes / No / If no, what additional training would have been helpful? _____	Yes
On-demand training	What additional training would have been helpful?	Open-ended question	No
Confidence in System Management	How confident are you in managing the building's new systems after the training?	Extremely confident / Somewhat confident / Somewhat unconfident / Not Confident	Yes
Support Availability	Can you access or request additional support (besides the manuals) when the systems are not functioning as expected?	Yes / No / If yes, what kind of support have you been offered? _____	Yes (additional details optional)

Feedback and Suggestions

Question	Description	Answer Options	Mandatory
Overall Satisfaction	How satisfied are you with the new systems?	Very Satisfied / Satisfied / Neutral / Unsatisfied / Very Unsatisfied	Yes
System Improvements	What improvements, if any, would you suggest for the new systems or their operation?	Open-ended text field	No
Open Comments	Please share any additional comments or insights about your experience with the new systems:	Open-ended text field	No

APPENDIX 2: MODELS' VALIDATION BASED ON MONITORED DATA

This section reports the methodology applied to validate the models' results. In this context, the term models refers to both building and energy systems models (e.g., HVAC, PV system) used to simulate the building operation.

The models' validation process is important for mainly two objectives.

First, the models have been used to calculate some of the KPIs presented in the RfT_TD2_ "Challenge Brief" and shortly described in section 3.1 as not enough monitored data are available from the pilot sites for a meaningful evaluation of the described KPIs at yearly time horizon.

Second, the models constitute a virtual environment where the optimized control logics developed for the specific pilot site can be tested. The testing of the optimized control logic in a validated simulation environment allows for testing a wider range of potential control logics to find the optimal one based on the defined objective in a shorter time and without affecting the occupants' comfort. The fact that the models are validated means that the results obtained from them can be reasonably considered representative of the behaviour of the considered real building.

Models' results, in terms of building electric consumption and PV production, have been validated following the procedure described in the following:

1. Identification of the days to be tested and eventual identification of similar days (measured and simulated days) to be compared.

In this step, the two suppliers worked in a slightly different way.

Paradise prepared an infrastructure to allow the direct connection between their models and some measured quantities. More specifically, their infrastructure allows to feed the models with boundary conditions (external temperature, Global Horizontal Irradiation (GHI)) measured on site. In this way, the models work with exactly the same boundary conditions, in terms of climatic conditions, as in the real case, limiting the possible errors in the considered outputs (building's electric consumption, PV production) associated with differences in the input quantities.

SEBR, instead, checked and found days in common meteorological yearly (with hourly time resolution) files used in dynamic simulation environments that are similar, in terms of external temperature and GHI, to those measured on site. In this way, the real measurements are compared with simulation results on days that present a similar external temperature and GHI patterns. The comparison and the definition of the pairs of days to be considered is done using as KPIs the correlation coefficient and the Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE)

2. Setting of the boundary conditions, in terms of building usage (schedule of occupancy) and system control in the model as same (or as similar as possible) to those applied in the specific pilot.

This aims to avoid/minimize differences in building's electric consumption between real measurements and simulations associated with differences in how the building is used or the related systems controlled.

3. Qualitative and quantitative assessment of the simulated and monitored building electric consumption and PV production.

This assessment includes a qualitative analysis of the hourly pattern of electricity consumption and PV production from simulations and monitored data, and a quantitative assessment using indicators as the correlation coefficient and the RMSE.

4. If needed, calibration of the models, adjusting parameters (e.g., management of the heat pump operation, occupancy schedule) to improve the agreement between simulated and measured results.
5. Repeat the process until meaningful results are obtained.

At the end of the process, the models can be considered representative of the building's operation and can be used to calculate the KPIs described in the section 3.1, and to test eventual optimized control strategies, with a realistic estimation of their effect if applied, before future real implementation in the pilot sites.

In the following, a series of figures are shown to present the comparison between the models' results and measured data for both suppliers.

Figure 81 shows the comparison done by the SEBR consortium between measured data (red) and simulated data (blue) for one day in Nuremberg. As already mentioned above, SEBR compared different days that present similar hourly patterns in terms of external temperature and GHI. This can be noted in the upper figures presenting the external temperature trend (upper left figure) of one measured day (red) and the hourly pattern of a day available in the Nuremberg climatic data file used in the simulations (blue). The external temperature difference between measured data and the data used in the simulations is up to 1.5 °C, and, most of the time, lower than 1 °C.

The upper right figure shows the other considered boundary quantity, the GHI. The GHI patterns from measurements and from the file used in the simulations for the same pair of days show slightly higher differences. However, the typical bell shape centred around noon can be noted in both profiles.

The lower figures present instead the model outputs and the measured data in terms of building's electric consumption (bottom left figure) and PV production (bottom right figure).

Regarding the building's electric consumption, although there are some differences in the hourly values between measured (red) and simulated (blue) quantities, the hourly patterns are well aligned, with similar peaks, similar base load consumption, and with the two hourly patterns well aligned in terms of time.

Finally, the bottom right figure shows the PV production obtained from measurements (red) and from the simulations (blue). The PV production hourly pattern obtained from simulations is strictly aligned with the GHI pattern visible in the upper right figure, while the measured PV production shows higher differences. The differences between the measured GHI and the measured PV production can be partly due to the fact that the measured GHI data values are taken from a weather station and not measured at the pilot site, where some effects (e.g. shadings) could influence the real PV production.

Figure 81. Comparison between simulation results (blue) and measured quantities (red) for the Nuremberg Model’s validation

Note: The figure shows the comparison between simulated and measured quantities for one pair of days used for model validation. The sub-figures show: upper left figure: external temperature hourly pattern of the measured (red) and simulated (blue) day; upper right figure: GHI hourly pattern of the measured (red) and simulated (blue) day; bottom left figure: building’s electric consumption of the measured (red) and simulated (blue) day; bottom right figure: PV production hourly pattern of the measured (red) and simulated (blue) day.

Paradise consortium, instead, compares model results and measured data in terms of building’s electric consumption and PV production using, as boundary conditions, exactly the same external temperature and GHI hourly time series.

Figure 82 presents the comparison between measured (blue) and simulated (red) building’s hourly electric consumption in Eilat for the period 5-18 May 2025. From this figure, it can be noted the well alignment in terms of both peak and base electric consumption (except on 13th and 18th May, in which a slightly higher difference in terms of peak electric consumption can be noted) between measured and simulated values. The temporal alignment is also very good, indicating that the schedule profile in terms of occupancy and the building’s usage considered in the simulation environment are aligned with reality. A higher difference between simulated and measured electric consumption can be observed on weekend days (May 9th, 10th, 16th, 17th) where the building should not be used and characterized by the base load consumption, while in reality, also based on the procurer’s feedback, the building is partially used.

Figure 82. Building’s electric consumption in Eilat

Note: from simulations (red) and measurements (blue). Period: 5-18 May 2025

Finally, Figure 83 shows the simulated hourly PV production in the Eilat pilot site from the building’s model and the measured PV production at the pilot site in the same period. The fact that the values are negative is simply because the suppliers used the convention of considering consumption positive (see the figure above about the building’s electric consumption) and PV production negative (see the figure below).

As can be noted in the figure, the measured and simulated PV production are, in general, well aligned, with the model able to catch the measured PV production’s hourly pattern. The main differences are associated with the peak production on some days (especially on May 12th, 13th, and 15th). These differences come from the control logic used to manage the PV system. In fact, the PV system is managed in a way that avoids injecting electricity into the grid, and this results in the curtailment of the PV production in some hours. As this behaviour strictly depends on the interaction among the building’s electric consumption, PV production, and battery SoC, it is possible that an error in the estimation of the building’s electric consumption resulted in a difference in PV production between the model and reality.

Figure 83. PV production in Eilat

Note: from simulations (red) and measurements (blue). Period: 5-18 May 2025

APPENDIX 3: DEFINITION OF PROCURE KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

This appendix describes the KPIs used to assess a de-fossilisation renovation and have originally been defined for the Challenge Brief which was part of the tender. Many indicators are custom build to reflect the operation of a building over time rather than as a yearly statistic.

Energy Key Performance Indicators

The energy performance KPIs assess how effectively on-site RES will be harvested and exploited. In the calculation of KPIs, one year is defined as 8,760 hours.

Final energy consumption (E_F)

This indicator refers to the utilisation of different energy vectors to cover the energy demand of the building independently of their origin, either local or remote (i.e., energy networks). The procurers want to make sure first that the best technologies with the least overall costs are exploited, minimising the energy needed on site.

The suppliers are requested to assess and provide final energy consumption values for each of the energy vectors (e. g. thermal, electric) utilised on site, at least on an hourly basis for the entire year. For each building accounted for in the specific design phase, the suppliers are requested to provide both whole-building energy consumption expressed in kWh/h and specific energy consumption per gross building volume (including façades volume) expressed in kWh/(m³h). In addition to these values, suppliers are also requested to assess and provide yearly final energy consumption both in MWh/y and kWh/(m³y). The yearly final energy consumption values are obtained integrating the hourly final energy consumption over the entire year.

Assessment: The procurers will use both yearly final energy consumption values (MWh/y and kWh/(m³y)) for the quantitative assessment of the system performance, and the hourly distribution to verify the calculations presented.

Both dynamic simulations and semi-dynamic methods accepted by European and National norms are acceptable calculation methods. The suppliers are requested to provide indication on the calculation method and the boundary conditions adopted, together with the results obtained as part of the offer and future deliverables at the end of each design phase.

On-site renewable energy production (RE_P)

This indicator refers to the on-site production of renewable energy for the different energy vectors utilised on-site. Procurers want to make sure that the best available technologies are exploited, maximising the coverage of the energy needed on site by means of locally available RES.

“On-site” refers to the building and its nearest vicinity – air, surface, ground and underground –, which, in any case, cannot exceed the building premises or attached structures. Although, for some Demonstration Sites large land surface is available, the procurers want to make sure that the solutions adopted are highly replicable at all their building stock. During the project, solution proposals for functional structures within described perimeters (e.g., courtyard) will be assessed during Co-Design on a case-by-case basis.

The suppliers are requested to assess and provide on-site renewable energy production values for each of the energy vectors utilised on site, at least on an hourly basis for the entire year. For each building accounted for in the specific design phase, the suppliers are requested to provide both

overall on-site renewable energy production expressed in kWh/h and specific renewable energy production per gross building volume (including façades volume) expressed in kWh/(m³h). In addition to these values, suppliers are also requested to assess and provide yearly on-site renewable energy production both in MWh/y and kWh/(m³y). The yearly on-site renewable energy production values are obtained by integrating the hourly on-site renewable energy production over the entire year.

Assessment: The procurers will use both yearly on-site renewable energy production values (MWh/y and kWh/(m³y)) for the quantitative assessment of the system performance, and the hourly distribution to verify the calculations presented.

Both dynamic simulations and semi-dynamic methods accepted by European norms are acceptable as calculation methods. The suppliers must provide descriptions of the calculation method and the adopted boundary conditions, together with the results obtained as part of the deliverables at the end of each design phase.

Renewable energy share (RE_Sh)

This indicator states the fraction of final energy consumed that is either covered by renewable energy produced on-site during the same timeframe or previously produced and stored on-site. The suppliers are requested to assess and provide renewable energy share values for each of the energy vectors utilised on site, at least on an hourly basis for the entire year.

This indicator is calculated for each energy vector “j” using the following formula:

$$RE_Sh_{i,j} = \frac{(E_{REU,i} + E_{EFS,i})}{E_{F,i}} \Big|_j$$

Where:

- $RE_Sh_{i,j}$ is the renewable energy share calculated at hour “i”, for each of the energy vectors “j” covered through renewable energy.
- $E_{REU,i}$ is the renewable energy produced on-site at hour “i” and used to cover a final energy use during the same hour.
- $E_{EFS,i}$ is the renewable energy previously generated and stored on-site used to cover the final energy use during hour “i”.
- $E_{F,i}$ is the final energy consumption at hour “i”, for each of the energy vectors “j”.

In addition to hourly values, suppliers are also requested to assess and provide yearly renewable energy share values. For each energy vector “j”, the yearly on-site renewable energy share value is obtained as the integral of the hourly values:

$$RE_PCR_{Y,j} = \frac{\sum_1^{8760} E_{REP,i}}{\sum_1^{8760} E_{F,i}} \Big|_j$$

Assessment: The procurers will use both the yearly renewable energy production to consumption ratio for the quantitative assessment of the system performance, and the hourly values distribution to check whether an attempt has been placed on continuously balancing local renewable energy production and the building’s final energy use. As some buildings like schools are not in use during relevant periods of the day and of the year, a better matching reduces the need for storage capacity installed optimising the utilisation of renewable energy produced on-site.

On-site renewable energy utilisation (RE_UT)

This indicator refers to the renewable energy that is produced and used or stored on site, hence without being exported and then re-imported to the building premises. Export/Import of on-site produced renewable energy has a cost for the community, both environmental and economic, due to losses, infrastructures to be set up, etc. The procurers want to make sure that the burden onto the community is minimised technically and economically as much as possible. The suppliers are requested to assess and provide on-site renewable energy utilisation values for each of the energy vectors utilised on site, at least on an hourly basis. The values should be calculated as the ratio of renewable energy produced and used or stored on-site along the considered timeframe, and the renewable energy produced in the same timeframe. The on-site renewable energy utilisation shall be calculated as:

$$RE_UT_{i,j} = \frac{(E_{REU,i} + E_{ETS,i})}{E_{REP,i}} \Big|_j$$

Where:

- $RE_UT_{i,j}$ is the renewable energy utilisation calculated at hour “i”, for each of the energy vectors “j” covered through renewable energy.
- $E_{REU,i}$ is the renewable energy produced at hour “i” and used to cover a final energy use during the same hour.
- $E_{ETS,i}$ is the renewable energy produced and stored on-site at hour “i”.
- $E_{REP,i}$ is the total renewable energy produced on-site at hour “i”, for each of the energy vectors “j”.

In addition to the hourly values, suppliers are required to assess and provide yearly on-site renewable energy utilisation values. For each energy vector “j”, the yearly on-site renewable energy utilisation value shall be calculated as:

$$RE_UT_{Y,j} = \frac{\sum_1^{8760} (E_{REU,i} + E_{ETS,i})}{\sum_1^{8760} E_{REP,i}} \Big|_j$$

Assessment: The procurers will use both yearly on-site renewable energy utilisation values for the quantitative assessment of the system performance, and the hourly values distribution to check whether continuous balancing of local renewable energy production and utilisation has been achieved.

IEQ Key Performance Indicators

Retrofitting of buildings should not have only an energy dimension, but also consider users, whose health and welfare are of utmost relevance for the Procurers. Accordingly, IEQ should be considered as a key element of the Suppliers’ proposals.

Starting in Phase I, more or less stringent IEQ requirements for each Demonstration Sites might be negotiated with the procurers through the Co-Design procedure. Better comfort conditions offered, e.g., accounting for improved humidity control compared to the minimum normative requirements, will be a merit.

Indoor air temperature (IEQ_T)

Suppliers are requested to respect minimum requirements in terms of thermo-hygrometric air conditions as per European and national normative. During occupancy hours, the temperature should never fall below 21°C nor exceed 25°C.

Assessment: The procurers will use the total number of hours during which the indoor air temperature level is being exceeded for the quantitative assessment of the system performance, and the hourly distribution to check how continuous achieved conditions are.

Indoor air quality (IEQ_AQ)

Suppliers are requested to assure that suitable air quality conditions are delivered to the building users during occupancy hours, according to the best practices and technologies available today and in line with the European and national regulatory requirements.

The suppliers are requested to assess and provide air quality conditions values at least in terms of ppm of CO₂ and provide the number of hours above the threshold of 1000 ppm CO₂. The suppliers are requested to provide descriptions of the calculation method and the adopted boundary conditions, together with the results obtained as part of the deliverables at the end of each design phase.

Assessment: The procurers will use the average CO₂ value and the total number of hours during which CO₂-threshold is being exceeded for the quantitative assessment of the system performance, and the hourly distribution to check how continuous achieved conditions are.

Lighting conditions (IEQ_LC)

Suppliers are requested to assure that comfortable lighting conditions are delivered to the building users during occupancy hours, according to the best practices and technologies available today and the European and national regulatory requirements.

The suppliers are requested to assess and provide illuminance values in lux (cd/m²), UGR (Unified Glare Index) and CRI (Colour Rendering Index) at representative working/training places. Both dynamic simulations and semi-dynamic methods, accounting for coupled artificial and natural lighting effects and for automated controls and accepted by European norms are acceptable calculation methods. The suppliers are requested to provide indication on the calculation method and the boundary conditions adopted, together with the results obtained as part of the deliverables at the end of each design phase.

Environmental Key Performance Indicators

CO₂ emissions during operation (E_CO2)

The performance indicator relates on the carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions of the proposed retrofit solution during building operation; the emissions values are to be computed based on the net final energy drawn from energy networks. For each energy vector imported on site, the suppliers are requested to use CO₂ emission factors derived from the most recent Covenant of Mayors (CoM) Emission Factors¹⁵. During the proposal, the most recent default values are to be used. During the

¹⁵ [Joint Research Centre Data Catalogue - CoM Default Emission Factors - European Commission \(europa.eu\)](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/tgm/table.do?tab=table&init=1&language=en&code=ts0000011)

project, national emission values reported in the CoM resource for each Demonstration Site are to be used.

Assessment: The procurers will use the total from all vectors for the quantitative assessment of the system performance.